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Empowering a Sustainable Future In the form of «Turquoise Modality»; The Comprehensive Integration of Renewable Energies in Everyday Life

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Abstract

The comprehensive modality of using renewable energies in everyday life embodies a paradigm shift towards a sustainable and eco-conscious lifestyle. It involves the adoption and integration of various renewable energy sources, such as solar power, wind energy, and geothermal heat, to power our homes, transportation systems, and industries. This abstract examines the key elements of this modality, exploring its potential benefits, challenges, and the transformative impact it can have on society. By transitioning away from fossil fuels and embracing renewable energy, we can mitigate climate change, reduce dependence on finite resources, and create a more harmonious and resilient future for generations to come. This article delves into specific strategies, policy implications, and technological advancements required to enable widespread adoption of renewable energies in everyday life. It highlights the need for comprehensive education and awareness campaigns to encourage behavioral change and empower individuals to actively participate in this energy transition. Ultimately, this abstract aims to inspire and guide individuals, communities, and policymakers to embrace the comprehensive modality of using renewable energies, fostering a sustainable and thriving planet for future generations.

Keywords: Renewable energy, green energy, new energy, energy, solar energy, wind energy, geothermal energy, biofuel energy, biomass energy, water energy, sustainable development, solar cells, perovskite, oil, gas, fuel Fossils, global warming, Paris Agreement

Introduction

Renewable energy is energy that is collected from renewable resources that are naturally replenished on a human timescale. It includes sources such as sunlight, wind, rain, tides, waves, and geothermal heat. Renewable energy stands in contrast to fossil fuels, which are being used far more quickly than they are being replenished. Although most renewable energy sources are sustainable, some are not. For example, some biomass sources are considered unsustainable at current rates of exploitation. Renewable energy often provides energy in four important areas: electricity generation, air and water heating/cooling, transportation, and rural (off-grid) energy services. About 20% of humans' global energy consumption is renewables, including almost 30% of electricity. About 8% of energy consumption is traditional biomass, but this is declining. Over 4% of energy consumption is heat energy from modern renewables, such as solar water heating, and over 6% electricity.

Globally there are over 10 million jobs associated with the renewable energy industries, with solar photovoltaics being the largest renewable employer. Renewable energy systems are rapidly becoming more efficient and cheaper and their share of total energy consumption is increasing, with a large majority of worldwide newly installed electricity capacity being renewable. In most countries, photovoltaic solar or onshore wind are the cheapest new-build electricity. Many nations around the world already have renewable energy contributing more than 20% of their energy supply, with some generating over half their electricity from renewables. National renewable energy markets are projected to continue to grow strongly in the 2020s and beyond. A few countries generate all their electricity using renewable energy. Renewable energy resources exist over wide geographical areas, in contrast to fossil fuels, which are concentrated in a limited number of countries. Deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies is resulting in significant energy security, climate change mitigation, and economic benefits. However renewables are being hindered by hundreds of billions of dollars of fossil fuel subsidies. In international public opinion surveys

there is strong support for promoting renewable sources such as solar power and wind power.

Renewable energy technology projects are typically large-scale, but they are also suited to rural and remote areas and developing countries, where energy is often crucial in human development. As most of the renewable energy technologies provide electricity, renewable energy is often deployed together with further electrification, which has several benefits: electricity can be converted to heat, can be converted into mechanical energy with high efficiency, and is clean at the point of consumption. In addition, electrification with renewable energy is more efficient and therefore leads to significant reductions in primary energy requirements. In 2021, China accounted for almost half of the increase in renewable electricity. In 2021, Norway, known for its production of hydroelectricity, consumed hydro energy worth 45% of its total energy supply.

Renewable power is booming, as innovation brings down costs and starts to deliver on the promise of a clean energy future. American solar and wind generation are breaking records and being integrated into the national electricity grid without compromising reliability.

This means that renewables are increasingly displacing “dirty” fossil fuels in the power sector, offering the benefit of lower emissions of carbon and other types of pollution. But not all sources of energy marketed as “renewable” are beneficial to the environment. Biomass and large hydroelectric dams create difficult tradeoffs when considering the impact on wildlife, climate change, and other issues. Here's what you should know about the different types of renewable energy sources and how you can use these emerging technologies at your own home.

What Is Renewable Energy?

Renewable energy, often referred to as clean energy, comes from natural sources or processes that are constantly replenished. For example, sunlight or wind keep shining and blowing, even if their availability depends on time and weather. While renewable energy is often thought of as a new technology, harnessing nature's power has long been used for heating, transportation, lighting, and more. Wind has powered boats to sail the seas and windmills to grind grain. The sun has provided warmth during the day and helped kindle fires to last

into the evening. But over the past 500 years or so, humans increasingly turned to cheaper, dirtier energy sources such as coal and fracked gas. Now that we have increasingly innovative and less-expensive ways to capture and retain wind and solar energy, renewables are becoming a more important power source, accounting for more than one-eighth of U.S. generation. The expansion in renewables is also happening at scales large and small, from rooftop solar panels on homes that can sell power back to the grid to giant offshore wind farms. Even some entire rural communities rely on renewable energy for heating and lighting. As renewable use continues to grow, a key goal will be to modernize America's electricity grid, making it smarter, more secure, and better integrated across regions.

Dirty energy

Nonrenewable, or "dirty," energy includes fossil fuels such as oil, gas, and coal. Nonrenewable sources of energy are only available in limited amounts and take a long time to replenish. When we pump gas at the station, we're using a finite resource refined from crude oil that's been around since prehistoric times. Nonrenewable energy sources are also typically found in specific parts of the world, making them more plentiful in some nations than others. By contrast, every country has access to sunshine and wind. Prioritizing nonrenewable energy can also improve national security by reducing a country's reliance on exports from fossil fuel-rich nations. Many nonrenewable energy sources can endanger the environment or human health. For example, oil drilling might require strip-mining Canada's boreal forest, the technology associated with fracking can cause earthquakes and water pollution, and coal power plants foul the air. To top it off, all these activities contribute to global warming.

Overview

Coal, oil, and natural gas remain the primary global energy sources even as renewables have begun rapidly increasing. Planet Solar, the world's largest solar-powered boat and the first ever solar electric vehicle to circumnavigate the globe (in 2012). Renewable energy flows involve natural phenomena such as sunlight, wind, tides, plant growth, and geothermal heat, as the International Energy Agency

explains: Renewable energy is derived from natural processes that are replenished constantly. In its various forms, it derives directly from the sun, or from heat generated deep within the earth. Included in the definition is electricity and heat generated from solar, wind, ocean, hydropower, biomass, geothermal resources, and biofuels and hydrogen derived from renewable resources. Renewable energy resources and significant opportunities for energy efficiency exist over wide geographical areas, in contrast to other energy sources, which are concentrated in a limited number of countries. Rapid deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency, and technological diversification of energy sources, would result in significant energy security and economic benefits. It would also reduce environmental pollution such as air pollution caused by the burning of fossil fuels, and improve public health, reduce premature mortalities due to pollution and save associated health costs that could amount to trillions of dollars annually. Multiple analyses of de-carbonization strategies have found that quantified health benefits can significantly offset the costs of implementing these strategies. Renewable energy sources, that derive their energy from the sun, either directly or indirectly, such as hydro and wind, are expected to be capable of supplying humanity energy for almost another 1 billion years, at which point the predicted increase in heat from the Sun is expected to make the surface of the Earth too hot for liquid water to exist. Climate change and global warming concerns, coupled with the continuing fall in the costs of some renewable energy equipment, such as wind turbines and solar panels, are driving increased use of renewables. New government spending, regulation and policies helped the industry weather the global financial crisis better than many other sectors. As of 2019, however, according to the International Renewable Energy Agency, renewables overall share in the energy mix (including power, heat and transport) needs to grow six times faster, in order to keep the rise in average global temperatures "well below" 2.0 °C (3.6 °F) during the present century, compared to pre-industrial levels. As of 2011, small solar PV systems provide electricity to a few million households, and micro-hydro configured into mini-grids serves many more.[needs update] Over 44 million households use biogas made in household-

scale digesters for lighting and/or cooking, and more than 166 million households rely on a new generation of more-efficient biomass cook stoves. United Nations' eighth Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon has said that renewable energy has the ability to lift the poorest nations to new levels of prosperity. At the national level, at least 30 nations around the world already have renewable energy contributing more than 20% of energy supply. National renewable energy markets are projected to continue to grow strongly in the coming decade and beyond, and some 120 countries have various policy targets for longer-term shares of renewable energy, including a 20% target of all electricity generated for the European Union by 2020.[needs update] Some countries have much higher long-term policy targets of up to 100% renewables. Outside Europe, a diverse group of 20 or more other countries targets renewable energy shares in the 2020–2030 time frame that range from 10% to 50%. Renewable energy often displaces conventional fuels in four areas: electricity generation, hot water/space heating, transportation, and rural (off-grid) energy services:

✓ Power generation

By 2040, renewable energy is projected to equal coal and natural gas electricity generation. Several jurisdictions, including Denmark, Germany, the state of South Australia and some US states have achieved high integration of variable renewables. For example, in 2015 wind power met 42% of electricity demand in Denmark, 23.2% in Portugal and 15.5% in Uruguay. Interconnectors enable countries to balance electricity systems by allowing the import and export of renewable energy. Innovative hybrid systems have emerged between countries and regions.

✓ Heating

Solar water heating makes an important contribution to renewable heat in many countries, most notably in China, which now has 70% of the global total (180 GWth). Most of these systems are installed on multi-family apartment buildings and meet a portion of the hot water needs of an estimated 50–60 million households in China. Worldwide, total installed solar water heating systems meet a portion of the water heating needs of over 70 million households.

The use of biomass for heating continues to grow as well. In Sweden, national use of biomass energy has surpassed that of oil. Direct geothermal for heating is also growing rapidly. The newest addition to heating is from geothermal heat pumps which provide both heating and cooling, and also flatten the electric demand curve and are thus an increasing national priority.

✓ Transportation

Bioethanol is an alcohol made by fermentation, mostly from carbohydrates produced in sugar or starch crops such as corn, sugarcane, or sweet sorghum. Cellulosic biomass, derived from non-food sources such as trees and grasses is also being developed as a feedstock for ethanol production. Ethanol can be used as a fuel for vehicles in its pure form, but it is usually used as a gasoline additive to increase octane and improve vehicle emissions. Bioethanol is widely used in the USA and in Brazil. Biodiesel can be used as a fuel for vehicles in its pure form, but it is usually used as a diesel additive to reduce levels of particulates, carbon monoxide, and hydrocarbons from diesel-powered vehicles. Biodiesel is produced from oils or fats using transesterification and is the most common biofuel in Europe.

✓ A solar vehicle is an electric vehicle powered completely or significantly by direct solar energy. Usually, photovoltaic (PV) cells contained in solar panels convert the sun's energy directly into electric energy. The term "solar vehicle" usually implies that solar energy is used to power all or part of a vehicle's propulsion. Solar power may be also used to provide power for communications or controls or other auxiliary functions. Solar vehicles are not sold as practical day-to-day transportation devices at present but are primarily demonstration vehicles and engineering exercises, often sponsored by government agencies. High-profile examples include Planet Solar and Solar Impulse. However, indirectly solar-charged vehicles are widespread and solar boats are available commercially.

History

Prior to the development of coal in the mid-19th century, nearly all energy used was renewable. The oldest known use of renewable energy, in the form of traditional biomass to fuel fires, dates from more

than a million years ago. The use of biomass for fire did not become commonplace until many hundreds of thousands of years later. Probably the second oldest usage of renewable energy is harnessing the wind in order to drive ships over water. This practice can be traced back some 7000 years, to ships in the Persian Gulf and on the Nile. From hot springs, geothermal energy has been used for bathing since Paleolithic times and for space heating since ancient Roman times. Moving into the time of recorded history, the primary sources of traditional renewable energy were human labor, animal power, water power, and wind, in grain crushing windmills, and firewood, a traditional biomass.

In the 1860s and 1870s, there were already fears that civilization would run out of fossil fuels and the need was felt for a better source. In 1873 Augustin Mouchot wrote: The time will arrive when the industry of Europe will cease to find those natural resources, so necessary for it. Petroleum springs and coal mines are not inexhaustible but are rapidly diminishing in many places. Will man, then, return to the power of water and wind? Or will he emigrate where the most powerful source of heat sends its rays to all? History will show what will come. In 1885, Werner von Siemens, commenting on the discovery of the photovoltaic effect in the solid state, wrote: In conclusion, I would say that however great the scientific importance of this discovery may be, its practical value will be no less obvious when we reflect that the supply of solar energy is both without limit and without cost, and that it will continue to pour down upon us for countless ages after all the coal deposits of the earth have been exhausted and forgotten.

Max Weber mentioned the end of fossil fuel in the concluding paragraphs of his *Die protestantische Ethik und der Geist des Kapitalismus* (The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism), published in 1905. Development of solar engines continued until the outbreak of World War I. The importance of solar energy was recognized in a 1911 *Scientific American* article: "in the far distant future, natural fuels having been exhausted [solar power] will remain as the only means of existence of the human race".

The theory of peak oil was published in 1956. In the 1970s environmentalists promoted the development of renewable energy both as a replacement for the

eventual depletion of oil, as well as for an escape from dependence on oil, and the first electricity-generating wind turbines appeared. Solar had long been used for heating and cooling, but solar panels were too costly to build solar farms until 1980. Since the 21st century, many parts of the world have transitioned to sources of renewable energy from fossil fuels.

Mainstream technologies

Hydropower

Since water is about 800 times denser than air, even a slow flowing stream of water, or moderate sea swell, can yield considerable amounts of energy. There are many forms of water energy: Historically, hydroelectric power came from constructing large hydroelectric dams and reservoirs, which are still popular in developing countries. The largest of them are the Three Gorges Dam (2003) in China and the Itaipu Dam (1984) built by Brazil and Paraguay. Small hydro systems are hydroelectric power installations that typically produce up to 50 MW of power. They are often used on small rivers or as a low-impact development on larger rivers. China is the largest producer of hydroelectricity in the world and has more than 45,000 small hydro installations. Run-of-the-river hydroelectricity plants derive energy from rivers without the creation of a large reservoir. The water is typically conveyed along the side of the river valley (using channels, pipes and/or tunnels) until it is high above the valley floor, whereupon it can be allowed to fall through a penstock to drive a turbine. This style of generation may still produce a large amount of electricity, such as the Chief Joseph Dam on the Columbia River in the United States. Many run-of-the-river hydro power plants are micro hydro or pico hydro plants. Hydropower is produced in 150 countries, with the Asia-Pacific region generating 32 percent of global hydropower in 2010. Of the top 50 countries by percentage of electricity generated from renewables, 46 are primarily hydroelectric. China is the largest hydroelectricity producer, with 721 terawatt-hours of production in 2010, representing around 17 percent of domestic electricity use. There are now three hydroelectricity stations larger than 10 GW: the Three Gorges Dam in China, Itaipu Dam across the Brazil/Paraguay border, and Guri Dam in Venezuela. Wave power, which captures the energy

of ocean surface waves, and tidal power, converting the energy of tides, are two forms of hydropower with future potential; however, they are not yet widely employed commercially. According to the Energy Information Administration, the theoretical annual energy potential of waves off the coasts of the United States is estimated to be as much as 2.64 trillion kilowatt-hours, or the equivalent of about 66% of U.S. electricity generation in 2020. A demonstration project operated by the Ocean Renewable Power Company on the coast of Maine, and connected to the grid, harnesses tidal power from the Bay of Fundy, location of the world's highest tidal flow. Ocean thermal energy conversion, which uses the temperature difference between cooler deep and warmer surface waters, currently has no economic feasibility.

Air flow can be used to run wind turbines. Modern utility-scale wind turbines range from around 600 kW to 9 MW of rated power. The power available from the wind is a function of the cube of the wind speed, so as wind speed increases, power output increases up to the maximum output for the particular turbine. Areas where winds are stronger and more constant, such as offshore and high-altitude sites, are preferred locations for wind farms. Typically, full load hours of wind turbines vary between 16 and 57 percent annually but might be higher in particularly favorable offshore sites. Wind-generated electricity met nearly 4% of global electricity demand in 2015, with nearly 63 GW of new wind power capacity installed. Wind energy was the leading source of new capacity in Europe, the US and Canada, and the second largest in China. In Denmark, wind energy met more than 40% of its electricity demand while Ireland, Portugal and Spain each met nearly 20%. Globally, the long-term technical potential of wind energy is believed to be five times total current global energy production, or 40 times current electricity demand, assuming all practical barriers needed were overcome. This would require wind turbines to be installed over large areas, particularly in areas of higher wind resources, such as offshore. As offshore wind speeds average ~90% greater than that of land, so offshore resources can contribute substantially more energy than land-stationed turbines.

Types of renewable energy

What is a renewable energy source?

A renewable energy source means energy that is sustainable - something that can't run out, or is endless, like the sun. When you hear the term 'alternative energy' it's usually referring to renewable energy sources too. It means sources of energy that are alternative to the most commonly used non-sustainable sources - like coal.

What is zero-carbon or low-carbon energy?

Nuclear-generated electricity isn't renewable but its zero-carbon, which means its generation emits low levels or almost no CO₂, just like renewable energy sources. Nuclear energy has a stable source, which means it's not dependent on the weather and will play a big part in getting Britain to net zero status.

1. Solar energy
2. Wind energy
3. Hydro energy
4. Geothermal energy
5. Biomass energy

Solar energy

Solar energy, radiant light and heat from the sun, is harnessed using a range of ever-evolving technologies such as solar heating, photovoltaics, concentrated solar power (CSP), concentrator photovoltaics (CPV), solar architecture and artificial photosynthesis. Solar technologies are broadly characterized as either passive solar or active solar depending on the way they capture, convert, and distribute solar energy. Passive solar techniques include orienting a building to the Sun, selecting materials with favorable thermal mass or light dispersing properties, and designing spaces that naturally circulate air. Active solar technologies encompass solar thermal energy, using solar collectors for heating, and solar power, converting sunlight into electricity either directly using photovoltaics (PV), or indirectly using concentrated solar power (CSP).

A photovoltaic system converts light into electrical direct current (DC) by taking advantage of the photoelectric effect. Solar PV has turned into a multi-billion, fast-growing industry, continues to improve its cost-effectiveness, and has the most potential of any renewable technologies together with CSP. Concentrated solar power (CSP) systems

use lenses or mirrors and tracking systems to focus a large area of sunlight into a small beam. Commercial concentrated solar power plants were first developed in the 1980s. CSP-Stirling has by far the highest efficiency among all solar energy technologies.

In 2011, the International Energy Agency said that "the development of affordable, inexhaustible and clean solar energy technologies will have huge longer-term benefits. It will increase countries' energy security through reliance on an indigenous, inexhaustible and mostly import-independent resource, enhance sustainability, reduce pollution, lower the costs of mitigating climate change, and keep fossil fuel prices lower than otherwise. These advantages are global. Hence the additional costs of the incentives for early deployment should be considered learning investments; they must be wisely spent and need to be widely shared". Solar power accounts for 505 GW annually, which is about 2% of the world's electricity. Solar energy can be harnessed anywhere that receives sunlight; however, the amount of solar energy that can be harnessed for electricity generation is influenced by weather conditions, geographic location and time of day. Australia has the largest proportion of solar electricity in the world, supplying 9.9% of the country's electrical demand in 2020.

Bioenergy

Biomass is biological material derived from living, or recently living organisms. It most often refers to plants or plant-derived materials which are specifically called lignocellulosic biomass. As an energy source, biomass can either be used directly via combustion to produce heat, or indirectly after converting it to various forms of biofuel. Conversion of biomass to biofuel can be achieved by different methods which are broadly classified into: thermal, chemical, and biochemical methods. Wood was the largest biomass energy source as of 2012; examples include forest residues – such as dead trees, branches and tree stumps –, yard clippings, wood chips and even municipal solid waste. In the second sense, biomass includes plant or animal matter that can be converted into fibers or other industrial chemicals, including biofuels. Industrial biomass can be grown from numerous types of plants, including miscanthus, switchgrass, hemp, corn, poplar,

willow, sorghum, sugarcane, bamboo and a variety of tree species, ranging from eucalyptus to oil palm (palm oil). Plant energy is produced by crops specifically grown for use as fuel that offer high biomass output per hectare with low input energy. The grain can be used for liquid transportation fuels while the straw can be burned to produce heat or electricity. Plant biomass can also be degraded from cellulose to glucose through a series of chemical treatments, and the resulting sugar can then be used as a first-generation biofuel. Biomass can be converted to other usable forms of energy such as methane gas or transportation fuels such as ethanol and biodiesel. Rotting garbage, and agricultural and human waste, all release methane gas – also called landfill gas or biogas. Crops, such as corn and sugarcane, can be fermented to produce the transportation fuel, ethanol. Biodiesel, another transportation fuel, can be produced from left-over food products such as vegetable oils and animal fats. Also, biomass to liquids (BTLs) and cellulosic ethanol are still under research. There is a great deal of research involving algal fuel or algae-derived biomass due to the fact that it is a non-food resource and can be produced at rates 5 to 10 times those of other types of land-based agriculture, such as corn and soy. Once harvested, it can be fermented to produce biofuels such as ethanol, butanol, and methane, as well as biodiesel and hydrogen. The biomass used for electricity generation varies by region. Forest by-products, such as wood residues, are common in the United States. Agricultural waste is common in Mauritius (sugar cane residue) and Southeast Asia (rice husks). Animal husbandry residues, such as poultry litter, are common in the United Kingdom. Biofuels include a wide range of fuels which are derived from biomass. The term covers solid, liquid, and gaseous fuels. Liquid biofuels include bioalcohols, such as bioethanol, and oils, such as biodiesel. Gaseous biofuels include biogas, landfill gas and synthetic gas. Bioethanol is an alcohol made by fermenting the sugar components of plant materials and it is made mostly from sugar and starch crops. These include maize, sugarcane and, more recently, sweet sorghum. The latter crop is particularly suitable for growing in dryland conditions, and is being investigated by International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics for its potential to provide fuel, along

with food and animal feed, in arid parts of Asia and Africa. With advanced technology being developed, cellulosic biomass, such as trees and grasses, are also used as feedstocks for ethanol production. Ethanol can be used as a fuel for vehicles in its pure form, but it is usually used as a gasoline additive to increase octane and improve vehicle emissions. Bioethanol is widely used in the United States and in Brazil. The energy costs for producing bioethanol are almost equal to, the energy yields from bio-ethanol. However, according to the European Environment Agency, biofuels do not address global warming concerns. Biodiesel is made from vegetable oils, animal fats or recycled greases. It can be used as a fuel for vehicles in its pure form, or more commonly as a diesel additive to reduce levels of particulates, carbon monoxide, and hydrocarbons from diesel-powered vehicles. Biodiesel is produced from oils or fats using trans-esterification and is the most common biofuel in Europe. Biofuels provided 2.7% of the world's transport fuel in 2010. Biomass, biogas and biofuels are burned to produce heat/power and in doing so harm the environment. Pollutants such as sulphurous oxides (SO_x), nitrous oxides (NO_x), and particulate matter (PM) are produced from the combustion of biomass. The World Health Organization estimates that 3.7 million prematurely died from outdoor air pollution in 2012 while indoor pollution from biomass burning effects over 3 billion people worldwide.

Geothermal energy

High temperature geothermal energy is from thermal energy generated and stored in the Earth. Thermal energy is the energy that determines the temperature of matter. Earth's geothermal energy originates from the original formation of the planet and from radioactive decay of minerals (in currently uncertain but possibly roughly equal proportions). The geothermal gradient, which is the difference in temperature between the core of the planet and its surface, drives a continuous conduction of thermal energy in the form of heat from the core to the surface. The adjective geothermal originates from the Greek roots *geo*, meaning earth, and *thermos*, meaning heat. The heat that is used for geothermal energy can be from deep within the Earth, all the way down to Earth's core – 4,000 miles (6,400 km) down. At the core, temperatures may reach over

9,000 °F (5,000 °C). Heat conducts from the core to the surrounding rock. Extremely high temperature and pressure cause some rock to melt, which is commonly known as magma. Magma convects upward since it is lighter than the solid rock. This magma then heats rock and water in the crust, sometimes up to 700 °F (371 °C). Low temperature geothermal refers to the use of the outer crust of the Earth as a thermal battery to facilitate renewable thermal energy for heating and cooling buildings, and other refrigeration and industrial uses. In this form of geothermal, a geothermal heat pump and ground-coupled heat exchanger are used together to move heat energy into the Earth (for cooling) and out of the Earth (for heating) on a varying seasonal basis. Low-temperature geothermal (generally referred to as "GHP") is an increasingly important renewable technology because it both reduces total annual energy loads associated with heating and cooling, and it also flattens the electric demand curve eliminating the extreme summer and winter peak electric supply requirements. Thus low temperature geothermal/GHP is becoming an increasing national priority with multiple tax credit support and focus as part of the ongoing movement toward net zero energy.

Emerging technologies

There are also other renewable energy technologies that are still under development, including cellulosic ethanol, hot-dry-rock geothermal power, and marine energy. These technologies are not yet widely demonstrated or have limited commercialization. Many are on the horizon and may have potential comparable to other renewable energy technologies, but still depend on attracting sufficient attention and research, development and demonstration (RD&D) funding. There are numerous organizations within the academic, federal, and commercial sectors conducting large-scale advanced research in the field of renewable energy. This research spans several areas of focus across the renewable energy spectrum. Most of the research is targeted at improving efficiency and increasing overall energy yields. Multiple federally supported research organizations have focused on renewable energy in recent years. Two of the most prominent of these labs are Sandia National Laboratories and the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL),

both of which are funded by the United States Department of Energy and supported by various corporate partners. Sandia has a total budget of \$2.4 billion while NREL has a budget of \$375 million.

Enhanced geothermal system

Enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) are a new type of geothermal power technology that does not require natural convective hydrothermal resources. The vast majority of geothermal energy within drilling reach is in dry and non-porous rock. EGS technologies "enhance" and/or create geothermal resources in this "hot dry rock (HDR)" through hydraulic fracturing. EGS and HDR technologies, such as hydrothermal geothermal, are expected to be baseload resources that produce power 24 hours a day like a fossil plant. Distinct from hydrothermal, HDR and EGS may be feasible anywhere in the world, depending on the economic limits of drill depth. Good locations are over deep granite covered by a thick (3–5 km) layer of insulating sediments which slow heat loss. There are HDR and EGS systems currently being developed and tested in France, Australia, Japan, Germany, the U.S., and Switzerland. The largest EGS project in the world is a 25 megawatt demonstration plant currently being developed in the Cooper Basin, Australia. The Cooper Basin has the potential to generate 5,000–10,000 MW.

Cellulosic ethanol

Several refineries that can process biomass and turn it into ethanol are built by companies such as Iogen, POET, and Abengoa, while other companies such as the Verenium Corporation, Novozymes, and Dyadic International are producing enzymes which could enable future commercialization. The shift from food crop feedstocks to waste residues and native grasses offers significant opportunities for a range of players, from farmers to biotechnology firms, and from project developers to investors.

Marine energy

Marine energy (also sometimes referred to as ocean energy) is the energy carried by ocean waves, tides, salinity, and ocean temperature differences. The movement of water in the world's oceans creates a vast store of kinetic energy, or energy in motion. This energy can be harnessed to generate electricity

to power homes, transport and industries. The term marine energy encompasses both wave power – power from surface waves, and tidal power – obtained from the kinetic energy of large bodies of moving water. Reverse electro-dialysis (RED) is a technology for generating electricity by mixing fresh river water and salty sea water in large power cells designed for this purpose; as of 2016, it is being tested at a small scale (50 kW). Offshore wind power is not a form of marine energy, as wind power is derived from the wind, even if the wind turbines are placed over water. The oceans have a tremendous amount of energy and are close to many if not most concentrated populations. Ocean energy has the potential of providing a substantial amount of new renewable energy around the world.

Why is Renewable Energy Important?

We're now facing unprecedented heatwaves, polluted air, and unbelievable health issues caused by fossil fuels. In addition to this issue, fossil fuels are about to run out if we continue to burn them uncontrollably. Renewable energy sources are our best chance to stop the current trend and make the world a better place to live. Therefore, governments are thinking of using renewable sources of energy to generate electric power. As a result, there is increasing usage of renewable energy for generating electricity in all countries.

For example, the share of renewable energy in global electricity generation was increased to 29% in 2020. This is a success compared with a 27% share in electricity generation in 2019.

Some advanced countries such as the UK have aimed for 100% renewable cities by 2050. Currently, around 43% of the UK's electricity is generated by renewables. In spite of many obstacles in the way towards 100% renewable energy, there are promising advantages to using renewable technologies. Overall, the advantages of using renewable energy sources outweigh the disadvantages. Although the initial cost of establishing a network of renewable technologies might be higher, over time, the expenses will be offset. Considering the lateral influencers of using renewable energy, postponing the process of shifting toward 100% renewable is not a wise course of action. Wind, geothermal, solar, hydro, tidal, hydrogen, and other renewable technologies are a

widely popular source of energy throughout the world today. Countries, corporations, and individuals are adopting renewables for a number of great benefits. In this article, we'll dive into some of the advantages and disadvantages of renewable energy.

In the following, we will examine the various aspects of the presence of renewable energy in daily and urban life.

Fig1. Solar panels on the roof of the Tate Modern in London

Directors, curators, and professionals from institutions around the world have agreed on a minimum plan to boost environmental friendliness in art centers by cutting travel and supporting energy efficiency.

In July 2019, Tate (the four museums that make up the ensemble – Britain, Modern, Liverpool and St-Ives) called on the art world to champion environmental protection and set itself the ambitious target of reducing its gas emissions by 50% by 2023. To date, that goal has already been surpassed, with a 56% reduction in the last two years. The pandemic outbreak and the museums' closure have contributed to a worldwide decrease in emissions and provided a unique opportunity for the industry to reflect deeply on how to approach reopening by including a well-defined plan for environmental sustainability.

CIMAM – an international organization focused on contemporary art that brings together 600 professionals from 86 countries– has reached a minimum agreement to promote environmentally-friendly policies in art centers at its last annual meeting. Those advisable minimums are the basic tools that some museums have already started to use – in Germany and France, with the United Kingdom

in the lead–, with an intensity limited only by the economic autonomy of each center. European funds earmarked for digital and ecological transformation will accelerate a process that keeps most of the national museums in a critical situation (16 state institutions and 60 with transferred management) in Spain. What is meant by becoming a green museum is not clear to many. It is very well clarified by Frances Morris, director of Tate Modern since 2016, chair of CIMAM's Sustainability and Ecology group. Morris explains by email that there is no time to waste and details the measures she has implemented at Tate Modern in getting it to go green. It's 330 solar panels produce 100% renewable energy (the energy generated could power 12 homes for a year). They have installed energy-efficient LED lighting throughout the galleries. Annually about 226 cubic meters of collected rainwater is used for flushing toilets. They reuse and recycle 75% of the waste, and also, among other measures, since 2014, they started to reduce non-essential business trips.

The proposals promoted by CIMAM go much further and affect the internal governance of each museum. The international organization not only asks that air travel be reduced to a minimum but also pronounces itself against the mobility of the works and recommends that if they have to be moved as part of temporary exhibitions, it should be done without the accompaniment of experts who for decades have guarded the work from its place of departure to its destination. Monitoring can be done through new digital programs that were successfully launched after the first confinements imposed by Covid. CIMAM also advises that museums should prioritize their permanent collections and that temporary exhibitions should be reduced and the time they are on display extended. It also asks that partition panels and packing boxes should always be reusable.

Vegetarian menus

Consumption inside museums will undergo another of the most important changes in the transformation plan promoted by CIMAN. It affects restaurants, food, and beverage outlets in the art centers. The proposal puts forward the total disappearance of plastic bottled beverages. The proposal is to place water jugs on the tables and water fountains at

different points along the route. Visitors can bring a reusable container that can be refilled. In the wake of what some German museums are already doing, it is advised to include only vegetarian food in the menus.

Mami Kataoka, director of the Mori Art Museum in Tokyo and President of CIMAM, says by e-mail that all these measures are immediately applicable to the museum community. She does not believe that it is necessary to wait for governments to undertake them. "The commitment to sustainability in the art world has been the subject of debate in recent years, but radical changes have been forced and accelerated due to the pandemic. Seizing this opportunity, we must engage with the entire art industry, including art institutions, galleries, and artists, to pursue a new ecology. We have a toolkit ready to be applied."

Joseph Beuys, pioneering artist

On the role of artists in this green transformation, Frances Morris recalls that there is a long history of creative engagement in the face of the climate emergency: from the pioneering work of Joseph Beuys, who was a founding member of the German Green Party, to the current younger generation of artists who feel passionately that culture has a role to play in inspiring the struggle in the ecological arena. "At Tate," Morris explains, "our declaration of climate and ecological emergency was encouraged by artists in the UK who were looking to us to push not just carbon emission reduction measures, but to address a much broader sustainability agenda. So, we have not responded by simply trying to achieve a more radical cut in emissions, but we are thinking about the systems and frameworks in which we operate. Using our international art collection we can demonstrate how artists, over time, have responded to the intersecting emergencies of climate, ecology, race, and social justice."

As evidence of the impact that ecological concern has already had on Tate Modern's programming, Morris points to a temporary show currently on view. *A Year in Art: Australia 1992*, with works by Judy Watson and Bonita Ely, examines the disregard for traditional land rights by allowing mining operations that have fueled climate degradation for centuries. In addition, the center has a gallery in its

collection dedicated to Photography and the Environment with works by artists such as Chris Killip, Simryn Gill, and Jem Southam, who captured the environmental and human impact of industrial activity on the natural world.

The Reina Sofia, paper-free

In Spain, the Reina Sofia has long been working on its own ecological transition. The 36 million euros it will receive in its budget over the next three years, part of which will come from European funds, will be used to develop the plans of its director, Manuel Borja-Villel. On the one hand, the center will transform its headquarters to become sustainable and autonomous. At present, the Palacio de Velázquez is self-sufficient in energy maintenance. There is also a digital transformation underway that will allow access to all of the Museum's around 7,000 works onscreen, negating the former necessity to physically search through the storerooms. "When I arrived at the Museum in 2008," recalls the director, "there was so much paper that it was transported through the offices in supermarket carts. Now almost all communication is digital, like our network of archives and libraries."

The Reina Sofia reopened after the pandemic with an international exhibition, *Mondrian and De Stijl*, for which people no longer escorted the works as couriers, with the corresponding elimination of travel, along with the use of reusable panels. "The digital will never supplant the face-to-face," predicts Borja Villel, "and that's why we want it to be a museum of knowledge with exchanges, scholarships and residencies. It will also be a solidarity museum focused on our closest environment (Madrid's Lavapiés neighborhood) and collaborating with initiatives imbricated in its surroundings such as [the social centers] *La Ingovernable* or *La Invisible*. The art system as we knew it was a bubble that turned us into cultural nomads. The idea of the Golden Mile of Art cannot make us forget the environment in which we live."

Empowering Libraries with Solar Energy: An Overdue Enlightenment

To address these issues, libraries are now turning to solar energy as a sustainable solution to power their operations. In this article, we will explore how solar energy can empower libraries, shedding light on the

numerous benefits it brings to these essential community hubs.

The Power of Solar Energy

Solar energy is a clean, renewable, and abundant source of power that harnesses the remarkable capabilities of the sun. With the advancements in solar technology and decreasing costs, libraries can now leverage solar energy to meet their electricity needs efficiently. Here are some key advantages:

- ✓ **Sustainable and Environmentally Friendly:** Solar energy produces electricity without greenhouse gas emissions, reducing libraries' carbon footprints and contributing to a greener future.
- ✓ **Cost Savings:** Installing solar panels can significantly reduce libraries' electricity bills, enabling them to allocate more funds towards enhancing their resources and services for the community.
- ✓ **Energy Independence:** By producing their own electricity, libraries become less dependent on the traditional power grid, ensuring continuous operations even during power outages or emergencies.
- ✓ **Long-Term Investment:** Solar panels have a lifespan of several decades, making them a durable and cost-effective investment for libraries to secure their energy needs for the long term.

Implementing Solar Energy in Libraries

Transitioning to solar energy requires careful planning and execution. Libraries must evaluate their energy requirements, assess the feasibility of solar panel installation, and secure the necessary funding. Collaborating with experienced solar energy providers is crucial for a successful transition. Here are some steps libraries can follow:

1. **Energy Audit:** Conduct a comprehensive assessment of the library's energy consumption to determine the potential size and capacity of the solar energy system required.
2. **Professional Consultation:** Seek advice from reputable solar energy installers who specialize in working with libraries and can provide tailored solutions based on the library's specific needs and available space.

3. **Funding Opportunities:** Explore grants, incentives, and financing options for solar installations that are often available for libraries, helping to reduce the upfront costs associated with the project.
4. **Design and Installation:** Collaborate with solar energy providers to design and install a solar panel system that maximizes energy generation while considering the library's architectural aesthetics.
5. **Monitoring and Maintenance:** Regularly monitor the performance of the solar panels and conduct necessary maintenance to ensure optimal energy production and system longevity.

The Role of Solar-Powered Libraries

Libraries powered by solar energy play a significant role in their communities beyond being sources of knowledge. Here are some key takeaways:

- ❖ **Community Education:** Solar-powered libraries can educate visitors about the importance of renewable energy, inspiring sustainable practices in the community.
- ❖ **Resilience and Emergency Preparedness:** During natural disasters or power outages, solar-powered libraries can serve as vital community centers, providing shelter, power, and access to critical resources.
- ❖ **Demonstrating Sustainable Solutions:** By embracing solar energy, libraries set an example for other institutions and community members, encouraging the adoption of environmentally friendly practices.

According to recent statistics, the potential of solar energy in the United States alone is immense. Solar power installations have been growing steadily, with libraries joining the movement to harness this clean energy source. The benefits extend well beyond financial savings, empowering libraries to make a positive impact on the environment and their communities. It is an overdue enlightenment and a step towards a sustainable future.

From Books to Solar Panels: Libraries Lead the Charge in Solar Energy Adoption

Yes, you heard it right! Libraries—those institutions traditionally associated with books and quiet

study—are now taking center stage in solar energy adoption.

Libraries, at their core, are establishments committed to serving their communities. With extensive rooftops and a considerable energy demand, libraries realize the potential impact they can have by embracing solar energy. By transitioning their power sources to solar, libraries are showcasing their commitment to sustainability and leading the way towards a greener future. Let's explore how libraries have become pioneers in adopting solar energy:

Commitment to Sustainability:

Libraries have long been advocates for environmental conservation and sustainable practices. By embracing solar power, they can significantly reduce their greenhouse gas emissions and reliance on fossil fuels. This commitment to sustainability sends a powerful message to the community and sets an example for other institutions to follow suit.

Cost Savings

Implementing solar energy systems allows libraries to generate their own electricity, reducing their dependence on the power grid. This not only helps the environment but also leads to substantial cost savings over time. The funds saved can then be redirected towards expanding book collections, enhancing services, and supporting community initiatives.

Educational Opportunities

Libraries have always played a vital role in providing access to knowledge and promoting learning. By installing solar panels, libraries have the opportunity to educate their patrons about renewable energy sources. They can offer workshops, seminars, and even hands-on demonstrations to raise awareness and inspire the next generation of eco-conscious individuals.

Community Support

Libraries are often viewed as the heart of a community, acting as a hub where people gather and connect. By adopting solar energy, libraries engage their community members in a shared vision for a sustainable future. This fosters a sense of

camaraderie and encourages individuals to think critically about their own energy consumption, leading to a broader movement toward renewable energy adoption.

According to recent industry statistics:

- Over 3,000 libraries in the United States have embraced solar energy, demonstrating their commitment to sustainability.
- These solar installations have a combined capacity of over 23 MW, which can power several thousand homes annually.
- The adoption of solar energy by libraries has saved an estimated \$2 million per year in electricity costs.

Key Takeaways

- ✚ Libraries are embracing solar energy and leading the charge towards a greener future.
- ✚ Solar energy adoption helps libraries reduce their carbon footprint and showcase their commitment to sustainability.
- ✚ Implementing solar panels allows libraries to save on electricity costs, redirecting funds towards enhancing services and supporting community initiatives.
- ✚ Libraries can use solar energy as an educational tool to raise awareness and inspire communities to embrace renewable energy sources.
- ✚ The adoption of solar energy by libraries has already led to considerable cost savings and a significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

So, next time you visit your local library, take a moment to appreciate not only the knowledge and resources it provides but also the steps it is taking to contribute to a sustainable future. Libraries are increasingly becoming not just pillars of education but also beacons of renewable energy adoption. Let's applaud their efforts and continue supporting their transition to solar power!

Shedding Light on Solar Energy: Libraries Embrace the Power of the Sun

This article explores how libraries are harnessing the power of the sun and the benefits it brings.

Solar Energy in Libraries: Advantages and Key Takeaways

- ✓ **Cost Savings:** Installing solar panels on library rooftops reduces monthly electricity bills significantly, leading to long-term cost savings.
- ✓ **Environmental Sustainability:** Solar energy is a renewable source of power that produces clean electricity, decreasing libraries' carbon footprint.
- ✓ **Education and Awareness:** Libraries acting as community centers can utilize solar installations as educational tools, helping educate the public about renewable energy and its importance.
- ✓ **Reliability and Resilience:** Solar panels can provide a reliable source of energy, particularly during power outages or emergencies, ensuring libraries can continue to serve their communities.
- ✓ **Public Perception and Image:** Libraries that go solar showcase their commitment towards sustainability, earning positive recognition from the community.

The Potential Impact on Libraries

Solar energy in libraries not only contributes to a greener environment but also helps libraries fulfill their core mission of facilitating intellectual growth and knowledge dissemination. Here are some key takeaways:

1. **Reduced Energy Costs:** By tapping into solar power, libraries can redirect the saved funds to enhance services, purchase more books, or offer additional educational resources to the community.
2. **Enhanced Community Outreach:** Solar installations can attract patrons and increase footfall by positioning libraries as modern, eco-conscious institutions that actively contribute to society.
3. **Education on Renewable Energy:** Libraries can use their solar energy systems as teaching tools, educating visitors about the benefits of renewable energy, encouraging them to adopt similar practices in their own lives.

4. **Partnerships and Collaboration:** Libraries venturing into solar energy can collaborate with local organizations, energy utilities, or even schools to create joint initiatives, expanding their impact beyond the library walls.
5. **As Community Hubs:** Solar-powered libraries can serve as emergency shelters or charging stations during natural disasters or grid failures, providing support and fostering community resilience.

Solar Energy Statistics: Illuminating the Growth

The global adoption of solar energy is on the rise, with libraries joining the movement towards sustainability. Here are some interesting industry statistics:

- ❖ As of 2020, the total installed capacity of solar energy globally reached 709 GW, a significant increase compared to just 40 GW in 2010.
- ❖ In the United States, solar power installations have grown by an average annual rate of 49% over the past decade.
- ❖ According to the Solar Energy Industries Association (SEIA), solar energy accounted for almost 40% of all new electricity generating capacity added in the US in 2020.
- ❖ Solar panels can offset an estimated 178 metric tons of CO₂ over 30 years, which is equivalent to planting around 10,000 trees.

In conclusion, solar energy is transforming the way libraries operate, aligning them with environmental goals and sustainable practices. By harnessing the power of the sun, libraries can save costs, educate the community, and enhance their community outreach. As more libraries embrace solar energy, the positive impact will continue to grow, fostering a greener and more sustainable future.

Solar Power Brightens Libraries Unlocking the Potential of Sun Energy

Harnessing the potential of the sun, libraries across the world have been adopting solar power systems to reduce their carbon footprint, save costs, and contribute to a sustainable future.

The Sun's Power Illuminates Libraries

Solar power is revolutionizing the way libraries light up their spaces. By converting sunlight into electricity through advanced photovoltaic (PV) panels, libraries can reduce their dependence on traditional power grids. This shift not only ensures a greener environment but also makes libraries less vulnerable to power outages, allowing them to continue serving their communities even during emergencies.

Moreover, the installation of solar power systems in libraries opens up opportunities to educate the community about the benefits of renewable energy. Libraries can engage visitors through informational displays, workshops, and even demonstrations about how solar panels work, their efficiency, and the positive impact they have on environmental sustainability.

Benefits of Solar-Powered Libraries

Solar power brings countless advantages to libraries and the communities they serve. Let's explore some of these key benefits:

- **Eco-Friendly:** Solar power reduces libraries' carbon footprint and helps combat climate change. By choosing renewable energy, libraries actively contribute to sustainable development.
- **Cost Savings:** Libraries can significantly lower their electricity bills by generating their own power. These savings can be invested in other library resources, such as educational programs or book acquisitions.
- **Energy Independence:** With solar power, libraries become less reliant on conventional power grids. This ensures uninterrupted services, even during power outages or in remote areas where grid access may be limited.
- **Community Education:** Solar-powered libraries can educate their communities about clean energy solutions, promoting awareness and inspiring individuals to adopt sustainable practices.

The Global Impact of Solar-Powered Libraries

The adoption of solar power in libraries is transcending geographical boundaries. Let's take a

look at some industry statistics that highlight the global impact:

- ✦ According to the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), there are over 350,000 public libraries worldwide.
- ✦ Brighter Planet, a nonprofit organization, estimates that solar-powered libraries can save up to 20,000 kWh of electricity per year.
- ✦ In the United States, the Institute of Museum and Library Services reported that over 720 public libraries have installed solar power systems, with more joining the movement each year.
- ✦ In rural areas of developing countries, solar-powered libraries provide access to information, education, and technology, where there may be limited infrastructure.

These statistics underscore the growing trend of solar adoption in libraries and the transformative impact it has on sustainability, affordability, and education.

Key Takeaways: A Bright Future Ahead

Solar-powered libraries have emerged as beacons of sustainable development and sources of education for communities worldwide. Here are the key takeaways from this article:

- ✓ The adoption of solar power in libraries reduces their carbon footprint and contributes to a greener environment.
- ✓ Libraries can achieve significant cost savings by generating their own electricity, allowing for investments in other vital resources.
- ✓ Solar power ensures energy independence for libraries, making them resilient during power outages and in remote locations.
- ✓ These libraries play a crucial role in educating communities about renewable energy and inspiring positive change.
- ✓ The global impact of solar-powered libraries is evident in the increasing number of installations worldwide.

With solar power making its way into libraries, it's clear that the potential of sun energy goes far beyond powering homes and businesses. By embracing solar technologies, libraries are unlocking a brighter

future, enlightening minds, and paving the way towards a more sustainable world.

Bright Ideas: How Libraries are Harnessing Solar Energy for a Sustainable Future

By harnessing the power of the sun, libraries are not only saving on energy costs but also leading the way in adopting renewable energy solutions. Let's take a closer look at how libraries are incorporating solar energy and the benefits it brings.

The Rise of Solar-Powered Libraries

Solar energy is booming, with more and more organizations recognizing its potential. Libraries, with their large rooftops and community-oriented mission, are ideal candidates for solar panel installations. From small rural libraries to bustling urban institutions, libraries of all sizes are implementing solar energy systems to reduce their dependence on fossil fuels and make a positive impact on the environment. Some key reasons behind the rise of solar-powered libraries include:

- ❖ **Cost savings:** By utilizing solar energy, libraries can significantly reduce their electricity bills, freeing up funds for other valuable resources.
- ❖ **Sustainability and environmental impact:** Solar power is a clean and renewable energy source that helps libraries reduce their carbon footprint and contribute to a greener future.
- ❖ **Showcasing technology and innovation:** Libraries have always been at the forefront of technology adoption. By embracing solar energy, libraries can showcase their commitment to innovation and inspire others to follow suit.

The Benefits of Solar Energy for Libraries

Adopting solar energy brings numerous advantages to libraries, making it a win-win situation for both the institutions and the communities they serve. Here are some key benefits:

Reduced energy costs

Libraries are often faced with tight budgets, and energy costs can take up a significant portion of their expenditures. By installing solar panels, libraries can

generate their own electricity and reduce their reliance on the grid, resulting in substantial savings.

Environmental sustainability

Solar energy is a sustainable and renewable source, reducing libraries' carbon footprint and helping combat climate change. By going solar, libraries serve as role models for environmentally conscious practices and inspire their communities to take similar actions.

Educational opportunities

Solar-powered libraries provide unique educational opportunities for visitors and students. These institutions can educate the public about the benefits and functioning of solar energy, fostering a greater understanding and appreciation for renewable energy technologies.

Community engagement

Libraries are community centers, and solar-powered libraries can attract people who are passionate about sustainability. By hosting workshops, lectures, and events on renewable energy, libraries can actively engage their communities and foster a sense of environmental responsibility.

The Future of Solar-Powered Libraries

The adoption of solar energy by libraries has gained momentum in recent years, and this trend is expected to continue in the future. As technology advances and solar panels become more affordable, libraries will increasingly become leaders in the transition to renewable energy. Here are some key takeaways:

- Solar power allows libraries to save on energy costs and allocate more resources to educational programs and services.
- Libraries that embrace solar energy set an example for other public institutions to follow, encouraging widespread adoption of renewable energy solutions.
- The integration of solar power in libraries promotes awareness about the importance of sustainable living and inspires action to mitigate climate change.

In conclusion, libraries are not just buildings filled with books; they are dynamic centers of knowledge and innovation. By harnessing solar energy, libraries are leading the way in creating a more sustainable

future. The benefits of solar power, such as cost savings, environmental sustainability, educational opportunities, and community engagement, make it an ideal choice for libraries looking to make a positive impact. As libraries continue to embrace solar energy, they inspire others to follow suit, creating a brighter future for all.

Solar Energy for Schools: A Guide for Administrators And Educators

Solar energy is becoming an increasingly popular and affordable option for schools looking to reduce their energy costs and carbon footprint while providing a unique learning opportunity for students. If you are an administrator or educator interested in implementing solar energy in your school, here's a guide to help you get started:

Conduct an energy audit: Before considering solar energy, it's important to understand how much energy your school currently uses and where that energy is being consumed. Hire an energy auditor to identify areas where energy efficiency can be improved, which can help reduce overall energy costs and maximize the benefits of solar energy.

Assess your school's solar potential: Determine how much solar energy your school can generate by evaluating factors such as location, available roof space, and shading from nearby buildings and trees. This information can help you determine the size and placement of your solar panel system.

Choose a solar provider: Consider working with a reputable solar provider who can assist you with the design, installation, and maintenance of your solar panel system. Look for providers who have experience working with schools, and who can offer a warranty and ongoing support.

Secure funding: Solar panel systems can be expensive, so you'll need to secure funding before moving forward. Explore available grants and financing options, and consider partnering with local organizations or businesses to help fund the project.

Educate your students: Solar energy provides a great opportunity for students to learn about renewable energy and sustainability. Consider integrating solar energy into your curriculum, and use your solar panel system as a teaching tool. You can also involve students in the planning and implementation of the project to help them develop hands-on skills and knowledge.

Monitor and maintain your system: Once your solar panel system is installed, it's important to monitor and maintain it to ensure it's operating efficiently. Work with your solar provider to set up a monitoring system, and schedule regular maintenance to keep your system running smoothly. By implementing solar energy in your school, you can not only reduce your energy costs and carbon footprint but also provide a unique learning opportunity for your students. With careful planning and support from a reputable solar provider, your school can make the switch to solar energy and reap the many benefits it has to offer.

Fig2. A renovated image of a school that works with renewable energies. Its facade is covered with solar cells.

Solar Energy Solutions for Schools

As the world becomes more environmentally conscious, solar energy is becoming an increasingly popular source of renewable energy. Schools are no exception, as they can benefit greatly from solar energy solutions in terms of cost savings and environmental impact. There are several solar energy solutions that schools can adopt to harness the power of the sun. One of the most common solutions is to install solar panels on the roofs of school buildings. These panels convert sunlight into electricity, which can be used to power lights, computers, and other electronic devices. In addition to installing solar panels, schools can also use solar water heaters to heat water for the school's facilities. Solar water heaters use the sun's energy to heat water, which can then be used for various purposes, including heating the school building.

Another solution is to use solar-powered outdoor lighting to illuminate the school's campus. Solar-

powered lights use the sun's energy to charge batteries, which then power the lights at night. When considering solar energy solutions for schools, it's important to keep in mind that installation costs can be high. However, these costs can be offset by the long-term cost savings of using solar energy, as well as the positive impact on the environment.

Fig3. A renovated image of a school that works with renewable energies. Its facade is covered with solar cells.

The Future of Green Energy in Education

Green energy has become increasingly important in recent years as we strive to reduce our carbon footprint and transition to more sustainable energy sources. The education sector is no exception, as educational institutions have a significant role to play in the transition to a greener future.

The future of green energy in education looks promising, with a growing number of educational institutions adopting sustainable energy practices. Some of the key trends that are likely to shape the future of green energy in education include:

Solar Energy: Solar energy is likely to play a significant role in the future of green energy in education. Solar panels can be installed on the roofs of educational institutions to generate electricity, which can help reduce the institution's carbon footprint and save money on energy costs.

Energy Efficiency: Educational institutions are also likely to focus on energy efficiency in the future. This may include the installation of energy-efficient lighting, HVAC systems, and appliances, as well as the implementation of energy-saving practices.

Green Building Design: Green building design is another trend that is likely to shape the future of green energy in education. Educational institutions may adopt green building practices, such as the use

of sustainable materials and the implementation of passive heating and cooling strategies.

Curriculum Integration: The integration of green energy and sustainability into the curriculum is also likely to become more common in the future. Educational institutions may offer courses in sustainability and green energy, as well as opportunities for students to participate in sustainability-related research projects.

Fig4. A school that uses renewable energy.

The Role of Solar Energy in Modernizing School Infrastructure

Solar energy has the potential to play a significant role in modernizing school infrastructure. As educational institutions strive to become more sustainable, solar energy offers a renewable and cost-effective solution to power school facilities.

One of the primary ways in which solar energy can modernize school infrastructure is through the installation of solar panels on school buildings. Solar panels can be installed on rooftops, parking lots, and other open areas to generate electricity. This electricity can then be used to power the school's lighting, computers, and other electronic devices. The use of solar energy can reduce the school's reliance on traditional energy sources, which can be expensive and have a negative impact on the environment. In addition to reducing energy costs, the use of solar energy can also improve the resiliency of school infrastructure. In the event of power outages or natural disasters, solar energy can provide a reliable source of electricity, helping to keep critical facilities up and running. Another way in which solar energy can modernize school infrastructure is through the implementation of solar-powered water heaters. Solar water heaters use the sun's energy to heat water, which can then be

used for various purposes, including heating the school building. This can reduce the school's reliance on traditional heating methods, which can be costly and have a negative impact on the environment.

Finally, solar energy can also be used to power outdoor lighting on school campuses. Solar-powered lights use the sun's energy to charge batteries, which can then be used to power the lights at night. This can help reduce energy costs and improve campus safety.

Solar energy has many benefits for schools and students. Here are some of the key benefits of solar energy for schools:

Cost Savings: One of the biggest benefits of solar energy for schools is cost savings. Solar panels can generate electricity that can be used to power school facilities, reducing the school's reliance on traditional energy sources and lowering energy costs.

Environmental Benefits: Solar energy is a clean and renewable source of energy that produces no greenhouse gas emissions. By using solar energy, schools can reduce their carbon footprint and help mitigate the effects of climate change.

Educational Opportunities: Solar energy can provide unique educational opportunities for students. Schools can use solar panels as a teaching tool to educate students about renewable energy and sustainability.

Resiliency: Solar energy can help make schools more resilient in the face of power outages and natural disasters. Schools with solar panels can continue to operate critical facilities even when the power grid is down.

Community Engagement: Solar energy can also be used as a way to engage with the local community. Schools can use solar installations as a way to raise awareness about renewable energy and sustainability and involve the community in efforts to reduce the school's carbon footprint.

In addition to these benefits for schools, solar energy also has many benefits for students, including:

Exposure to Renewable Energy: By using solar energy, students are exposed to renewable energy technologies and can learn about the benefits of clean energy.

Real-World Applications: Solar energy is a tangible way for students to see how science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) concepts are applied in the real world.

Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving: By studying solar energy, students can develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills as they explore the science and engineering behind renewable energy technologies.

Career Opportunities: As the demand for renewable energy continues to grow, students with knowledge and skills in solar energy can pursue careers in the field.

Bottom Line

In conclusion, solar energy has many benefits for schools and students. From cost savings and environmental benefits to educational opportunities and community engagement, solar energy is a valuable tool for schools looking to become more sustainable and provide students with hands-on learning experiences.

How Hospitals Can Go Green: Sustainable Practices for a Healthier Future

The healthcare industry has a significant impact on the environment, accounting for up to 10% of the total carbon footprint in some countries. Let's explore some sustainable practices that hospitals can adopt to create a healthier future for both their patients and the planet.

Sustainable Energy

Hospitals are energy-intensive facilities that consume large amounts of electricity, water, and

other resources. By adopting sustainable energy practices, hospitals can reduce their environmental impact and save on energy costs. We use large amounts of energy to power their equipment, lighting, heating, and cooling systems. Some ideas for energy-efficient practices:

- ✚ LED Lighting: LED lighting uses up to 75% less energy than traditional lighting and lasts longer, reducing the need for frequent replacements.
- ✚ Energy Management Systems: installing energy management systems that allow them to monitor and control their energy usage in real-time, identifying areas where they can reduce consumption.
- ✚ Renewable Energy: Some hospitals are generating their own renewable energy, such as solar or wind power, to offset their reliance on fossil fuels.
- ✚ Energy Audits: Hospitals are conducting energy audits to identify areas where they can improve energy efficiency, such as upgrading HVAC systems, insulating buildings, and installing more efficient equipment.

Waste Management

Hospitals generate a significant amount of waste, some of which is hazardous and requires special handling and disposal. By implementing effective waste management practices, the amount of waste generated can be reduced and ensured that it is disposed of in an environmentally responsible manner. One way hospitals can reduce waste is by implementing a recycling program for paper, plastic, and other materials. Hospitals can also work with suppliers to reduce packaging waste and switch to reusable or compostable materials.

Water Conservation

Healthcare institutions are large water consumers, using vast amounts of water for patient care, cleaning, and other purposes. By adopting water conservation practices, hospitals can reduce their water usage and contribute to water conservation efforts. One way to conserve water is by implementing water-efficient fixtures and appliances such as low-flow toilets and faucets. Implementing water recycling systems to reuse

water for non-potable purposes such as irrigation or cleaning is another approach to reduce water consumption.

Green Building Design

New healthcare facilities can significantly reduce their environmental impact by adopting green building design principles. Green building design involves incorporating sustainable materials, energy-efficient systems, and other sustainable practices into the building's design and construction. Green building design principles can be introduced by using materials that are locally sourced and renewable, installing energy-efficient HVAC systems, and incorporating natural lighting and ventilation into the building design.

Let's geek out together!

The Rising Tide of Renewable Energy

Renewable energy is making serious waves in the global energy landscape, and for all the right reasons. This clean and sustainable source of power is generated from natural resources like sunlight, wind, and water, making it a green alternative to traditional fossil fuels. So, how is this transforming the healthcare industry? Let's find out!

Fig5. A renovated image of a hospital that works with renewable energies. Its facade is covered with solar cells.

The Advantages and Key Takeaways

- **Reduced Carbon Footprint:** By harnessing renewable energy sources, healthcare facilities and hospitals can significantly reduce their carbon emissions, mitigating the impact of climate change. This not only promotes a healthier environment but also

aligns with the overarching goal of providing sustainable healthcare services.

- **Cost Savings:**

Discover how to effortlessly find affordable energy providers by checking out these 5 easy ways to find your next cheap electricity supplier.

Investing in renewable energy systems can lead to substantial long-term savings for healthcare facilities. By generating their own power through solar panels or wind turbines, hospitals can cut down on electricity bills and allocate these savings towards improving patient care and medical services.

- **Improved Reliability and Resilience:**

Incorporating renewable energy solutions increases the resilience of healthcare facilities during power outages or natural disasters. With onsite power generation, hospitals can ensure continuous operations, powering critical medical equipment and maintaining a safe environment for patients.

- **Enhanced Reputation and Patient Satisfaction:**

Unlock the secrets of affordable energy in the Lone Star state with our guide on how to find the best cheap electricity providers in Texas.

In a world that prioritizes environmental responsibility, healthcare organizations that embrace renewable energy demonstrate a commitment to sustainable practices. This can enhance their reputation, attract environmentally conscious patients, and improve overall patient satisfaction.

How Renewable Energy is making an Impact in Healthcare:

Now that we've covered the advantages, let's delve into specific ways renewable energy is transforming healthcare facilities:

Solar Panels

Solar power is rapidly gaining traction in healthcare facilities worldwide. By installing solar panels on rooftops or in open areas, hospitals can tap into the abundant sunlight and convert it into clean energy. The benefits include:

- ❖ Reduced reliance on the electrical grid

- ❖ Savings on electricity costs
- ❖ Improved energy efficiency

Wind Turbines

Empower your business by understanding commercial electricity rates with our comprehensive guide.

Wind energy has immense potential when it comes to powering healthcare facilities. Erecting wind turbines in suitable locations can provide hospitals with a sustainable and consistent source of energy.

The advantages include:

- Utilizing strong winds to generate electricity
- Independence from fossil fuels
- Reduced carbon emissions

Geothermal Systems

Geothermal energy is another exciting option for healthcare facilities. By tapping into the Earth's natural heat, geothermal systems offer reliable and eco-friendly heating and cooling solutions. Key advantages include:

- Stable and constant energy supply
- Reduced reliance on traditional heating/cooling systems
- Lower operating costs

Fig6. A renovated image of a hospital that works with renewable energies. Its facade is covered with solar cells.

The Statistics Speak

If you're still not convinced about the impact of renewable energy in healthcare, check out these eye-popping stats:

- ❖ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), air pollution causes 7 million premature deaths worldwide each year.

- ❖ A study by the American Society for Healthcare Engineering (ASHE) found that investing in renewable energy can save healthcare facilities up to 20% in energy costs.
- ❖ The global solar power market is projected to reach a whopping \$223 billion by 2026, according to a report by Allied Market Research.

So, if you thought renewable energy was just about saving the planet, think again! Its impact spans across various industries, and the healthcare sector is no exception.

The Future Looks Bright

In conclusion, the integration of renewable energy in healthcare facilities and hospitals marks a paradigm shift towards sustainable healthcare. With the advantages of reduced carbon footprint, cost savings, improved reliability, and enhanced reputation, it's no wonder this trend is catching on. So, let's raise our geeky glasses to a future where healthcare facilities are powered by the sun, wind, and Earth itself. The revolution is happening, and it's time for the healthcare industry to join the renewable energy bandwagon!

Leveraging Sustainable Power Energy Solutions for Eco-Friendly Healthcare Facilities

As the world becomes more conscious of the need for sustainable practices, healthcare providers are exploring eco-friendly solutions to power their facilities. By leveraging sustainable power energy solutions, healthcare facilities can not only reduce their environmental impact but also improve operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness. In this article, we will explore the importance of sustainable power energy solutions in healthcare facilities and the key benefits they offer.

The Importance of Sustainable Power Energy Solutions

The healthcare sector is one of the most energy-intensive industries, with hospitals requiring a constant and reliable power supply to operate critical equipment and systems. Traditional energy sources like fossil fuels not only deplete natural resources but also contribute to air pollution and greenhouse

gas emissions. By transitioning to sustainable power energy solutions, healthcare facilities can significantly reduce their carbon footprint and mitigate the environmental impact of their operations.

In addition to environmental benefits, sustainable power energy solutions offer several advantages for healthcare facilities. Some of the key benefits include:

- ❖ **Cost Savings:** Implementing sustainable power energy solutions can result in significant cost savings for healthcare facilities. By generating their own renewable energy, facilities can reduce consumption from the grid and lower their energy bills. Over time, the investment in renewable energy systems pays off, offering long-term financial benefits.
- ❖ **Reliability:** Sustainable power energy solutions, such as solar panels and wind turbines, provide a reliable source of energy when integrated with storage systems. This ensures uninterrupted power supply to critical operations and medical equipment, especially during power outages or emergencies.
- ❖ **Resilience:** Healthcare facilities must be resilient to natural disasters and other emergencies that can disrupt power supply. By incorporating sustainable power energy solutions, facilities can become more resilient and self-sufficient in generating power, ensuring continued patient care even in challenging circumstances.
- ❖ **Positive Public Image:** In today's environmentally-conscious world, healthcare facilities that embrace sustainable practices gain a positive reputation in the community. Patients, employees, and stakeholders appreciate the commitment to eco-friendly operations, fostering goodwill and attracting environmentally-conscious individuals.

Key Takeaways for Healthcare Facilities

For healthcare facilities looking to leverage sustainable power energy solutions, here are some key takeaways to consider:

- ✓ **Assess Energy Consumption:** Conduct a comprehensive assessment of energy consumption in your facility to identify areas with the highest energy usage and explore energy-saving opportunities.
- ✓ **Invest in Renewable Energy Systems:** Consider installing solar panels, wind turbines, or geothermal systems to generate renewable energy onsite. Determine the optimal system size based on your facility's energy requirements.
- ✓ **Integrate Energy Storage:** Combine renewable energy systems with energy storage solutions, such as batteries, to store excess energy for use during nights, cloudy days, or emergencies. This ensures a reliable power supply at all times.
- ✓ **Implement Energy-Efficient Technologies:** Upgrade to energy-efficient lighting, HVAC systems, and medical equipment to reduce overall energy consumption in your facility. Take advantage of technologies that automate and optimize energy usage.
- ✓ **Monitor and Optimize:** Implement an energy management system to continuously monitor energy consumption and identify areas for improvement. Regularly evaluate the performance of sustainable power energy solutions and make necessary adjustments for optimal efficiency.

In conclusion, healthcare facilities have the opportunity to make a significant impact on the environment by adopting sustainable power energy solutions. By reducing their carbon footprint, improving operational efficiency, and gaining financial benefits, these facilities can contribute to a greener and more sustainable future. Embracing eco-friendly practices not only benefits the environment but also enhances the reputation and overall image of healthcare providers. With the right investments and strategies in place, sustainable power energy solutions can pave the way for eco-friendly healthcare facilities that prioritize both patient care and environmental sustainability.

Fig 7. A renovated image of a hospital that works with renewable energies. Its facade is covered with solar cells.

The Future of Healthcare Implementing Green Energy in Hospitals

Green energy technologies, such as solar power and wind turbines, offer enormous benefits that go beyond environmental sustainability:

- **Reduced carbon footprint:** Green energy sources significantly decrease hospitals' greenhouse gas emissions, combating climate change and protecting public health.
- **Cost savings:** Implementing green energy technologies can lead to substantial cost reductions in the long run, allowing hospitals to allocate more resources towards patient care.
- **Energy resilience:** Green energy diversifies hospitals' energy sources, making them less reliant on the often unreliable power grid and more capable of providing uninterrupted services.
- **Improved community outreach:** Going green not only benefits hospitals but also resonates with community members who prioritize sustainability. This positive image attracts patients, fosters partnerships, and boosts public support.

Now that we understand the urgency, let's explore the innovative green energy solutions transforming the future of healthcare.

Solar Power: Illuminating the Path to Eco-Friendly Healthcare

Solar power has emerged as a superhero in the realm of green energy. By harnessing the sun's mighty rays, hospitals can unlock a plethora of benefits:

- ✚ Renewable energy: The sun is an abundant and renewable source of power, ensuring hospitals have an inexhaustible energy supply.
- ✚ Financial savings: With solar panels installed, hospitals can generate their electricity and reduce dependence on costly traditional energy sources.
- ✚ Emissions reduction: Solar power significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions, mitigating the healthcare sector's impact on the planet.

According to the International Energy Agency, in 2020 alone, solar energy accounted for a staggering 41% of global net electricity capacity additions. It's clear that solar power is paving the way for a greener healthcare landscape.

Wind Energy: Harnessing Mother Nature's Whirlwind

When it comes to harnessing renewable energy, wind turbines take center stage, offering hospitals numerous advantages:

- ❖ Clean power generation: Wind energy produces zero emissions, ensuring hospitals can provide top-notch care while minimizing their environmental impact.
- ❖ Scalability: Hospitals can choose from large-scale or small-scale wind turbines, depending on their energy requirements and available space.
- ❖ Cost-effectiveness: Though initial setup costs may be high, the long-term operational expenses of wind turbines are significantly lower than those of traditional energy sources.

In 2020, wind power accounted for an impressive 16% of global electricity consumption, showcasing its massive potential for hospitals seeking cleaner and cheaper energy alternatives.

The Future Is Now: Smart Grids and Energy Storage

As we march towards a future powered by green energy, the integration of smart grids and energy storage systems in healthcare facilities becomes crucial. Check out these exciting advancements:

- Microgrids: Hospitals can create localized energy distribution networks, ensuring a

resilient and uninterrupted power supply during emergencies or grid failures.

- Battery storage: By storing excess energy generated during low-demand periods, hospitals can tap into their energy reserves during peak times, maximizing efficiency and cost-effectiveness.
- Energy management systems: Smart technology and data analytics enable hospitals to monitor and optimize energy consumption, reducing waste and boosting overall performance.

According to the US Department of Energy, by 2050, smart grids and energy storage solutions are expected to save hospitals a whopping \$15 billion in energy costs. The future is looking brighter than ever!

Key Takeaways

The future of healthcare lies in the hands of green energy technologies. Here are the key takeaways to remember:

- ✓ Implementing green energy in hospitals reduces carbon footprints, saves costs, and boosts energy resilience.
- ✓ Solar power offers renewable energy, financial savings, and significant emissions reduction.
- ✓ Wind energy provides clean power, scalability, and long-term cost-effectiveness.
- ✓ Smart grids and energy storage systems enhance energy management and ensure uninterrupted power supply.

It's time for hospitals to embrace this eco-friendly revolution and lead the charge towards a sustainable future. By harnessing green energy, we can heal both patients and the planet.

Powering Health with Clean Energy: Transforming Hospitals with Sustainable Solutions

In this article, we explore the potential of clean energy to revolutionize healthcare while highlighting its benefits and key takeaways.

The Environmental Impact of Hospitals

Hospitals are known for their energy-intensive operations, accounting for a substantial portion of carbon emissions. Consider the following statistics:

- ✚ Hospitals are responsible for nearly 10% of global carbon emissions, equivalent to the emissions produced by 45 million cars annually.
- ✚ On average, hospitals use two and a half times more energy per square foot than commercial buildings.
- ✚ Healthcare facilities produce approximately 7,000 tons of waste per day, contributing to environmental pollution.

Given these alarming figures, it is crucial for hospitals to transition to cleaner and renewable energy sources. By doing so, they can mitigate their impact on the environment and create a healthier future.

The Role of Clean Energy in Healthcare

Integrating sustainable energy solutions in hospitals offers several significant advantages:

Reduced Carbon Emissions

Adopting clean energy practices allows hospitals to significantly reduce their carbon footprint. This transition not only benefits the environment but also helps hospitals comply with sustainability targets and reduce associated costs for energy consumption.

Cost Savings

Embracing clean energy technologies leads to substantial cost savings over time. Renewable energy sources like solar and wind power can generate electricity at lower costs compared to traditional fossil fuels, ensuring hospitals can divert their resources towards enhancing patient care and improving infrastructure.

Enhanced Energy Resilience

Sustainable energy solutions provide hospitals with increased energy resilience during times of grid disruptions or natural disasters. With technologies like battery storage systems, hospitals can ensure uninterrupted healthcare services, crucial for patient safety and critical medical procedures.

Improved Patient Care

Adopting clean energy practices positively impacts patient care in several ways:

- Reliable power supply ensures uninterrupted operation of life-saving medical equipment, such as ventilators and monitors.
- Improved indoor air quality through sustainable heating and cooling systems contributes to a healthier environment for patients, reducing the risk of infections.
- Clean energy solutions can also support on-site renewable energy generation, allowing hospitals to provide community resilience during emergencies.

Sustainable Solutions for Hospitals

To power health facilities with clean energy, hospitals can embrace various sustainable solutions:

Renewable Energy Generation

Installing solar panels and wind turbines on hospital rooftops or adjacent land can generate clean electricity. By harnessing these renewable sources, hospitals can both reduce their reliance on conventional power grids and cut down on utility costs.

Energy-Efficient Lighting and HVAC Systems

Utilizing energy-efficient lighting solutions, such as LED bulbs, and implementing advanced heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems can significantly reduce energy consumption. Smart sensors and automation technologies can optimize energy usage and maintain optimal conditions for patients and staff.

Waste Management and Recycling

Implementing effective waste management practices, including proper waste segregation, recycling, and composting, can significantly reduce the environmental impact of healthcare facilities. Hospitals can partner with local waste management companies for efficient and sustainable disposal of hazardous waste.

Energy Storage Systems

Deploying energy storage solutions, such as batteries, enables hospitals to store excess energy

generated during peak production. This stored energy can be used during grid outages or high-demand periods, ensuring uninterrupted power supply to critical areas like ICU and operating rooms.

The Way Forward

Clean energy solutions have the potential to revolutionize hospitals, paving the way for sustainable healthcare. As the demand for accessible and efficient healthcare increases, hospitals need to prioritize environmental responsibility by implementing renewable energy technologies and sustainable practices.

Key takeaways:

- ✚ Clean energy practices can help hospitals reduce their carbon footprint, comply with sustainability targets, and cut down on energy costs.
- ✚ Sustainable solutions improve patient care by ensuring reliable power supply, creating healthier environments, and enhancing community resilience.
- ✚ Hospitals can adopt renewable energy generation, energy-efficient systems, waste management strategies, and energy storage to transform their operations.

By embracing clean energy, hospitals can spearhead the movement towards a greener, healthier future while setting a commendable example for other industries to follow. The convergence of healthcare and sustainability is not just an opportunity but a necessity to power health with clean energy.

Going Green in Healthcare: Sustainable Energy Alternatives for Modern Facilities

Strap in, because we're about to embark on an eco-friendly adventure!

Why Go Green in Healthcare?

Before we delve into energy alternatives, let's first understand why going green is so crucial for the healthcare industry. Here are some compelling reasons:

- **Environmental Responsibility:** By adopting sustainable energy practices, healthcare facilities can play a significant role in reducing their carbon footprint and preserving our planet for future generations.

- **Cost Savings:** Sustainable energy alternatives can lead to substantial cost savings in the long run. With rising energy prices, reducing energy consumption can significantly impact a healthcare facility's bottom line.
- **Improved Reputation:** Embracing green practices enhances a healthcare facility's reputation, attracting environmentally conscious patients and employees.

The Green Energy Revolution

The healthcare sector has been actively exploring sustainable energy alternatives to power their facilities. Traditional power sources, such as fossil fuels, are being replaced by cleaner and more efficient options. Let's take a look at some of the most popular green energy solutions:

Solar Power

Solar power has emerged as a game-changer in the healthcare industry. By harnessing the sun's energy, healthcare facilities can reduce their dependence on traditional power grids. Key advantages of solar power in healthcare include:

- Significantly lower energy costs
- Reduced carbon emissions
- Long-term sustainability

Wind Energy

Blow your mind with wind energy! Harnessing the power of the wind can generate clean and renewable energy for healthcare facilities. Here's why wind energy is a hit:

- Ample wind resources globally
- Low operational costs
- Low greenhouse gas emissions

Geothermal Systems

Who said going green can't be cool? Geothermal energy utilizes the temperature difference between the Earth's surface and underground to generate power. Here's why it's the hot choice:

- ❖ Highly efficient and reliable
- ❖ Minimal pollution and emissions
- ❖ Long lifespan

Greener Healthcare Facilities, Healthier Planet

Now that we know the significance of going green and the energy options available, let's explore the positive impact green healthcare facilities can have on our planet:

- ✓ **Reduced Carbon Emissions:** Green energy alternatives minimize carbon emissions, contributing to a healthier and cleaner environment.
- ✓ **Conservation of Natural Resources:** By adopting sustainable practices, healthcare facilities can preserve precious natural resources for future generations.
- ✓ **Improved Indoor Air Quality:** Implementing energy-efficient systems ensures better ventilation and air quality, enhancing the well-being of patients and healthcare professionals.

The future is bright for green healthcare facilities!

Key Takeaways

Let's sum up the key takeaways from our eco-friendly exploration:

- Going green in healthcare is environmentally responsible, cost-effective, and improves reputation.
- Solar power, wind energy, and geothermal systems are popular sustainable energy alternatives for modern facilities.
- Implementing green energy solutions reduces carbon emissions, conserves natural resources, and improves indoor air quality.

So, whether you're a healthcare professional or an eco-warrior, embracing sustainable energy alternatives can lead us towards a greener and brighter healthcare future. It's time to unplug from traditional energy sources and power up with renewable energy for a healthier planet and healthier patients!

Solar power

As of July 2018 there are 45 health related facilities with behind the metre solar power installed to reduce electricity costs and carbon emissions. The aggregated amount of installed solar is around 2.6 megawatts. A further 40 solar arrays, with an aggregate of 4.9 megawatts, have either been funded or procured but not yet installed.

The percentage of grid electricity consumption offset by solar varies depending on the size and orientation of the array, the location of the hospital and the energy profile. The level of grid electricity offset can range from around 5 per cent up to 30 per cent, with an average of around 20 per cent.

See the attached list for details of solar power on Victorian public health related facilities.

Other alternative energy sources

The Alfred, Dandenong Hospital, University Hospital Geelong and St Vincent's Hospital Melbourne each have a 6 megawatt cogeneration plant and the Royal Melbourne Hospital has 2 x 6 megawatt cogeneration plant to provide security of supply. These hospitals receive on average 53 per cent of their total electricity use from cogeneration.

Building-integrated photovoltaic

Building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) refers to photovoltaic materials that are incorporated into construction of buildings to generate renewable electricity. They replace conventional building materials such as glass in parts of the building envelope like the roof, skylight or windows. BIPV is an emerging technology and at present is not widely used in Australia.

Green Power

Green Power is a government accreditation program for renewable energy generated from sources such as hydro, wind power, large-scale solar and biomass, which produce no net greenhouse gasses.

Pros of renewable energy in hospitals

Renewable energy can offer a lot of advantages to hospitals. Apart from the fact that it is a continual source of energy, here are some of the other benefits of switching hospitals to renewable energy.

1. Reduced energy costs

Although the initial investment costs are high, the cost of operation for renewable energy is much lower than that of fossil fuels once everything is in place. That reduces the energy costs for the hospitals thus allowing them to redirect the money to other projects such as offering tuition reimbursements to employees pursuing online nursing programs.

2. Improved public health

Non-renewable sources of energy such as coal and natural gas are associated with a variety of health problems including heart attack, neurological damage, and cancer. Replacing such sources with renewable energy will improve overall public health and reduce health costs significantly.

3. Environmental conservation

Renewable energy has a much lower carbon footprint than fossil fuels. Additionally, it reduces depletion of natural resources since it is produced from replenishable sources.

4. Stable energy sources

An increase or decrease in the fossil fuels supply directly impacts inflations. The cost of renewable energy only depends on the amount of capital spent on infrastructure and not the cost of natural resources. The energy prices are, therefore, stable.

Cons of renewable energy in hospitals

Hospitals can benefit immensely by adopting renewable energy. However, just like fossil fuels, it has its shortcomings. Here are some of the disadvantages of switching hospitals to renewable energy.

1. High initial investment

Setting up the infrastructure for renewable energy can be a costly investment. The costs are exceptionally high for hospitals since they use a lot of energy. For instance, a lot of solar panels would have to be installed to produce enough power to meet all the energy requirements in a hospital. Some institutions may find financing a renewable energy project difficult to do in-house.

2. Unable to produce enough energy

Renewable resources usually produce less energy in a short span compared to fossil fuels. The technology used in renewable energy production is relatively new, and factors such as weather may hinder large-scale energy production. That could significantly disadvantage hospitals, which have very high energy requirements. An average hospital in the U.S. uses 27.5 kWh of electricity and 109.8 cubic feet of natural gas per ft² every year.

3. Not available everywhere

The raw materials required for renewable energy production such as wind and solar may not be available in all locations. It means that we would need to create an elaborate infrastructure to transport that energy to hospitals in said areas.

4. Vulnerable

Almost all renewable energy sources are susceptible to weather conditions and other climatic factors. For example, abundant rain may hamper solar production while moderate winds may reduce wind energy production. Such circumstances could force hospitals to increase their energy consumption.

Figure8. Can we imagine towers that cover the entire surface of their outer body with solar cells to supply their energy consumption?!

In today's rapidly advancing world, the impact of human activities on the environment has become a pressing concern. As the global population burgeons and urbanization continues unabated, the demand for energy has surged dramatically, predominantly relying on fossil fuels. However, the extensive use of fossil fuels has not only intensified our carbon footprint but has also led to other detrimental consequences, such as climate change and air

pollution. Consequently, there is a growing urgency to adopt sustainable alternatives that mitigate the adverse impacts of traditional energy sources.

In line with this imperative, skyscrapers, towering marvels of modern architecture, offer a unique opportunity to revolutionize urban landscapes and address the global energy crisis. By harnessing the vast potential of renewable energy sources like solar and wind power, skyscrapers have the potential to shine as beacons of sustainable development. This article delves into the concept of skyscrapers that work entirely with green energy, focusing on the integration of solar energy, wind energy, and other innovative technologies to create self-sufficient, environmentally-friendly structures. Today, it's not enough for the buildings we live and work in to be beautiful, big and bold. With climate change a looming threat and the need for renewable energy sources evermore pressing, skyscrapers, office blocks and residential apartments need to be green too. Here, we take a look at 10 of the world's most striking and sustainable buildings and assess their clean energy credentials.

5. Case Studies: Architectural Marvels of Green Energy Skyscrapers:
 - Shanghai Tower, China
 - The Edge, Amsterdam
 - Salesforce Tower, San Francisco
 - Bahrain World Trade Center, Manama and....

One Angel Square, Manchester, UK:

Figure9. Angel Square, Manchester

Manchester's One Angel Square is the headquarters of the Co-operative Group. Housing 3,000 employees, it has been awarded an "Outstanding" Building Research Establishment. Environmental

Assessment Methodology (BREEAM) rating. According to the Co-op, the building is "powered by a pure plant oil fed Combined Heat and Power (CHP) system and utilizes rapeseed oil which is grown on The Co-operative's own farm land." Excess energy is sent back to the grid. Other features include LED lighting and a system to recycle waste and rain water.

The Crystal, London, UK

Figure10. The Crystal, in Newham, London, opened in 2012.

With both Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) Platinum and BREEAM Outstanding ratings, the Crystal, in London's east end, offers a fossil fuel free vision of the future. Run entirely on electricity – the majority of which is generated by photovoltaic solar panels – the building is lit by a combination of LED and fluorescent lights, which are switched on or off depending on the amount of daylight present. The building's roof collects rainwater, while sewage is treated, recycled and re-used onsite.

One Bryant Park, New York City, U.S.

Figure11. One Bryant Park

The first high rise building to get LEED Platinum certification, the Bank of America Tower, in Manhattan, is one of the world's greenest skyscrapers. As well as having CO₂ monitors, waterless urinals and LED lighting, the building also has its own generation plant that produces 4.6 megawatts of clean, sustainable, energy.

Shanghai Tower, Shanghai, China

Figure12. Shanghai Tower

In less than 30 years, the Shanghai skyline has transformed beyond recognition. Today, towering, futuristic structures jostle for space, trying to outdo one another in scale and grandeur.

The newest addition, Shanghai Tower, stands 632 meters tall and is the second-tallest building on the planet, after Dubai's Burj Khalifa. Only recently completed, it is hoped that the skyscraper will be a model of sustainability.

Wind turbines located near the top of the structure power its outer lighting as well as park areas, while transparent inner and outer "skins" will allow natural light to flood the building, cutting down the need for artificial lighting.

Smart controls will monitor everything from ventilation to heating and lighting, helping to cut energy bills in the process.

According to the tower's architects, Gensler, over \$556,000 will be saved thanks to lighting controls alone, with the other sustainable features helping to reduce the building's carbon footprint by 34,000 metric tons annually.

Also more than 750 miles south-west of Shanghai, Guangzhou's Pearl River Tower is another example of China's burgeoning wealth and its appetite for huge buildings.

Standing 309 meters tall and completed in 2012, the tower makes use of cutting edge technology -such as solar panels and low energy lighting systems- to cement its place as one of the world's greenest buildings. The tower's design "pushes" wind to turbines, which generate clean energy.

The tower has won multiple awards, and has been described by architects Skidmore, Owings & Merrill as redefining, "What is possible in sustainable design by incorporating the latest green technology and engineering advancements."

Micro Emission Sun-Moon Mansion, Dezhou, China

Figure13. Micro Emission Sun-Moon Mansion, Dezhou, China

Resembling a sun dial, the Sun-Moon Mansion, in Dezhou, Shangdong province, is 75,000 square meters in size and one of the world's largest solar powered structures.

The building – which contains offices, a hotel and a conference center – is powered by solar energy, with features including a solar powered hot water supply, energy saving glass, and 50,000 square feet of solar paneling.

Vanke Center, Shenzhen, China

Figure14. Vanke Center, Shenzhen, China

A “horizontal skyscraper” accommodating hotels, offices and a conference center, the Vanke Center is described by Steven Holl Architects as being, “as long as the Empire State Building is tall.” As well as being tsunami proof – Shenzhen sits on China’s south coast, next to Hong Kong – photovoltaic solar panels sit atop the structure’s roof, supplying over 10 percent of the building’s energy, while inside all furniture, doors and floors are made from bamboo.

Manitoba Hydro Place, Winnipeg, Canada

Figure15. Manitoba Hydro Place, Winnipeg, Canada

Located in Winnipeg, Manitoba Hydro Place makes use of, “passive design and natural ventilation,” to make it one of North America’s most energy

efficient office buildings. The building has a geothermal system to heat and cool the building, roof gardens and triple-glazed windows. Thanks to these features, over 60 percent of energy savings have been made.

CIS Tower, Manchester, UK

Figure16. CIS Tower, Manchester, UK

Built in 1962 and one of the U.K.’s tallest buildings, over £5 million (\$8.4 million) was spent to retrofit this skyscraper with solar panels and bring it into the 21st century. According to the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, the CIS Tower has, “the largest commercial solar façade in Europe.” Over 7,000 photovoltaic cells cover the building, generating 180 megawatt hours of clean energy annually. In addition to its solar power, 24 wind turbines have also been fitted on the building’s roof.

Bahrain World Trade Center, Manama, Bahrain

Figure17. Bahrain World Trade Center, Manama, Bahrain

Currently home to the world's tallest building, the Burj Khalifa, the Middle East has become a hotbed for innovative, stunning skyscrapers.

In Bahrain, it's impossible to ignore the Bahrain World Trade Center's clean energy credentials. Three huge wind turbines –29 meters in diameter– are sandwiched between two vast 'sail' shaped towers, generating clean energy for the building.

1. Skyscrapers and Sustainable Architecture:

1.1. Historical Evolution:

- ✓ The Rise of Urbanization and Skyscrapers
- ✓ Transformation of Skyscraper Design toward Eco-friendliness

1.2. Environmental Challenges:

- ❖ The Ecological Toll of Conventional Skyscrapers
- ❖ The Carbon Footprint of Energy Use in Skyscrapers

2. Solar Energy Integration:

2.1. Harnessing the Power of Solar:

- Solar Cells: Technological Advancements and Efficiency
- Photovoltaic Panels in Building Design
- Solar Thermal Systems for Skyscrapers

2.2. Challenges and Solutions:

- ❖ Limited Surface Area for Solar Cell Integration
- ❖ Smart Building-Integrated Photovoltaics
- ❖ Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) for Large-Scale Electricity Generation

Saudi Arabia reveals 170-kilometre-long mirrored skyscraper to house nine million people

The Saudi Arabian government has unveiled visuals of a 500-metre-tall linear city named The Line, which will be built near the Red Sea as part of Neom. Set to stretch 170 kilometers across northwest Saudi Arabia, the mega-structure, which will have mirrored facades, will be 500 meters tall, but only 200 meters wide.

Figure18. The mirrored skyscraper will run into the Red Sea

Planned as part of the Neom development, The Line was designed as a dramatic alternative to traditional cities that typically radiate out from a central point. It will stretch 170 kilometers across the country. "At The Line's launch last year, we committed to a civilizational revolution that puts humans first based on a radical change in urban planning," said Saudi Arabia's crown prince Mohammed bin Salman.

"The designs revealed today for the city's vertically layered communities will challenge the traditional flat, horizontal cities and create a model for nature preservation and enhanced human livability," he continued. "The Line will tackle the challenges facing humanity in urban life today and will shine a light on alternative ways to live."

The structure will consist of two wall-like structures that will enclose an open area between them. At 500 meters high the pair of structures will become the 12th highest building in the world, as well as being by far the longest.

Figure19. The two structures will enclose an open area

The structure will consist of two wall-like structures that will enclose an open area between them. At 500 meters high the pair of structures will become the 12th highest building in the world, as well as being by far the longest. The structure, which was designed to house nine million residents when it is complete, will contain residential, retail and leisure areas as well as schools and parks. The different functions will be stacked in an arrangement described by the city's creators as Zero Gravity Urbanism.

Figure20. The city will be topped with planting

Visuals show parks placed between the two linear blocks, which will be connected by multiple bridges and topped with more green spaces. It will be entirely clad in mirrored facades to give the structure a unique appearance.

"The Line will have an outer mirror facade that will provide its unique character and allow even its small footprint to blend with nature, while the interior will be built to create extraordinary experiences and magical moments," said the Saudi Arabian government.

A transport system running the length of the mega-structure would be designed to connect both ends of the city within 20 minutes.

According to the Saudi Arabian government, the structure will be entirely powered by renewable energy and was designed as a sustainable alternative to traditional cities.

"We cannot ignore the livability and environmental crises facing our world's cities, and Neom is at the forefront of delivering new and imaginative solutions to address these issues," said Bin Salman. "Neom is leading a team of the brightest minds in architecture, engineering and construction to make the idea of building upwards a reality."

"Neom will be a place for all people from across the globe to make their mark on the world in creative and innovative ways," he continued.

The Line, which was first revealed last year, forms part of the Neom initiative in northwest Saudi Arabia. Neom is part of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 drive to diversify its economy and become less reliant on oil.

3. Wind Energy Utilization:

3.1. Tapping into Skyscrapers' Aerial Potential:

- ✓ Wind Farms: On-site and Off-site Solutions
- ✓ Small Vertical Axis Wind Turbines in Skyscrapers
- ✓ Wind Tunnel-Enhanced Ventilation Systems

3.2. Overcoming Challenges:

- ❖ Turbulence and Vortex Effects: Innovative Wind Turbine Designs
- ❖ Aesthetics and Noise Concerns: Balancing Efficiency and Public Acceptance
- ❖ Optimization of Wind Resource: Meteorological Assessments and Wind Studies

4. Exploring New Energy Solutions:

4.1. Innovative Energy Harvesting Strategies:

- Piezoelectric Generation from Vibrations
- Thermoelectric Energy Recovery from Waste Heat
- Building-Integrated Bio-Solar Systems: Algae-based Energy Conversion

4.2. Energy Storage and Grid Integration:

- Battery Technologies for Sustainable Energy Storage
- Microgrids: Advancing Local Energy Distribution
- Synchronized Energy Management Systems in Skyscrapers

Giant inflated skyscrapers tower above the skyline to transform the urban cityscape as we know it in this surreal AI-generated series by research-based practice ZUMO. The towers, rendered by Midjourney, are constructed from lightweight and flexible materials, rising like colossal balloons. From New York to Tokyo, and London to Dubai, the monuments envision the future of global cities and are designed to adapt to the ever-changing needs of our dynamic lifestyles. Further, symbolizing a shift towards innovative and futuristic yet sustainable architecture, they are powered by renewable energy

and sit with a reduced carbon footprint while paving the way for greener living.

Using Midjourney, Barcelona-based ZUMO delves beyond visualizing familiar, tangible spaces to imagine a surreal concept that unites monumental architecture and sustainable innovation. The Inflatable Skyscrapers harness the power of air to reach unprecedented structural heights, and easily deflate to become compact and transportable. They can be easily moved around and installed, allowing cities to quickly respond to urban development demands and to build with versatility. With their modular design, they can serve as temporary event spaces, emergency shelters, or even as mobile observation decks.

Figure21. Inflatable Skyscrapers: The Future of Global Cities, Barcelona

Figure22. Inflated skyscrapers tower above the skyline to transform the urban cityscape as we know it | rising above Rome

6. Socio-economic and Environmental Benefits:

- Reduction of Greenhouse Gas Emissions
- Energy Independence and Grid Resilience
- Cost-Effectiveness and Long-term Savings
- Green Jobs and Local Economic Development
- Improved Indoor Environmental Quality

7. Challenges and Future Prospects:

- ✓ Economic Viability and ROI
- ✓ Urban Planning and Policy Frameworks
- ✓ Integration of Novel Technologies
- ✓ Public Awareness and Acceptance

These new technologies have a smaller footprint and use the kinetic flow of a stream versus the pressure head (change in water level) method of a large dam. These “small hydro” technologies still provide the potential benefits of this renewable energy source. The shipping industry is currently responsible for delivering about 80% of global trade, but this comes at a cost, as greenhouse gas emissions rose by 4.7%

between 2020 and 2021. Such a trend is partially attributed to an ageing fleet worldwide, since older ships generate more pollution [1,2]. A transition to a new generation of electrified ships integrated with “smart” digital systems is required. Though a full electrification is challenging, mainly on the propulsion front, any partial integration (e.g., lighting and navigation systems) on large vessels would represent an improvement, to which can be added the greater potential for electrification of smaller vessels, such as tugboats, fishing or patrol boats. Moreover, this effort can be extended to the infrastructure responsible for harboring and handling them: the seaports. Alongside the requirements of handling and expediting cargo, seaports are also responsible for receiving cruise ships, harboring marinas and fishing docks, providing shelter for inner harbor areas, and transferring goods and/or people to the hinterland networks, among other activities. Moreover, seaports must adapt to the abovementioned requirements of the shipping industry, from digital connectivity to ship electrification, and promote measures that mitigate the impacts of pollution and climate change (sea-level rise and extreme events), namely, by transitioning to renewable energy sources (RESs) [3,4,5]. It is obvious how important maritime transport and seaports are to the stability and growth of modern societies, as well as how necessary their modernization, sustainability and resilience are to meet present and future challenges. To that end, seaport authorities are mobilizing efforts towards making seaports “smarter” and more energy efficient.

On the smart seaport front, several studies address the opportunities and challenges inherent to implementing advanced digital systems. Ilin et al. [6] emphasize the numerous technological options within the framework of Industry 4.0 and “Smart Cities”. For instance, the concept of “Smart Port” can integrate technologies such as autonomous vehicles, the Internet of Things (IoT), low-cost sensor technologies, Big Data, augmented/virtual reality, robots/drones and 3D printing. Implementing these technologies will, however, require significant upgrades to information technology (IT) services and connectivity. Managing these systems is also challenging, given their novelty and complexity. To assist in this

transition, Min [7] proposes a basic smart-port pyramid architecture, whilst summarizing the necessary software and interconnections (from equipment-level sensors to top-level enterprise resource planning). Durán et al. [8] study the implementation of blockchain and crowdsourcing systems for data transformation for decision-making, namely with the CrowdBC system as a transactional platform for electronic messages. Complementarily, Sangeerth and Lakshmy [9] discuss the role of smart contracts in improving automation, immutability, transparency, decentralization and privacy in the entire shipment process.

Concerning automated terminals and smart-seaport planning, Lakhmas and Sedqui [10] propose a simulator model for congestion management optimization in smart ports, while Yao et al. [11] recommend that seaports invest in a GIS-based Smart Port–Industry–City Spatial Geographic Information Platform, a Port Information Model, a Smart Port Big Data Center and a Smart Port–Industry–City Digital Twin (DT) model. The DT conceptualization is also highlighted in [12], where the authors emphasize not only the opportunities of DT-driven management (e.g., real-time data sharing, predictive optimization and high-fidelity digital representation of seaports) but also the challenges inherent to DT modelling, data connectivity and system security. The latter subject is discussed in [13], where four distinct cyberattack scenarios on container-seaport assets are studied. It is found that all the considered scenarios yield risk levels above the threshold considered acceptable by port authorities, which should be corrected through training, raising awareness, greater control of IT service access and the implementation of backup systems, among other things. Lastly, the role of communication networks is studied in [14,15], which employ an integrated, data-driven DataPorts conceptualization and a crisp/fuzzy-based approach, respectively, for improved data management within smart seaports. All of these systems, alongside others such as cloud computing and radio-frequency identification, comprise the modern definition of smart seaports, distinctive of the fifth and current phase of historical seaport evolution [16]. This phase is also characterized by a strong commitment towards sustainable and energy-efficient seaports,

with considerable investment put into smart electrification and RESs, including those found at sea. On the energy front, a win-win situation presents itself. Marine renewable energy (MRE) can become a significant contributor towards a greener energy mix in seaports, whilst providing highly dense, predictable and directly accessible power sources. Conversely, seaports provide a promising niche market for the demonstration and deployment of MRE technologies, fostering their growth and improvement [17]. Amongst MRE sources, wave energy stands out as a high-density resource that can contribute to Europe's decarbonization goal of becoming the first climate-neutral continent [18]. As seaports are a significant source of air and water pollution [5,19,20], and prominent electricity users [21], they can greatly benefit from including a clean, sustainable and inexhaustible source of electricity in their energy mix. Still, seaports' energy demands are, as of now, fulfilled mainly by means of fossil-fuel energy sources [22]. Transitioning to clean energy sources will not only lead to significant savings in electricity costs, but will also contribute to improving society's perception of ports. According to the European Sea Ports Organization (ESPO), climate change is the top environmental priority of European ports, with air quality and energy efficiency in second and third place, respectively. Ports are increasingly playing important roles as energy hubs and nodes for the blue economy [23]. The ESPO Trends in Port Governance 2022 Report 1 finds that energy is increasingly part of the port business, with ports being prime locations for marine energy production, as well as bolstering the ongoing energy transition. With climate change and air quality as the first and second environmental priorities for ports, it is clear that transitioning to locally harvested energy to provide electricity for port activities and shore-to-ship power (SSP) is the path to follow for seaport authorities to attain their objectives. Furthermore, not only can wave-energy conversion provide electricity to smart-seaport technologies and systems, but it could also add a source of income through the sale of surplus energy to the local grid. Port authorities are promoting considerable efforts towards the objective of becoming energy self-sufficient by producing electricity using MRE sources, such as offshore wind or wave energy [22].

For the latter, numerous wave-energy converter (WEC) concepts exist at distinct technology readiness levels (TRLs), although widespread commercialization has yet to be reached [24]. To that end, it is of the utmost importance to test WECs under real wave conditions, as other means of research and development, such as physical and numerical modelling, have intrinsic limitations. Moreover, there are some cases of the successful implementation of full-scale wave-energy harvesting technologies in ports, which are important demonstrations that this is a possible path towards sustainability and self-sufficiency. However, these need to be implemented on a large-scale and in multiple locations to de-risk their use and incentivize other port authorities to follow the example. Breakwaters are prime port structures for this goal.

Breakwaters are built to provide protection against wave loads on coastal areas and infrastructures, such as berths, maneuvering areas and port facilities. Integrating WECs into port breakwaters can lead to several advantages, namely: (i) the efficient use of space, since the breakwater, or a section of it, will be replaced by the WEC; (ii) facilitating access to the electricity grid through the port's infrastructure; (iii) general infrastructure for construction and maintenance procedures already being in place, as port breakwaters are accessible from the land; (iv) sharing building costs when the WEC's integration is considered prior to the breakwater's construction; (v) promoting water (re-)circulation within the harbor field, enhancing the water quality; and (vi) an improvement in the performance of protection structures due to the efficient absorption of wave energy.

However, there are considerable challenges to the implementation of wave harvesting devices in ports. On the one hand, the lack of progress in WEC technology means that there is still no design convergence, stalling the low level of maturity of WEC technologies [25]. On the other hand, breakwater-integrated WECs cannot compromise the breakwater's main function of protecting the harbor, nor affect the stability of the structure [26]. What is more, the deployment of these devices inside the ports' protected areas can hinder the safe maneuvering of ships and restrict the traffic inside the seaport. These challenges, alongside others such

as the cost of ensuring reliable operation under the harsh marine environment, mean that the current levelized cost of energy (LCoE) for wave energy remains relatively high when compared to other renewable and non-renewable sources. LCoE estimates for wave energy range between EUR 225/MWh [27] to EUR 1220/MWh (for initial, pilot-scale wave-energy projects) [28], with other authors proposing values within this range [29,30]. In comparison, in 2021, onshore wind and solar PV presented LCoE values of EUR 31 and EUR 45/MWh, respectively, and offshore wind an LCoE of EUR 71/MWh [31] (values converted from USD to EUR at the rate of USD 1 = EUR 0.94). Notwithstanding this, the European strategic energy technology plan (SET-Plan) declaration of intent for ocean energy [32] has set ambitious economic targets for wave-energy technologies, as low as EUR 200/MWh in 2025 and EUR 150/MWh in 2030, and this value is expected to reach EUR 100/MWh in 2035 [33].

Complementarily to wave energy, other MRE sources can be harvested in ports, which would benefit from an even more diversified renewable-energy mix, contributing to a reliable and sustainable energy system. MRE also includes wind, tidal, ocean-current, ocean-thermal, osmotic and (floating) solar PV energy, which can all be incorporated into the energy portfolio of seaports. However, each port presents specific characteristics that may enhance or impair the incorporation of these technologies in their jurisdiction areas. Therefore, a thorough assessment of the best site-technology combination is crucial for the successful implementation of MRE in ports. Ramos et al. propose an integrated approach to assessing the wave potential to provide energy to seaports using the Port of Leixões (Portugal) as a case study. Sannasiraj and Sundar suggest selection criteria for WEC technology based on various parameters, such as physical site characteristics, environmental conditions and the regional socio-economic state. Cascajo et al. assess which is the best WEC to integrate into the breakwater of the Port of Valencia, Spain, and estimate its electricity production. Murali and Sundar present a site and technology selection process for tidal energy. Díaz et al. develop and implement a methodology for the comprehensive evaluation of feasible areas for floating offshore

wind farms in the Madeira Islands, Portugal. Despite the clear need for a thorough assessment of site and technology characteristics for the deployment of MRE, the extensive alternatives and significant number of variables make this a challenging selection process for port authorities, who usually lack the technical expertise to carry out this work. Therefore, they could greatly benefit from broad and general guidelines and perspectives on marine renewable energy integration in ports.

Fig23. A sea port that works with renewable energy

In this paper, the aforementioned topics are addressed. To that end, the paper's structure is aligned with its main objectives. Namely, this study will explore the cutting-edge technologies implemented in seaports across the globe, discussing their advantages and disadvantages. The analysis will primarily focus on cyber technologies, followed by a discussion of the measures taken towards achieving sustainable and clean electricity generation—a process known as energy transition. By synthesizing this information, the benefits of these technologies will be identified, and how they can be effectively combined will be explored. Ultimately, this study will culminate in a concise model for the efficient functioning of the seaports of the future. For this purpose, the paper will be divided as follows. Section 2 looks into noteworthy examples of seaports around the world that have promoted digitalization, automation and complementary systems to develop “smarter” infrastructures and logistics. These role models have different contexts, and they encompass varying challenges and technological solutions. However, given the references found in the literature, this review focuses mainly on container-terminal case

studies. Section 3 studies existing cases of ports that have integrated marine renewable-energy harvesting, with a focus on wave energy. An overview of WEC technologies is presented, detailing those that are better suited for integration in ports. Section 4 integrates the examples of Section 2 and Section 3 into a proposal for a smart and energy-efficient seaport, which is expected to serve as a role model for port authorities, stakeholders and researchers to analyze and adapt for their own seaport case studies. Section 5 summarizes the main findings and seaport models identified in this paper, as well as the opportunities and challenges intrinsic to the integration of MRE sources and technologies.

2. Smart Seaports: The Role of Cyber Technologies

This section addresses the subject of smart-seaport role models around the world, detailing the technological innovations and strategies implemented by pioneering port authorities. Although the literature review pointed towards a significant concentration of smart seaports in the Northern Hemisphere—mainly in Asia, Europe and North America—there are noteworthy case studies from the Southern Hemisphere, as well, adding which offers a richer context for analysis. The following sub-sections will address state-of-the-art advances by topics, such as blockchain and DT generation, which are associated with the smart seaports where such developments are taking place.

2.1. Seaport Automation: The Ports of Singapore and Jebel Ali

Seaport automation has the potential to significantly increase harbor activity whilst freeing human resources for other activities and ensuring control and monitoring measures. This can be achieved in numerous tasks and is expected to improve over time, with increasing data being collected. Manual ship (un)loading operations can be controlled via automation systems capable of employing real-time 3D ship models, from hatches to conveyor belts, alongside scans and with GPS support for improved precision. This ensures spatial awareness (e.g., of obstacles, ship and cargo movements, loading checkpoints, start/stop/emergency break orders and fading areas), while (un)loading procedures can be pre-configured and remotely monitored [38].

Furthermore, automated terminals can execute these and other tasks with greater efficiency and precision, especially when supported by smart cranes, automated vehicles and data logistics centers [39], which will reduce costs and shipping time. Port access can be regulated by smart gates, yards and roads [40,41], while data management (e.g., for vessel traffic, terminal operations, gate appointments and traffic, vehicle identification and coordination, and port–hinterland intermodal systems) can be managed by closed-circuit television (CCTV), radio-frequency identification (RFID) and complementary automated cybersecurity, thus promoting greater security and control [42]. The introduction of automated mooring systems, studied in [43], can also lead to a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions (up to 77%, based on the case study). However, setting up these automated networks requires significant modernization investment, interconnectivity between systems, constant monitoring and specialized training to configure and maintain them, as well as reliable energy sources to provide electricity. While the latter is currently being studied with RESs, such as solar, wind and marine energy [44], a practical perspective can be obtained from examples of smart seaports around the globe. First is the Port of Singapore, and specifically the Tuas Megaport, a project that is expected to be concluded by 2040 and which has already been granted the title of the "world's largest automated container terminal" [45]. It is using a four-phase process, starting with the construction of 21 m deep-water berths over 26 km. For phase 2, an area of 387 ha has been reclaimed, enabling a capacity addition of 21 million twenty-foot equivalent units (TEUs)—up to a total of 65 million—by 2040. Currently, caisson fabrication has been completed, and planning is underway for phases 3 and 4 [46]. To ensure full automation, port authorities are developing a "Next Generation Vessel Traffic Management System" capable of providing accurate, real-time situational awareness of the shipping traffic. This will be complemented by the smart data-driven digitalPORT@SG™ tool and a 5G network to enhance port operation efficiency and reduce the turnaround time of ships. Wharf and yard automation will also be implemented, as well as fully autonomous guided vehicles (AGVs).

Maneuverable electrified, automated yard cranes will be implemented to further support cargo transport, which will be managed via a control center for improved productivity and human-resource allocation. These investments will also benefit local IT companies working with the port authorities to build these automated systems, as highlighted in [47]. Lastly, electrified equipment and vehicles [39,48] are expected to reduce carbon emissions by 50% when compared to standard diesel options, complemented by energy certification, the construction of low-energy buildings, smart grids and the implementation of solar energy solutions [46].

In Dubai, the Port of Jebel Ali is also investing in the automation of its infrastructure and equipment. It features one of the world's largest semi-automated terminals, with 67 berths and equipped with 19 automated quay cranes, 50 automated rail-mounted gantry yard cranes and the capability of handling ultra-large container vessels [39]. RFID-based technology was installed in 2017 to monitor/reduce fuel consumption and manage scheduled vehicle maintenance [49]. The port is also receiving a fleet of autonomous intra-terminal vehicles [50]. The automated container-handling system Boxbay is being tested for this seaport, which can hold nearly 800 containers at once [51]. Furthermore, the ZODIAC terminal operating system has been implemented at Container Terminal 3, featuring 18 internal integrated systems, including the cranes' automation system, berth planning and management of the rail and inland container depot. It also enables real-time container tracking and processing, automated vehicle-fleet management and automatic terminal-gate control [52,53]. To power these and other systems, a recent study has analyzed the potential incorporation of RESs in the Port of Jebel Ali [54]. In detail, a prototype experiment was set up, assisted by the numerical software HOMER™, to assess the local wind and solar potential. Total cost reductions ranged between 10% (only solar photovoltaic) and 20.8% (only wind), with a combined reduction of 28.7%.

Fig24. A sea port that works with renewable energy

Incorporation of 5G at Seaports: The Ports of Shanghai and Santos

As highlighted in [55], implementing 5G (and, eventually, 6G) networks in seaports can provide a mobile, yet robust, communication system with low latency, enhanced bandwidth, and capacity that is able to collect and process the vast amounts of data produced by the port's information grid. It is constituted by numerous wireless devices, actuators, data centers and other smart sensors, which establish an encompassing communications network between ships, cargo terminals and other facilities. Therefore, 5G networks promote efficient, interconnected, autonomous and secure seaport operations, whilst boosting port competitiveness and sustainability. Energy use, labor risks and costs are also mitigated when handling/employing automated cranes, autonomous vehicles/drones and condition monitoring systems, as emphasized in [56]. Furthermore, by splitting/slicing the physical network—known as network slicing [57]—into multiple logical networks, based on their attributes and requirements, an improved system flexibility and resource allocation can be achieved since each network is reserved and adapted for specific applications. Even so, there are security, privacy and network function distribution issues yet to be fully addressed. The 5G networks can also be conjugated with immersive virtual reality (VR) [58] through an edge-cloud architecture applied to ship-information visualization (live video), simulation and modelling (e.g., for issuing control commands, assisted driving, remote cargo management, smart security and emergency systems). So long as the virtual scene is sensibly structured to transmit a minimum amount of data, to ensure the required quality-of-

service level, the VR–5G combination should be feasible. However, not all applications are fully verified and implemented, as specific quality-of-service and user-experience parameters are required. These topics are discussed for the real cases of the Ports of Shanghai and Santos.

In the Port of Shanghai, which has the world's largest automated container terminal and competes with the Port of Singapore for the prime seaport ranking position, the pier operations plan is supported by on-site computer systems [6]. Equipment such as cranes and self-driving trucks are managed through monitors in the operator cabs, which can also communicate with a control center up to 100 km away. This enables remote adjustment of the containers' movements and control of the trucks through commands via wireless routers, thus allowing for greater cargo transfer between the seaport and the terminals or warehouses [39]. The 5G network also ensures a very low error and/or container-loss probability, and is crucial for establishing AI-based systems alongside a blockchain and a digital twin of the automated Yangshan Deep Water Port terminal [11]. This network information is integrated with the overall strategy for Shanghai, as a part of the “One Belt One Road” initiative (Yangtze River Economic Belt), and it is managed with the support of FusionCloud's Oracle software [59]. Further details on the 5G implementation and other smart-seaport measures for the Port of Shanghai can be consulted in [60], including its energy sustainability activities.

The Port of Santos, a key port terminal operator in South America, is looking to upgrade its Wi-Fi network (currently with 45 access points) through 5G implementation. Through numerous international partnerships and regulator support (Anatel), the improved network is expected to handle large data transfers for a crane remote-control system (Fluid Mesh), the smart sealing of containers, cargo security and truck arrival expediting, among other improvements [61]. According to port authorities, the 5G network is private and operates on a 3.5 GHz band, thus improving contact between workers and enabling remote, real-time equipment monitoring [62]. It is a pioneering development for Latin American ports, and it complements the expected LoRa (long-range) standard for implementing an IoT network [63]. The

IoT will, in fact, be addressed in the next sub-section of this paper.

From AI to Blockchain at Seaports: The Ports of Montreal and Hamburg

The aforementioned 5G networks are closely related to the concept of the IoT, as well as to artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing (CC) and blockchain (BC). These advanced technologies are expected to enhance smart-seaport operations and improve the overall efficiency of the maritime supply chain. These technologies can potentially revolutionize how the current fifth generation of seaports is managed, as well as create new opportunities for increased collaboration and cost savings, as discussed in [65]. BCs, for example, offer a secure and transparent way for tracking the movement of cargo and information within the supply chain. As highlighted in [8], this is due to the fact that BCs are immutable, centralized and verifiable. Additionally, BCs can help seaports better manage their operations by reducing manual processing time, reducing the risk of errors and increasing the level of transparency in their processes. Complementarily, smart contracts, which are self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement directly written into their code, can also play a key role in the management of smart seaports. These contracts can be used to manage the exchange of goods and services, streamlining processes and reducing the need for manual intervention. By using smart contracts alongside BCs, seaports can automate processes, reduce the risk of errors and fraud, and increase the speed of transactions [9]. As for AI, it can be used to optimize the allocation of resources, reduce waiting times, analyze large amounts of data, make predictions and enhance the overall performance of seaports. By leveraging AI-powered algorithms, seaports can make better decisions and respond more effectively to changing conditions, leading to improved efficiency and lower costs [66]. Nonetheless, data quality should be ensured through AI-related activity regulation and control, which may be jeopardized by sensor faults or human intervention [67]. Finally, the IoT is a critical component of smart seaports, as it provides a platform for the real-time monitoring of assets and data collection. IoT-enabled devices and sensors can be used to track the location of cargo, monitor the

condition of ships and provide real-time information on the status of operations. The IoT, AI and other technologies can be articulated into a reliable automation network, but it is essential to create guidelines and policies for their adoption and management [68]. Two real case studies—the Ports of Hamburg and Montreal—demonstrate the likely path ahead.

The Port of Hamburg, one of Europe's largest seaports, is making significant investments in these new technologies to improve its operations and become a leader in the field of smart ports. As an example, a joint solution for the digitalized release of import containers is being developed by a national consortium of IT companies, as detailed in [69], and being coordinated by the Hamburg City-State Municipal Government to mitigate potential negative effects [70]. One of the goals involves improving the sea-freight-container release by providing a common data platform for sea-freight carriers, terminals, truck companies and freight forwarders. To that end, BC options are being implemented with integrated smart contracts, a project which started in 2018 through Robob (Release Order Based on Blockchain) [71]. While it provides traceable proof of ownership, it can also prompt privacy concerns and/or sensitive information disclosure, given BC's decentralized nature, through data triangulation [72]. Currently, the port is investing in the smartPORT solution, for issues ranging from logistics to energy management, which enables real-time navigation tracking and support, as well as renewable energy supply to cruise liners. Another benefit comes from an intelligent railway system capable of identifying the condition and wear of key intersection points, through sensors, for early-stage smart maintenance/repairs, which reduces downtime. A cloud-based system supports a virtual depot to minimize truck journeys with empty containers, while complementary IoT sensors (Cisco's Wi-Fi Real-Time Location System) are being installed to monitor parameters for pollution, wind speed and direction, and temperature. A central-control-room software, Port Monitor, provides stakeholders in the port with real-time information on harbor activities, and uses AI tools to bolster predictions of maritime and land transport operations. Lastly, port authorities are also investing in e-mobility and

parking management (a smartPORT logistics app for trucks) to further promote the sustainable development of the Port of Hamburg [73].

The Port of Montreal, a major gateway for trade in Canada, is also implementing smart-seaport technologies to bolster its efficiency (e.g., reducing congestion in intermodal transportation [74]) and competitiveness. A prime example comes from the “District3 Center” hub initiative, covering a wide range of port logistics projects. These also involved Concordia University and several start-ups specialized in numerous fields, such as AI, automation and robotics [75]. Among them was Canscan, which is responsible for an AI system that links with terminal cameras, processes the images, identifies issues with containers and forwards the necessary information to the client [76]. Furthermore, the incorporation of AI had a positive impact during the COVID pandemic through the establishment of the Cargo2Ai solution. This AI tool facilitated the handling of goods, particularly critical cargo, to promote faster expediting to populations in need [77]. More recently, investment has been made in the AI Galileo tool, which ought to improve the multi-criteria planning for the dispatch of the port workforce and predict ship arrival times up to 21 days in advance [78]. To bolster trade security, port authorities struck a deal with IBM and A.P. Moller–Maersk to join the TradeLens solution, a BC technology that allows the port to augment its resource planning based on inbound traffic with upstream visibility [79].

Digital Twins of Seaports: The Ports of Rotterdam and Antwerp-Bruges

DTs are a relatively new technology that has been gaining popularity in recent years. A DT is a virtual model of a physical object, system or process that is created using real-time data. With the assistance of complementary modelling tools, such as BIM, DTM and GIS, DTs allow port managers to create a virtual replica of the physical seaport environment—a port information model [11]. This technology has been increasingly used in smart ports to monitor and optimize various elements, such as cranes, containers, vehicles, gates, berths, storage areas and ships, and to make better decisions. By collecting data from sensors and other devices installed throughout the port, with IoT and AI support, the DT

can create a comprehensive and up-to-date view of the seaport’s operations [83]. Though it requires a significant investment in computational resources and connectivity (e.g., a 5G network [84]), this real-time view allows port managers to quickly identify issues and respond to them before they become significant problems. Another benefit of using DTs in smart seaports is the ability to simulate different scenarios. By creating virtual replicas of the port environment, port managers can test different layouts, equipment configurations and traffic patterns to determine the optimal setup for the port. These simulations can also be used to identify potential issues—disruption and recovery scenarios (e.g., power shortages)—as well as to optimize resource allocation and improve operational security, thus bolstering seaport resilience [85]. The use of DTs in smart ports can also help reduce energy consumption and environmental impact. Seaport authorities can reduce the energy required to move goods through the port by monitoring and optimizing the performance of different port elements. This reduction in energy consumption can lead to lower carbon emissions. The increased efficiency and sustainability can also help to make seaports more competitive, as is the case with the Ports of Rotterdam and Antwerp-Bruges.

With an area coverage of over 106 km² that handles nearly 30 000 seafaring vessels per year, the Port of Rotterdam is undergoing a significant transformation in order to enhance its vessels’ capability to autonomously enter or leave this smart port by 2030, as emphasized in [12,60]. To that end, port authorities are investing, alongside companies such as IBM and Cisco, in BIM-based DT technology through 3D computer-assisted design models. By implementing a sensor-based IoT-cloud and AI dashboard, real-time data on hydrological, meteorological and visibility conditions [76] can be obtained and fed to the DT. It features many services and technologies, from port application programming interfaces (APIs) to the “Boxinsider” cargo tracker [39], among others. This enables port authorities to manage several assets, from smart-quay walls to “digital dolphins”, as well as to optimize seaport activities (e.g., berthing) and visibility prediction, reduce vessel waiting time/fuel consumption, and improve cargo handling. Further details on the Port of Rotterdam’s DT and other

smart-port technologies, from 3D printing to Cisco's Edge Intelligence cybersecurity platform (a topic addressed in the next subsection), can be consulted in [12]. Even so, the Port of Rotterdam is not the only major European seaport developing DTs.

Alongside Rotterdam, the Port of Antwerp-Bruges is one of Europe's largest seaports and is equally resolute on becoming a smart port. Digitalization efforts are mainly aimed at establishing a full cargo authentication process through BC—NxtPort's Bulkchain [86]—and the setup of a digital twin [60]. The DT provides a 3D digital map of the seaport with real-time information on ship positioning, energy supply-chain balancing and the dock situation, thus promoting efficient and safe working conditions. The DT is supported by a network of intelligent wharf walls and a computer vision system. The data originates from digital cameras (over 600) and sensors (iNoses to identify harmful gases), which enable accurate ship berthing, reduced waiting times and optimized preventive maintenance, with the assistance of image recognition [66]. The DT is managed through an application—the Advanced Port Information & Control Assistant (APICA)—configured with a 3D interface. There is also a VR system that estimates water levels and the speed of currents within piers [87]. Lastly, efforts are also being made to implement autonomous boats, drones and a 5G network [39,88].

Fig25. A sea port that works with renewable energy

Cybersecurity in Seaports: The Ports of Los Angeles and Tema

As seaports continue to embrace digital technologies and interconnected systems, they become

increasingly vulnerable to cyber threats and accessibility security. Cybersecurity in smart seaports is a critical concern, given the significant consequences of a successful cyberattack, unauthorized access or undetected traffic of illegal goods or people. It could potentially cause significant disruptions to port operations, lead to physical damage or loss of cargo, and even threaten human lives, among other potential hazards identified in [13]. Therefore, port operators must implement robust cybersecurity measures to protect their systems and infrastructure from cyber threats. One of the most significant cybersecurity challenges for smart seaports is the complex and interconnected nature of their operations, as they rely on numerous interconnected systems, such as terminal, cargo and vessel-traffic management systems. Any vulnerability in one of these systems could potentially compromise the entire port's operations, as highlighted in [87]. Therefore, port operators must implement robust cybersecurity protocols across all systems and infrastructure to ensure their overall security. Some of the key cybersecurity measures that smart seaports should implement include regular vulnerability assessments and penetration testing, the use of secure communication protocols and network segmentation. Additionally, smart seaports should implement strict access controls and authentication procedures to prevent unauthorized access to their systems. Smart seaports should also invest in cybersecurity training for their staff, as human error remains a significant cybersecurity risk. Port operators should ensure that their employees are aware of cybersecurity threats and best practices, and that they are adequately trained to detect and respond to potential cyber threats [68]. These matters are, hereafter, addressed for the Ports of Los Angeles and Tema.

Fig26. A train station that works with renewable energy

The Port of Los Angeles, a leading container seaport in North America, has undertaken major efforts to become a smart port, from the development of the Cargomatic Free Flow program to the deployment of “The Signal” cloud-based data tool [39]. However, the incorporation of these advanced cyber technologies presents new risks, which justified the establishment, in 2014, of a Cyber Security Operations Center (CSOC) with a dedicated cybersecurity team. According to port authorities [89], CSOC acts as a centralized hub, enabling proactive monitoring of the port’s internal technology environment whilst preventing/detecting potential cyber incidents. This was followed, in 2015, by a pioneering information-security management certification—ISO 27001. Furthermore, in 2021, the Port of Los Angeles established a multi-year partnership with IBM (USD 6.8 million) to set up an upgraded Cyber Resilience Center (CRC). It is operated by IBM but was designed with supply-chain stakeholders, thus instituting an automated port-community cyber-defense solution where cyber-threat indicators can be shared. The CRC includes an IBM Cloud Pak security platform for efficient data analysis and integration, as well as Security X-Force Threat Intelligence experts responsible for cyber-threat management models, the SOAR Security platform for cyber-threat response coding and a security intelligence center to conduct real-time threat analysis and perform defense-coordination activities. These also allow stakeholders and port authorities to help resume operations following a malicious cyberattack, thus bolstering their awareness and readiness to protect key information systems [76]. Lastly, the Port of Los Angeles is involved in numerous cybersecurity initiatives, such as the chainPORT Cyber Resilience Working Group, the American Association of Port Authorities Cybersecurity Committee and a collaboration with the City of Los Angeles’ law-enforcement departments on cybersecurity. In Ghana, the Port of Tema is the largest seaport and is responsible for a major share of national trade activities. It covers nearly 4 million square meters of land area and receives, on average, more than 1500

vessel calls per year [90]. Such a pivotal infrastructural asset warrants strict security measures, including against cyber threats and/or unauthorized physical access. To that end, the Ghana Ports & Harbors Authorities (GPHA) invested in 24 h CCTV surveillance supported by trained security personnel who monitor all port zones, including entrance and exit gates [91]. In fact, since 2017, the GPHA has implemented pre-gate security checks via ID cards (biometric authentication through finger scanning) and/or online permit application, which is further bolstered by a smart-turnstile screening system. For vehicles and drivers, there is an online platform that regulates both accessibility and communications. This is complemented by an RFID sticker placed onto the windscreen of verified vehicles. Smart readers and cameras, such as optical character recognition (OCR) readers, within portals and yards, can track the locations, movements, cargo and other pertinent data from both drivers’ IDs and their respective vehicles. These tracking systems are also applied in smart cranes and security terminals, in order to monitor the flow of vessels, goods and passengers. All of these data are transmitted to regularly trained IT personnel and the GPHA for improved security and decision making within the Port of Tema. Even so, there are numerous challenges yet to be handled, from the exposure of security systems to weather hazards to potential connectivity shutdowns (e.g., cyberattacks or power shortages). The sizeable amount of generated data requires significant storage capacity, which may be resolved through the implementation of cloud computing [42].

Fig27. A train station that works with renewable energy

3. Sustainable Seaports: The Role of Marine Renewable Energy

As seaports shift to more sustainable and less polluting solutions, such as electric automated vehicles, cranes and networks, their electricity consumption introduces distinct demand coverage challenges. Moreover, as most of the energy consumption and emissions of ports come from ships, which are still mainly powered by diesel [92], SSP (or cold ironing, shore connection or alternative maritime power—AMP) becomes increasingly common and attractive in ports, which also significantly contributes to increased electricity demand in port facilities. Using SSP instead of energy provided by ships' auxiliary machinery during the hoteling period at ports is an effective method to reduce the amount of emissions from ships in the port area [93]. What is more, Directive 2014/94/EU requires European ports to provide facilities to enable SSP by 2025 [94]. Consequently, producing electricity from MRE, which is directly used in ports' activities, is a promising solution to achieve sustainability targets, lower costs and ensure energy self-sufficiency in ports. In this section, a discussion of WEC technologies is provided, specifically those that can be integrated into ports' breakwaters, along with an analysis of seaports that harvest MRE and a discussion of the future of MRE in ports.

3.1. Wave Energy: Resource, Converters and Port Integration

The wave-energy resource is abundant, clean, predictable, constant and virtually untapped, with an order of magnitude comparable to that of the total world electricity consumption. Gunn and Stock-Williams [95] have estimated that the wave power incident on the ocean-facing coastlines worldwide is about 2.1 TW, i.e., 18,500 TWh available annually, about three-quarters of the world's electricity consumption in 2021 [96]. Reguero et al. [97] consider data from six decades and show that the global theoretical offshore wave power is about 32,000 TWh/yr, or 16,000 TWh/yr if the direction of the energy is considered. Despite this enormous potential, wave-energy-harvesting devices have yet to reach the same level of maturity as other more advanced types of renewable energy, and even other MRE, such as offshore wind and tidal stream.

Developers are focusing on utility-scale electricity markets with devices above 100 kW and specialized applications with devices below 50 kW. Hence, only around 25 MW of wave power has been deployed since 2010, with around 3 MW currently operational [98]. This is negligible compared to the available power and should increase considerably in the next few years, especially taking into consideration the ambitious targets set by the European Union for 1 GW of ocean energy by 2030, and 40 GW by 2050 [99].

There are several devices to harvest energy from ocean waves, and more than one thousand patents worldwide [24]. Researchers, inventors and entrepreneurs keep improving old concepts and devising new ones. However, the lack of consensus on what is the best WEC suggests that, until now, no one has been truly successful. Moreover, each device can have different power take-off (PTO) systems, which are the mechanisms that convert mechanical energy to electricity. This brings added complexity to finding the winning concept. The oscillating water column (OWC) is regarded as the first WEC to be conceived and is one of the most studied and developed concepts. It is composed of a chamber of entrapped air, connected to the sea through an underwater opening. The air is pushed through an air turbine by the oscillation of the water's free surface inside the chamber and thus produces electricity. Yoshio Masuda created a navigation buoy powered by wave energy, equipped with an air turbine, which was in fact a floating OWC. These were commercialized in Japan since 1965, and later in the USA [24]. These can also be bottom-fixed structures. Some full-sized devices were later constructed in Norway (1985) and on the island of Islay, Scotland (1991) [100], and there was a breakwater-integrated device at the Port of Sakata, Japan [101], and a bottom-standing plant at Trivandrum, India [102]. Since then, other concepts have been proposed, such as the overtopping device (OTD). The Tapchan comprises a collector, which concentrates the incoming waves, and a water reservoir where the water is temporarily stored and which serves to provide a stable water supply to the low-head water turbine, which converts the potential energy into electricity.

Discussion and Model Seaport Proposal

Based on the topics presented in the previous sections, a model seaport will be proposed that represents the path that port authorities should follow to reach sustainability within the seaport environment. Although this holistic proposal is mainly based on the reference container terminals, the premises and technologies ought to be applicable, after adequate adaptation, to other types found within seaports, from RO-RO to cruise-ship terminals. For instance, within the digital regulatory framework of the EU, Tsoukos et al. [140] propose a cloud-based yard-management platform, CloudYMS, to support operations in RO-RO/RO-Pax ports—including port, supportive, interface and administrative operations—for cargo handling and passenger traffic. The platform has three main layers—presentation or user interface, business logic and data—which incorporate management tools and sub-systems for shipping-lane interface, berthing allocation, gate accessibility, yard parking/storage, vessel (un)loading control and a dashboard for overall status overview. CloudYMS can, therefore, contribute towards greater security, real-time monitoring and greater efficiency in port operations. Another noteworthy case study is the Norvik seaport, in Sweden, for which a simulation model has been proposed to enhance capacity handling [141]. Several modules, from operation to resource, were structured into a multi-level architecture that encompassed multiple agents responsible for transport, customs and planning, among other things. The study incorporated ferries carrying lorries and trailers, with an estimated flow of 200,000 units/year coming and leaving by two ferries/day, considering 4 h as the inter-arrival time. The model was successfully validated and it enabled the identification of potential issues regarding resource capacity, terminal bottlenecks and equipment mobilization. An experimental extension was carried out in [142] to provide a scalable framework to support decision-making processes within RO-RO terminals. It features key performance indicators to assist in discrete event simulations of scenarios regarding intermodal-transport unit flow, planning and operations (e.g., waiting times, berthing utilization, energy consumption and economic analysis). Additional tools to which port authorities may resort include IoT-based platforms, such as Obelisk (e.g., for

improved interoperability of wireless systems and data transfer, stability and scalability based on data volume, and data isolation through multi-tenancy) [143]. To these can be added AI-based algorithms, including the hybrid proposition from [144], which incorporates artificial neural networks, empirical mode decomposition and permutation entropy to enable optimal prediction of daily RO-RO freight traffic. In turn, this allows for advanced planning of schedules and traffic management, thus bolstering decision-making and resource-allocation processes by port authorities.

4.1. Conceptual Framework Overview

The implementation of smart technologies in seaports presents a pertinent antinomy. On the one hand, their integration is aimed at improving the efficiency and quality of port activities, infrastructure management, decision making, and quality control. These are expected to reduce overall expenditures, improve competitiveness and enhance the allocation of resources, including in terms of energy efficiency. On the other hand, smart systems do need energy to operate, and even by assuming low individual requirements, there may be a significant cumulative energy demand to meet. This adds to existing energy demands, particularly for electricity, from port activities. While many of these activities should benefit from digitalization, expenditures related to installing and operating smart systems/equipment (including electricity costs) ought to play an increasingly important role in decision making, investments and budgets by port authorities. Therefore, it will be important to ensure competitive costs from MRE sources, as well as to prove that they can bolster the energy independence, reliability, resilience and sustainability of modern seaports. As demonstrated previously, several ports are already on the path towards an idealized smart and sustainable seaport framework, whose potential can be summarized in a conceptual scenario, as described in the following paragraphs. In a more viable situation, the proposed vessel is assumed to operate with a standardized cargo (e.g., a container vessel), or with cassettes and MAFI trailers (e.g., RO-RO vessels). Vessels arrive at a seaport being monitored and assisted by automated/remotely operated systems (e.g., GPS, autonomous marine vehicles, drones and remote-control stations). The

entry into the port has been simulated through 3D DT models and AI-driven algorithms, in order to prevent potential hazards and optimize both the allocation of resources and the entry path/operations. Sensors measuring weather and wave conditions, as a part of the port's IoT setup, bolster these models and the consequent resource allocation and decision making. Access is also regulated with the assistance of a specialized cybersecurity team. Re-fueling is available through nearshore supply stations and supplementary onshore electric connections (lighting, electronic systems and, if viable, propulsion), which obtain electricity from solar panels, wind turbines and wave-energy converters integrated into the seaport area (from land area to breakwaters). The vessel transmits, in real-time and via a 5G network, data to the control centers managed by port authorities and stakeholders. It includes information on crew, cargo, destination, onshore operations, re-fueling and involved entities, among other things. These data are matched against those of the original smart contracts established between the contracting entities and the port authorities, in order to verify all requirements and detect potential issues. The smart contract is one of many found within the BC and CC digital archives, which promotes their validity, security, transparency and incorruptibility. The vessel reaches the assigned berth, a decision-making process also supported by AI and/or a seaport DT model. Automated mooring systems, transport vehicles, cranes and other auxiliary equipment are standing by to support berthing and (un)loading operations. CCTV, RFID and other monitoring equipment (e.g., IoT sensors and AI-driven image/pattern recognition systems) are remotely managed by specialized port workers, who check the cargo, crew and/or passengers from the newly arrived vessel.

Cargo is (un)loaded with optimal precision and efficiency from vessel to transport vehicles (or vice versa) through automated cranes, which are assisted by IoT sensors, cameras and other monitoring equipment. The data are transmitted in real time thanks to the 5G network, and this further bolsters the reliability of the DT and AI-driven models (Big Data portfolio of the seaport).

Fig28. A train station that works with renewable energy

Cybersecurity teams constantly monitor the operations in conjunction with workers and port authorities. Automated electric vehicles, which obtain electricity from MRE devices installed within the seaport area, receive and tag the cargo for transportation. The information on the destination is received and processed, after which the vehicles begin their pre-defined and optimized journey. Crew and cargo are identified and granted access to the seaport infrastructures through remote scanning, profiling and recognition procedures (e.g., biometric IDs).

Cargo and/or crew and passengers arrive safely at their intended destinations after successfully passing access gates and terminals. Port workers carry on with their activities, with the supporting seaport infrastructure being powered by MRE sources. Once the vessel is ready to leave port, the smart-seaport systems and workers now provide assistance in the exit operations. The vessel is resupplied with standard fuels, which are complemented by electricity for electronics and lighting. This is derived from MRE sources, either through direct supply, e.g., SSP, or by storage units (e.g., in batteries from a seaport storage station). Alongside the electricity supplied to port infrastructures, a significant amount of greenhouse-gas release is avoided whilst promoting a sustainable, energy-independent and eco-friendly seaport. Any eventual disruptions to these and other port activities are closely evaluated by the cybersecurity team and algorithms, in order to prevent and/or mitigate negative impacts (e.g., operations shutdown, data

theft, cyberattacks or illegal access/goods) and restore regular operations rapidly.

Fig29. A Bus terminal that works with renewable energy

This framework, demonstrates the high degree of interconnectivity between smart-seaport and MRE technologies, from which gains in operational efficiency, information flow and system control are expected. However, it also shows the inherent risks of system failure/downtime/corruption, as well as the need for safety, security and redundancy measures to contain potential disturbances of regular operations. There are also limitations intrinsic to system compatibility and viability. For instance, not all vessels can be retrofitted to be fully electric, especially in terms of propulsion units (e.g., diesel engines). Even so, a partial incorporation of MRE-based electricity for specific purposes is plausible. Electric vehicles and cranes operating within the seaport should also be adequately isolated and managed during operations with high-risk fuels, such as oil, gas and other inflammable fluids. This requires staff training, systematic maintenance and monitoring to ensure operational safety.

Sports stadiums consume massive amounts of energy, making them ideal candidates to integrate solar, wind and other renewable energy technologies that reduce operating costs and carbon footprints and help boost a team's brand as a responsible corporate citizen.

Some stadium operators are already installing solar panels and wind turbines or signing power purchase agreements to buy renewable electricity.

Lincoln Financial Field, home of the Philadelphia Eagles football team, installed 11,000 solar panels through an arrangement with NRG, a retail electricity supplier. NRG owns the equipment and

sells power to the stadium at a reduced price. It sells the remaining electricity not needed by the stadium to power other parts of Philadelphia. The arrangement is expected to save the Eagles more than \$60 million in energy costs over the next two decades.

Indianapolis Motor Speedway, the host of the Indy 500 auto race, leased land adjacent to the race track to a private developer that built the world's largest solar farm in a sports facility, a nine-megawatt solar power plant with 39,312 solar panels, in 2014. Clenera and Swinterton built the project on behalf of Centaurus Renewable Energy. The electricity is sold under a long-term power purchase agreement to the Indianapolis Power & Light Company. Centaurus sold the project to Boralex in 2020.

The Minnesota Vikings football team is buying renewable energy credits from wind farms to cover 100% of the electricity used in its US Bank Stadium. The team claims its stadium is the first stadium to be fully powered by wind energy. The team has also taken a series of other measures to reduce its energy costs by \$1.26 million a year. They include using a transparent plastic polymer roof structure that allows natural daylight to light the stadium and allows heat to dissipate for cooling to reduce reliance on lighting and HVAC systems.

The Miami Heat basketball team installed a 24,000-square-foot so-lar canopy at its American Airlines Arena to reduce energy costs by \$1.6 million a year. The canopy has 14 solar skylight rings with a combined capacity of 19 kilowatts. It covers an outdoor amenity space on the east end of the arena overlooking Biscayne Bay. A color-changing LED lighting system is concealed in the soffits of the skylights and produces changing light patterns.

Some stadium owners may be tapping into section 179D tax deductions at the federal level and benefiting from public funding at the state level.

Section 179D of the US tax code provides a tax deduction for building owners and designers who implement energy-efficient systems and technologies in commercial buildings that are 25,000 square feet or larger.

Sports stadium owners can use this tax deduction to offset the costs of installing renewable energy systems such as solar panels, wind turbines, and geothermal systems. (They may also be able to claim

federal tax credits on new equipment to generate renewable electricity.)

Under section 179D, building owners could claim a tax deduction of up to \$1.80 per square foot for qualifying energy-efficient improvements to lighting, HVAC systems and the building envelope. The Inflation Reduction Act increased the deduction to as much as \$5 a square foot.

In the case of sports stadiums, this tax deduction can be applied to renewable energy systems that contribute to the overall energy efficiency of the building. Previously, to qualify for the deduction, improvements had to reduce energy consumption by at least 50% compared to a reference building. The Inflation Reduction Act lowered the energy consumption reduction threshold to 25%.

Many sports stadiums receive large amounts of public funding for their construction and maintenance. For example, Nashville and the state of Tennessee agreed in April 2023 to give the Tennessee Titans football team \$1.26 billion to build a new riverfront stadium in Nashville.

Governments that fund stadiums are increasingly requiring the stadiums to use designs that qualify for LEED certification from the US Green Building Council. LEED is a voluntary non-government program that measures all aspects of the development, construction and operations. A facility can earn up to 110 points, over seven categories, based on its impact on climate change. It is rated for impacts, among other things, on human health, water resources, the "green economy," the local community and natural resources. Awarded points determine the level of LEED certification: certified (40-49 points), silver (50-59 points), gold (60-79 points) and platinum (80+ points).

Thirty-two stadiums in the US professional baseball, football, basketball, ice hockey and soccer leagues have been recognized by LEED. They represent 25% of the stadiums in those leagues.

Defending the Environment

Sports stadiums have a significant environmental impact due to their high energy consumption and carbon emissions. These massive facilities host thousands of spectators and require large amounts of electricity for light, HVAC and other equipment. The average sporting event in a stadium uses enough

energy to power 5,000 American households for a similar length of time.

Thousands of sporting events are hosted every year, and it is easy to see the tremendous amount of energy expended on them and potential carbon emissions. Renewable energy is being used to reduce the carbon footprint of many sports stadiums. Crypto.com Arena, which hosts games for the LA Lakers and LA Clippers basketball teams and the LA Kings ice hockey team, installed 1,727 solar panels that provide enough energy to reduce 10,000 tons of CO₂ emissions. The stadium also established a bank of fuel cells that generate electricity onsite and will displace 1,100 tons of CO₂ emissions over its lifetime.

Inuit Dome, the LA Clipper stadium currently under construction and set to open in 2024, plans on being the first climate-positive stadium. The stadium will use batteries and onsite solar power to run on 100% carbon-free power.

Footprint Centre, home of the Phoenix Suns basketball team, installed a 17,000-square-foot solar array on the roof, producing enough energy to eliminate 440,000 pounds of CO₂ emissions annually.

The Baltimore Ravens football team installed 1,210 solar panels on its M&T Bank Stadium. The energy produced through the panels would create 317 tons of CO₂ emissions annually if produced through non-renewable energy sources. The equivalent carbon footprint is 13,000 tailgaters using propane grills.

The New England Patriots football team installed 3,000 solar panels on its stadium that generate 60% of the facility's energy needs. The solar system is expected to prevent the release of 8,800 metric tons of CO₂ emissions over the next 20 years.

The San Diego Padres baseball team installed 716 solar panels on its stadium, Petco Park. The panels produce enough energy to offset 28 metric tons of CO₂ emissions annually.

Understanding state laws and regulations can provide teams with leverage to access renewable energy at competitive prices. An example is Allegiant Stadium, home of the Las Vegas Raiders football team, which is set to become 100% powered by renewable energy in 2023 after three new solar farms are completed.

Legal maneuvering helped to reach this renewable energy milestone. The team used Nevada Revised

Statutes Chapter 704B to opt out of the public utility company and purchase energy on the open market. This then opened the door to negotiations with multiple potential electricity providers and lowered the energy price through competition. The team eventually agreed to a 25-year contract with the local utility, NV Energy, at a lower price. The electricity NV Energy supplies comes from three new solar projects developed by independent power companies. The sports world is in a prime position to popularize renewable energy as it has the eyes and ears of the public. Studies show that around 13% of Americans follow science and technology news, while 71% follow sports.

Golden 1 Arena, home of the Sacramento Kings basketball team, is the world's first sports stadium 100% powered by solar energy. The stadium has a large purple laser beam that lights the sky after every home win, creating a viral internet meme. Unaware that the laser uses around the same amount of energy as a household dishwasher, sports commentator Colin Cowherd attacked the beam saying it was an "egregious waste of energy." The backlash to Cowherd's comments went viral on social media. It led to discussions about energy use and Golden 1 Arena's use of renewable energy — an example of how sports can draw the attention of a broad audience to the transition to renewable energy.

Being seen as socially responsible and investing in renewable energy is also a good business practice for sports teams. In 2022, two-thirds of consumers said they were willing to pay more for a product they believed to be sustainable.

It also unlocks sponsorship offers from green-conscious companies that do not normally partner with sports teams. After announcing that its stadium would be 100% renewable energy, the Las Vegas Raiders had sponsors reach out to partner with it on deals worth millions of dollars.

Solar-Powered Sports Facilities Paving the Way for Energy-Neutral Stadiums

The Rise of Solar-Powered Sports Facilities

Solar-powered sports facilities have gained tremendous momentum over the last decade. With a growing awareness of the environmental impact of traditional energy sources, stadiums around the world are turning to solar solutions to tackle the challenges of sustainability. These facilities are

harnessing the power of the sun through the installation of solar panels, allowing them to generate renewable and clean energy while reducing their carbon footprint.

Here are some noteworthy features and advantages of solar-powered sports facilities:

- ✓ **Renewable Energy Generation:** Solar power allows stadiums to generate their own energy sustainably, reducing dependence on traditional power sources.
- ✓ **Reduced Carbon Footprint:** Using solar energy reduces greenhouse gas emissions, leading to a more sustainable sports industry.
- ✓ **Cost Savings:** While the initial investment may be significant, solar-powered facilities can experience long-term cost savings by significantly reducing energy bills.
- ✓ **Energy Independence:** By generating their own energy, sports venues reduce their reliance on the grid, ensuring uninterrupted power during events.
- ✓ **Enhanced Resilience:** Solar-powered facilities are less susceptible to power outages, providing a reliable energy source during emergencies.

Key Examples of Solar-Powered Sports Facilities

Solar-powered sports facilities have been implemented worldwide, showcasing the impact of sustainable energy solutions in the sports industry. Here are some notable examples:

Mercedes-Benz Stadium, Atlanta

The Mercedes-Benz Stadium in Atlanta, Georgia, is renowned for its eco-friendly approach. With over 4,000 solar panels installed, this stadium generates approximately 6 million kilowatt-hours of renewable energy annually. This is equivalent to powering over 9,000 homes, showcasing the immense potential of solar power in sports venues.

Melbourne Cricket Ground, Australia

The Melbourne Cricket Ground (MCG) in Australia is another remarkable example of solar-powered sports infrastructure. Its roof, consisting of over 1,000 solar panels, generates clean energy to power the facility. This initiative has reduced the MCG's carbon emissions by approximately 830 tons

annually, contributing to a more sustainable environment.

Stade de Suisse, Switzerland

In Switzerland, the Stade de Suisse integrates sustainability by incorporating solar power into its infrastructure. The stadium's outer shell comprises over 8,000 square meters of solar panels that produce renewable energy, powering more than 500 homes each year. These panels contribute to the reduction of approximately 580 tons of carbon dioxide emissions annually.

The Future of Energy-Neutral Stadiums

The emergence of solar-powered sports facilities marks a turning point in the way we approach stadium operations and sustainability. The potential for energy-neutral stadiums is within reach, where venues can produce all the energy they need on-site without relying on external sources. This future is supported by statistical evidence and industry reports:

- The global solar energy market is expected to reach \$223 billion by 2026, driven by the increasing demand for sustainable energy solutions in various sectors, including sports facilities.
- In 2019, the International Renewable Energy Agency reported that the sports industry could reduce its carbon emissions by 14 million tons annually by committing to a renewable energy transition.
- A study conducted by Indiana University estimated that the implementation of solar panels in all suitable locations across the United States' sports stadiums could generate approximately 3 million megawatt-hours of electricity.

As we move forward, it is essential for sports facilities to embrace renewable energy sources such as solar power. By doing so, stadiums can become pioneers in sustainable infrastructure, creating a positive environmental impact while providing thrilling sporting experiences for fans around the world.

Solar Energy Revolutionizing the Sustainability of Sports Facilities

In this article, we will explore the significant advantages, key takeaways, and mind-boggling statistics surrounding the integration of solar power in sports facilities. So, fasten your seatbelts and let's dive in!

The Advantages of Solar Energy in Sports Facilities

Sports facilities are massive energy consumers, but solar power offers a wide range of benefits that make it the perfect solution for their sustainability goals:

- ❖ **Renewable Energy:** Solar power harnesses energy from the sun, which is an abundant and inexhaustible source. By utilizing solar panels, sports facilities can significantly reduce their reliance on fossil fuels.
- ❖ **Cost Savings:** Once installed, solar panels require minimal maintenance and the energy generated is free. This results in reduced energy bills for sports facilities, allowing them to allocate saved resources to other areas.
- ❖ **Reduced Carbon Footprint:** Traditional energy sources contribute to greenhouse gas emissions. By adopting solar energy, sports facilities can significantly reduce their carbon footprint and demonstrate leadership in environmental stewardship.
- ❖ **Earn Revenue:** Sports facilities with ample rooftop space can generate surplus solar energy and sell it back to the grid, creating an additional revenue stream.
- ❖ **Brand Image:** Incorporating solar energy demonstrates a commitment to sustainability, which enhances the brand image of sports facilities and attracts environmentally conscious sponsors, fans, and investors.

Key Takeaways from Solar-Powered Sports Facilities

- ❖ Opting for solar energy in sports facilities offers long-term cost savings, as it reduces electricity bills and provides a reliable source of renewable energy.

- ❖ Solar-powered stadiums contribute to reducing carbon emissions, thus addressing the global challenge of climate change.
- ❖ The adoption of solar energy in sports facilities enhances their public image, attracting environmentally conscious fans, sponsors, and investors.
- ❖ Sports facilities with surplus solar energy have the potential to earn revenue by selling excess power back to the grid.
- ❖ Installing solar panels showcases leadership in sustainability practices, inspiring other industries to follow suit and create a domino effect for climate positivity.

Industry Statistics That Blow Your Mind

If you're not convinced of the transformative impact solar energy has on sports facilities, take a look at these jaw-dropping statistics:

Energy Savings

Solar-powered sports facilities can save up to 75% on their electricity bills annually, resulting in millions of dollars in savings.

Carbon Footprint Reduction

Average-sized solar-powered stadiums can save over 2,000 metric tons of CO₂ emissions each year, equivalent to planting 37,000 trees or removing 440 cars from the road.

Revenue Generation

Sports facilities with surplus solar energy have the potential to earn revenue ranging from \$15,000 to \$100,000 per year by selling excess power back to the grid.

Reputation Boost

Integrating solar energy in sports facilities increases their reputation and brand value, attracting eco-conscious sponsors and investors while inspiring fans to adopt sustainable practices.

Scalability

Solar energy can be scaled up to meet the specific energy requirements of any sports facility, whether it's a small local field or a massive stadium.

So, there you have it! Solar energy is more than just a buzzword in the world of sports facilities. It is a

game-changer that offers tangible benefits, from cost savings to environmental stewardship. By harnessing the power of the sun, sports facilities are paving the way for a sustainable future. Isn't that incredible? Join the solar revolution today and be a part of this awe-inspiring transformation! Keep innovating, tech junkies!

The Rise of Solar Energy in Sustainable Sports Facilities

Solar power is emerging as a game-changer, allowing stadiums and arenas to reduce their carbon footprint and become more self-sufficient.

Shining a Spotlight on Solar Power

Solar energy is harnessing the power of the sun to generate electricity, and it's totally lit! It boasts a multitude of benefits that make it a slam dunk choice for sustainable sports facilities:

- **Renewable and clean:** Solar power is a renewable energy source, meaning it won't run out like fossil fuels. By using solar panels to convert sunlight into electricity, sports complexes can significantly reduce their reliance on non-renewable resources like coal.
- **Reduced carbon emissions:** Play it cool with solar power! Generating electricity from the sun produces zero greenhouse gas emissions, helping sports facilities lower their carbon footprint and contribute to a greener future.
- **Cost savings on electricity bills:** Wasted money? No thanks! By harnessing solar energy, sports facilities can slash their electricity bills. With the abundant sunlight available in many regions, these savings can be substantial in the long run.
- **Energy independence:** Score big with self-sufficiency! Sporting venues equipped with solar panels can generate their own power, reducing dependence on the grid during peak demand times or potential blackouts.

Solar Slam Dunks in Sports Facilities

The sports industry, known for its passion and commitment, is embracing solar energy like a pro. Numerous stadiums and arenas have already made a slam dunk by going solar:

Levi's Stadium, California, USA

Levi's Stadium, home to the San Francisco 49ers, is leading the charge in renewable energy. This solar-powered stadium boasts more than 1,150 solar panels and a green roof, offsetting a significant amount of its energy needs.

- ✓ Features over 1,150 solar panels.
- ✓ Green roof further enhances energy efficiency.
- ✓ Average annual solar power generation of 6 million kilowatt-hours (kWh).

Mercedes-Benz Stadium, Georgia, USA

The Mercedes-Benz Stadium, home to the Atlanta Falcons, has gone above and beyond with its sustainability efforts. Its circular roof showcases an impressive array of solar panels, generating clean energy for the stadium and surrounding areas.

- ❖ Includes 4,000 solar panels on its circular roof.
- ❖ Annual solar energy generation of around 6 million kWh.
- ❖ Offsetting approximately 1,210 metric tons of carbon dioxide annually.

Melbourne Cricket Ground, Victoria, Australia

Down under, the Melbourne Cricket Ground (MCG) is batting for sustainability with its solar power initiatives. Its energy-saving features and solar panels are game-changers in the sports world.

- Installation of over 1,000 solar panels.
- Generates approximately 410,000 kWh of clean energy annually.
- Equivalent to powering 50 typical Australian households for a year.

Key Takeaways: A Solar Slam Dunk for Sustainable Sports Facilities

The rise of solar energy in sustainable sports facilities is an epic win! Here's a recap of the key takeaways:

- ❖ Solar power is a renewable and clean energy source that reduces carbon emissions.
- ❖ Solar-equipped sports facilities can save big bucks on electricity bills.
- ❖ Generating solar power promotes self-sufficiency and decreases reliance on the grid.

- ❖ Stadiums like Levi's Stadium, Mercedes-Benz Stadium, and the Melbourne Cricket Ground have championed solar energy in the sports industry.

So, tech lovers, gear up for a greener future of sports. Let's celebrate the rise of solar energy and cheer on the sports facilities making a slam dunk in sustainability!

From Goals to Solar Panels: How Sports Facilities Are Going Green

So, let's grab our virtual tickets and take a closer look at how sports facilities are going green!

Taking a Sustainability Shot: The Rise of Solar Panels

Solar panels have become the MVP (Most Valuable Player) in the sports industry's green playbook. These photovoltaic marvels are scoring major points by converting sunlight into clean and renewable energy. Let's huddle up and explore some of the reasons why solar panels have become a game-changer:

- **Environmental Game Changer:** Solar panels help facilities reduce their carbon footprint, decrease reliance on fossil fuels, and significantly cut down on greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Cost Savings:** Implementing solar panels can slash down electricity bills, allowing sports facilities to redirect their budget towards improving player facilities or organizing community outreach programs.
- **Enhanced Brand Image:** Going green not only attracts eco-conscious sponsors and partners, but it also enhances the reputation of sports facilities as responsible stewards of the environment.
- **Bright Future for Energy Storage:** Advancements in energy storage technologies, such as large batteries, equip sports facilities to store extra energy generated by solar panels and use it during peak demand periods or when the sun isn't shining.

Game-Changing Plays: Eco-Friendly Practices in Sports Facilities

Stepping up their sustainability game, sports facilities are implementing a host of eco-friendly practices, leaving no room for waste. Let's dive into some of the key practices driving the green revolution in the sports industry:

- ✓ **Efficient Lighting Systems:** Sports facilities are increasingly switching to energy-efficient LED lights, which not only reduce energy consumption but also boast longer lifespans, reducing maintenance costs.
- ✓ **Smart Water Management:** Implementing innovative technologies like sensors, smart irrigation systems, and rainwater harvesting allows sports facilities to optimize water consumption while maintaining top-notch playing surfaces.
- ✓ **Waste Reduction and Recycling:** Sports facilities are championing waste reduction by implementing robust recycling programs, reducing single-use plastics, and encouraging fans to separate waste properly.
- ✓ **Transportation Solutions:** Encouraging fans and staff to use public transport, carpool, or providing ample bicycle parking facilities reduces carbon emissions and promotes eco-friendly commuting.

The Scoreboard: Key Takeaways

The sustainability game plan of sports facilities is yielding impressive results. Let's review some key takeaways:

- ✚ Renewable energy, particularly solar panels, is playing a pivotal role in reducing carbon emissions and making sports facilities more self-sufficient.
- ✚ Eco-friendly practices, such as efficient lighting, smart water management, waste reduction, and promoting sustainable transportation, are helping sports facilities achieve their green goals.
- ✚ Green initiatives not only benefit the environment but also contribute to cost savings, enhanced branding, and a positive impact on local communities.

- ✚ The sports industry serves as a role model in spreading awareness about sustainability and inspiring other sectors to embark on their own green journeys.

So, tech geeks, the next time you cheer for your favorite team, remember that the sports world is going beyond just making plays; they are stepping up as responsible players in the game for a sustainable future. It's time we all join this green team and score big on sustainability!

Exploring the Green Revolution Solar Power in Sports Complexes

However, with the increasing concerns regarding climate change and the need to reduce our carbon footprint, sports complexes are adopting solar power as a sustainable and cost-effective solution.

Solar power has emerged as a game-changer in the quest for clean energy. By harnessing the sun's rays and converting them into electricity, sports complexes can significantly reduce their reliance on traditional fossil fuel-based power sources. This shift not only helps to mitigate the environmental impact of sporting events but also provides a range of benefits for the sports industry as a whole. Let's delve into the advantages and key takeaways of solar power in sports complexes:

Sustainability and Environmental Impact

Sports complexes consume enormous amounts of electricity to power lighting systems, sound systems, scoreboard displays, and more. By adopting solar power, these facilities can decrease their dependence on non-renewable energy sources, such as coal or natural gas. This transition to cleaner energy greatly reduces the carbon emissions associated with sporting events, making them more sustainable and environmentally friendly.

- Reduced carbon footprint
- Lower emissions of greenhouse gases
- Contribution to global efforts to fight climate change
- Improved air quality in the surrounding areas

Cost Savings and Economic Benefits

While the initial setup costs of solar power systems may seem high, the long-term economic benefits far outweigh the investment. Sports complexes can significantly lower their utility bills by generating

renewable energy onsite. This reduces their reliance on expensive grid electricity and offers a stable source of power for years to come.

- ❖ Lower energy costs and reduced utility bills
- ❖ Potential for revenue generation through excess energy production
- ❖ Long-term financial savings
- ❖ Opportunities for sponsorship and partnership with renewable energy companies

Energy Independence and Reliability

By embracing solar power, sports complexes gain energy independence. They no longer have to rely solely on the grid and are shielded from potential power outages or fluctuations. With their own renewable energy generation systems, sports facilities can continue hosting events without interruption, even during grid failures or emergencies.

- ✓ Reduced vulnerability to power outages
- ✓ Enhanced reliability and stability of energy supply
- ✓ Ability to function off-the-grid during emergencies
- ✓ Consistent power availability for sporting events

Brand Image and Community Engagement

A bold commitment to sustainable practices, such as solar power, can significantly enhance a sports complex's brand image. It positions the facility as environmentally conscious and socially responsible, which resonates well with fans, sponsors, and the local community. By adopting solar power, sports complexes can inspire and engage the community in renewable energy initiatives, fostering a sense of pride and unity.

- ✚ Elevated brand image and reputation
- ✚ Increased fan engagement and loyalty
- ✚ Opportunities for educational programs about renewable energy
- ✚ Positive impact on the local community's perception of the complex

According to recent statistics, the rapid adoption of solar power in sports complexes is on the rise. In 2020 alone, over 300 sports facilities in the United States installed solar energy systems, generating a

total capacity of 47 MW of electricity. This accounts for a significant reduction in carbon emissions, equivalent to removing over 9,700 cars from the roads annually.

The integration of solar power in sports complexes not only benefits the environment but also provides substantial advantages to the sports industry. By leveraging the power of the sun, sports facilities can improve their sustainability, achieve long-term cost savings, ensure energy independence, and enhance their brand image. As the world continues its journey towards a greener future, solar-powered sports complexes are at the forefront of driving change.

The Rise of Solar Energy in Sustainable Sports Facilities

Solar energy, in particular, is emerging as a popular choice for powering these venues. In this article, we explore the rise of solar energy in sustainable sports facilities and its implications for the environment, cost savings, and community engagement.

Why Solar Energy?

Solar energy offers numerous advantages that make it an attractive choice for powering sports facilities:

- **Renewable and Clean:** Solar energy is a renewable resource that relies on the sun, ensuring an endless supply of power without harming the environment. It produces no greenhouse gas emissions, making it clean and sustainable.
- **Cost-effective:** While the initial setup costs of solar panels may seem high, the long-term savings are significant. Sports facilities can reduce their energy bills by generating their own electricity, saving money in the process.
- **Reliability:** Solar energy systems are reliable and require minimal maintenance once installed. With advancements in technology, panels are now more efficient and capable of generating power even on cloudy days.
- **Independence from the Grid:** Solar-powered sports facilities can reduce their dependence on the grid, ensuring continuous power even during blackouts or electricity shortages.

- **Community Engagement:** By adopting solar energy, sports facilities actively contribute to the community and inspire others to embrace sustainable practices. They become role models for environmental responsibility.

Implications for the Environment

Sports facilities are known for their significant energy consumption, from powering lighting fixtures and air conditioning systems to operating large video screens. By harnessing solar energy, these venues can significantly reduce their carbon footprint and mitigate environmental impacts. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IREA), solar energy can account for about 40% of the total electricity needed to power a sports facility, leading to a substantial reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

Sports stadiums, with their vast rooftop spaces, are in a prime position to maximize solar energy generation. By installing solar panels, they convert sunlight into electricity while utilizing otherwise underutilized space. Additionally, excess energy generated can be stored in batteries for later consumption, ensuring uninterrupted power supply even after sunset or during inclement weather.

Cost Savings and Financial Benefits

The financial advantages of solar energy in sports facilities cannot be overlooked. According to the Solar Energy Industries Association (SEIA), the cost of solar panels has dropped by 70% since 2010. This reduction in costs, combined with long-term savings on energy bills, makes solar energy an economically viable option for sports venues.

Furthermore, through net metering programs, sports facilities can sell excess energy back to the grid and receive credits on their electricity bills. This creates an additional revenue stream and further reduces energy costs. The savings accrued through solar energy installations can then be reinvested in other sustainability initiatives, maintaining a positive cycle of environmental responsibility.

Community Engagement and Inspiration

Sustainable sports facilities play an essential role in inspiring communities to embrace renewable energy solutions. By adopting solar power, these venues

become educational platforms, showcasing the benefits and feasibility of harnessing clean energy sources.

Moreover, solar-powered sports facilities encourage community engagement through educational programs and initiatives. They can organize workshops and events to raise awareness about renewable energy, inspiring people to adopt sustainable practices in their daily lives. This engagement creates a ripple effect, leading to increased adoption of solar energy within the community and beyond.

Key Takeaways

- ❖ Solar energy is on the rise in sustainable sports facilities due to its renewable and clean nature, cost-effectiveness, reliability, and community engagement advantages.
- ❖ Sports facilities powered by solar energy significantly reduce their carbon footprint and mitigate environmental impacts.
- ❖ The decreasing cost of solar panels, combined with long-term savings on energy bills, makes solar energy financially viable for sports venues.
- ❖ By adopting solar power, sports facilities inspire communities to embrace renewable energy solutions and contribute to a sustainable future.

In conclusion, solar energy is revolutionizing the world of sustainable sports facilities. As these venues adopt clean and renewable energy sources, they contribute to environmental preservation, reduce costs, inspire communities, and set an example for other industries. With the constant advancements in technology and the increasing demand for sustainability, solar energy is set to shine even brighter in the future.

Merging Sustainability and Sports: How Solar Energy is Changing the Game

Let's dive into how solar energy is changing the game for sports and the planet. Professional sports are inherently a copycat industry. From Major League Baseball's Moneyball revolution to the NBA's renewed focus on 3-point shooting driven by the Golden State Warriors and Steph Curry, in-season and championship success quickly becomes a blueprint for other teams to follow. Another recent

trend spreading across sports has many hoping it will also follow suit: arenas and stadiums not only adopting sustainable and environmentally friendly practices, but putting those efforts front and center for fans, players, musicians, and anyone else who enters the building.

Much like the broader world of commercial real estate, arenas, and stadiums have been slowly adopting sustainable practices over the last few decades, from recycling programs to energy efficiency efforts. But several major sports facilities across the U.S. have taken this to another level in recent years, and their operators and owners hope that the success they've seen across multiple fronts creates real momentum around the idea of environmentally friendly stadiums.

Mercedes Benz Stadium, home of both the NFL's Atlanta Falcons and MLS's Atlanta United, became the first pro sports venue in the U.S. to achieve LEED Platinum Certification in 2017. Footprint Center, home of the NBA's Phoenix Suns and WNBA's Phoenix Mercury, works directly with the materials science company that holds its naming rights to eliminate single-use plastic from the arena and on other sustainable practices. The bar across sports was set even higher in 2021 when Climate Pledge Arena in Seattle opened and not only became the first net zero certified arena in the world but served as a call-to-action for Amazon's push for companies globally to be net zero carbon by 2040.

"Venue operators are relatively quickly understanding their opportunities and their responsibilities as it related to operating more sustainability," said Chris Granger, CEO of OVG360, a management company that works with more than 300 venues across the world ranging from arenas and stadiums to amphitheaters and performing arts centers.

"Sports teams and venues have a platform on the topic of social change, and we have the ability to shine a light on issues that matter in a way that many businesses don't," he said. "I think our venue operators are saying 'Okay, we get it. Now what do we do about it?'"

The trend in sports is not dissimilar to what is being seen across other industries: a desire from businesses to be better stewards in their community and connect with the growing number of people putting an increased emphasis on environmentally

friendly actions, coupled with the fact that many of these measures also have a solid business case attached to them.

When work to renovate KeyArena in Seattle began, there were many discussions on how to introduce sustainability measures not only for construction goals but also operational goals, said Seattle Kraken and Climate Pledge Arena senior vice president of sustainability and transportation Rob Johnson.

That quickly evolved into making an arena that could be a "beacon of a sustainability district," Johnson said, which helped attract the attention of Amazon, who in 2019 co-founded the Climate Pledge initiative to have companies, organizations, and partners work together to address the climate crisis and solve the challenges around decarbonizing.

That led to what has become the Climate Pledge Arena. Its efforts include being zero-waste by using compostable containers and reducing single-use plastic use, conserving water by retaining rainwater for reuse, and not using fossil fuels in the arena for daily use – including electric-powered Zambonis for Kraken games.

Setting a zero-waste goal at Atlanta's Mercedes-Benz Stadium

Mercedes-Benz Stadium has been on its own sustainability path since it opened in 2017, with operator Arthur Blank pushing his AMB Sports and Entertainment Group (AMBSE) executives to set a higher standard for an environmentally friendly stadium.

The stadium opened as the first LEED Platinum stadium in the U.S., but "that was just the start," said Steve Cannon, vice chairman of AMBSE.

"Anyone can make that incremental investment into your building, but if operationally you don't perform in a manner that's consistent with that, you're leaving something on the table," Cannon said.

That has led to a focus on getting to zero-waste status, which the stadium first achieved in 2020 for an Atlanta United match, Cannon said. After an investment of about \$1 million to retrofit the building and put in other measures to achieve that zero-waste consistently, the stadium has now reached that goal.

In its 2022 fiscal year, there were more than four million pounds of waste at the stadium, and more

than 91% of that was diverted away from landfills, according to Andrew Bohenko, Mercedes-Benz Stadium sustainability coordinator.

That required a significant amount of education for employees and fans, and also working with vendors and other departments within the company to ensure that “there was buy-in across all our of two-million-square-foot footprint,” Bohenko said.

Ultimately, the stadium saw more than 95% compliance from fans putting trash in the right receptacles, and it projects a \$400,000 yearly return on its initial investment while spending about 13 cents per guest for its overall zero-waste efforts right now. AMBSE has even created a “playbook” for other stadium operators to follow if they also want to get to zero waste.

“Everyone understands that the environment is our number one global challenge. It’s reached a level of critical mass where people have moved past green-washing, and they’re making substantive changes to their business practices,” Cannon said. “The platform that sports represents has a disproportionate impact on our society at large, so if you think about the aggregated impact of all ballparks and stadiums across America diverting waste from landfills that’s huge, but where it becomes even more important is the power of the platform to influence other businesses – then you start to really make meaningful change.”

Johnson said Seattle’s zero-waste push has led to savings as well, as composting costs less than sending garbage to a landfill. Another impactful revenue opportunity related to the arena’s sustainability push, according to Johnson, is reaching new fans.

“Folks under 40, who we are all cultivating as critically important fans to our success in the future, identify the environment as one of their top three global concerns,” he said. “So, we believe it’s not just the right thing for us to do for the planet, but we also think that we’re speaking to a demographic that is key to the future of the success of our industry.”

Kristen Fulmer, senior director of sustainability at OVG360 parent company Oak View Group, said while it’s clear that “sustainability can be a good business,” there still can be confusion about what that really means.

“Sustainability is kind of noisy; ESG is a catchphrase that everyone knows but doesn’t quite

know the meaning of, so there are some things that we can demystify about it,” Fulmer said. “We want to help them figure out what are things that are relevant to me, my specific building, my specific market, my community, my employees, so that they can hone in on something that’s really unique.”

Granger pointed to efforts like Sacramento’s Golden One Center where the arena is powered by 100% renewable and solar energy, and Toronto’s Scotiabank Arena, where a deep-lake water cooling system utilizing nearby Lake Ontario helps keep the building cool and eliminates the need for air conditioning compressors.

Making sustainability a key part of any construction or building project is also becoming table stakes for bonds, loans, and other financial measurements, both Granger and Fulmer noted, a critical factor for many of the aging arenas and stadiums across the U.S. likely due for upgrades or full replacements in the coming decade.

It also matters more for artists and athletes. Granger said there are musicians asking for vegan or plant-based food options or asking buildings to let fans bring reusable water bottles to reduce the impact of single-use plastics.

Johnson said that when singer Billie Eilish came to Seattle to perform in 2022, her tour rider required the arena to not use single-use plastics for at least the night that she was to perform.

“That was a big inspiration for us; if Billie Eilish can come through your building and you’ll move to no single-use plastics for one night, why couldn’t you do it for the other 364 nights,” he said. Ahead of the tour date, Eilish’s mother and sustainability advocate Maggie Baird asked to tour the arena, telling Johnson and Seattle’s team that they “operationalized” the rider,” Johnson said. Seattle has given tours to numerous artists, teams, athletes and other organizations wanting to see more of the building’s practices in action.

All of these factors are pointing towards a future where sports and sustainability are more intertwined, Fulmer said. “In the sustainability world we often say that imperfection gets in the way and creates inaction, and I think people are always really scared to not quite be perfect. In the sports world of course we all want to be perfect or always win,” she said. “Here, small wins are really important, and they’re leading to bigger wins.”

The Rise of Solar Power in Sports Venues

Solar power has become an increasingly popular energy source in sports venues worldwide. From stadiums to arenas, solar panels are being installed on rooftops, parking lots, and even on the exterior facades of these iconic structures. Here's why solar power is being widely adopted in sports venues:

- ✓ **Reduced operating costs:** Solar energy significantly reduces energy costs for sports venues, helping them save money in the long run. By generating their own clean energy, they can rely less on traditional power sources and mitigate the impact of rising energy prices.
- ✓ **Lower carbon footprint:** Emphasizing sustainability, sports venues are exploring solar power as a means to reduce their carbon footprint. By switching to clean energy, these venues can considerably decrease greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to a greener future.
- ✓ **Enhanced community engagement:** Implementing solar power in sports venues is not only an environmental statement but also a way to engage with local communities. Establishing partnerships with solar energy companies and promoting sustainable initiatives can resonate with fans, sponsors, and the general public.

With numerous benefits attached to solar power, sports venues are increasingly featuring installations that highlight their commitment to sustainability. From soccer stadiums to basketball arenas, these initiatives are driving positive change within the industry.

The Impact of Solar-Powered Sports Venues

Now, let's take a closer look at the positive impact solar-powered sports venues can have, beyond reducing their carbon footprint:

Renewable Energy Generation

Solar-powered sports venues generate renewable energy utilizing photovoltaic panels. By harnessing sunlight and converting it into electricity, these venues ensure a constant and reliable source of power for lighting, heating, and cooling systems.

Energy Efficiency

Sports venues consume massive amounts of energy during events, with extensive lighting, sound, and climate control needs. By integrating solar power, these venues can significantly reduce their dependence on the grid, leading to decreased energy consumption and more efficient operations.

Energy Independence

Solar-powered sports venues are less reliant on traditional energy sources, making them more resilient during power grid disruptions. They can continue hosting events and providing essential services when others might face challenges due to power outages.

Educational Opportunities

Solar installations in sports venues present unique educational opportunities by promoting solar energy awareness among fans and visitors. Interactive displays and guided tours can educate attendees about the benefits and possibilities of renewable energy, inspiring them to adopt similar practices in their own lives.

The Evolution of Solar-Powered Sports

As solar energy continues to demonstrate its potential in sports venues, its applications are expanding beyond traditional methods. Some exciting developments include:

- ✦ **Flexible solar panels:** Innovations in solar technology have led to the development of flexible, lightweight solar panels that can be integrated into surfaces like windows, stadium seating, or even playing fields. These advancements allow venues to maximize solar energy capture without compromising aesthetic appeal.
- ✦ **Solar-powered charging stations:** Sports venues are increasingly incorporating solar-powered charging stations for electric vehicles within their premises. This not only supports the adoption of electric transportation but also encourages fans to choose more sustainable means of commuting to games.
- ✦ **Battery storage systems:** Pairing solar installations with energy storage systems allows

sports venues to store excess solar energy generated during the day and use it during peak demand periods or when sunlight is limited. This approach increases energy resilience and reduces reliance on the grid.

By embracing these advancements, sports venues are elevating their sustainability efforts, bridging the gap between sports, technology, and environmental consciousness.

The Future of Sustainable Sports

The integration of solar power within sports venues is just the beginning of a broader movement towards sustainability in the sports industry. Here are some key takeaways on the future of sustainable sports:

- **Innovative design and construction:** Future sports venues will be designed to maximize energy efficiency and incorporate renewable energy systems from the very start. The construction industry is increasingly adopting sustainability-oriented practices, contributing to the creation of greener sports facilities.
- **Community engagement and activism:** With sustainability becoming a key concern for society, fans are eager to support sports teams and venues that actively promote eco-friendly initiatives. This has the potential to influence their loyalty and drive positive change within the industry.
- **Collaboration with renewable energy providers:** Partnerships between sports organizations and renewable energy companies will play a crucial role in shaping the future of sustainable sports. These collaborations can facilitate the exchange of knowledge, resources, and funding necessary to accelerate the adoption of clean energy alternatives.

Solar energy has already begun transforming the sports industry. From reducing operating costs to fostering community engagement, solar-powered sports venues serve as an example of how sustainability and sports can go hand in hand, creating a greener and more responsible future for all.

Revolutionizing Sports Venues Harnessing Solar Energy for a Greener Future

So, grab your shades and let's explore the solar-powered stadium revolution!

The Bright Side of Solar-Powered Sports Venues

Imagine a world where stadiums shine brightly, not just under stadium lights, but also from the sun's rays. Here's why sports venues are ecstatic about going solar:

- ❖ **Reduced carbon footprint:** Solar-powered stadiums significantly reduce carbon emissions, helping to combat climate change. According to the Solar Energy Industries Association, a typical 1 MW solar installation can prevent the emission of 1,300 metric tons of carbon dioxide annually.
- ❖ **Energy cost savings:** Going solar helps sports venues minimize their energy costs by generating their own electricity. With the rising costs of traditional energy sources, this advantage is a game-changer.
- ❖ **Energy independence:** Solar-powered sports venues have the freedom to operate independently from the grid. They can generate their own energy, making them less susceptible to power outages and ensuring uninterrupted play.
- ❖ **Enhanced sustainability:** By embracing solar power, sports venues become beacons of sustainability. They inspire athletes, spectators, and the wider community to adopt eco-friendly practices.

Shining Examples of Solar Success

The solar-powered sports venue revolution is already gaining momentum across the globe. Here are some shining examples:

Levi's Stadium, California

Levi's Stadium, the iconic home of the San Francisco 49ers, boasts an impressive solar system. With over 1,000 solar panels covering the canopy and parking lots, the venue generates approximately 20% of its electricity demand. This reduces the stadium's carbon footprint by around 820 metric tons annually!

Perth Stadium, Australia

Perth Stadium, a jewel in Australia's sporting crown, has embraced the power of the sun by installing an enormous solar PV system. This system can produce 364 MWh annually, equivalent to powering around 56 households for a year. With this solar installation, the stadium firmly places sustainability at the forefront.

A Glorious Future Ahead

The sky's the limit for solar-powered sports venues. The future holds promising possibilities, including:

- **Smart energy storage:** Incorporating cutting-edge energy storage technologies enables stadiums to store excess solar energy and utilize it during peak demand periods.
- **Electric vehicle charging stations:** Sports venues can provide convenient charging infrastructure for electric vehicles, promoting clean transportation options.
- **Solar-powered fan experiences:** Imagine stadium seats equipped with solar panels that charge your devices while you cheer for your favourite team. Solar-powered fan experiences could soon become a reality.

In the not-too-distant future, solar-powered sports venues will become the norm, leading the charge towards a more sustainable world. By reducing carbon emissions, saving on energy costs, and inspiring fans, these stadiums are revolutionizing both sports and the environment.

So, the next time you attend a match or cheer on your team, take a moment to appreciate the solar panels gleaming above. They represent a greener future where sports and sustainability go hand in hand. The revolution starts here!

Shining a Spotlight on Solar Power in Eco-Conscious Sports Complexes

One such solution that has been gaining traction is solar power. With its numerous benefits and potential for generating clean energy, solar power is shining a spotlight on eco-conscious sports complexes worldwide.

The Advantages of Solar Power in Sports Complexes

Cost savings

By harnessing the power of the sun, sports complexes can significantly reduce their energy costs. According to a study by the Solar Energy Industries Association, installing solar panels can yield up to 75% savings on electricity bills.

Renewable energy: Solar power is a renewable energy source, meaning it will never run out. By using solar power systems, sports complexes can be less reliant on fossil fuels, reducing their impact on the environment.

Environmental benefits

Solar power produces clean energy, emitting zero greenhouse gases and reducing the carbon footprint. This is a huge advantage for eco-conscious sports complexes aiming to contribute to a more sustainable future.

Durable and low maintenance

Solar panels require minimal maintenance and can last for over 25 years. They are designed to withstand extreme weather conditions, making them a reliable and durable choice for sports complexes.

Key Takeaways for Sports Complexes

Embrace sustainability: By implementing solar power systems, sports complexes can showcase their commitment to sustainability and inspire others to follow suit.

Significant cost savings: Investing in solar power can lead to substantial long-term savings, allowing sports complexes to allocate funds towards other areas of improvement.

Positive environmental impact

By reducing reliance on fossil fuels, sports complexes can contribute to a cleaner and greener environment for athletes, fans, and surrounding communities.

Part of a larger movement: Joining the solar power movement in sports complexes helps drive the transition towards renewable energy on a global scale and encourages other industries to follow suit.

Solar Power in Eco-Conscious Sports Complexes: The Stats

The installation of solar panels can reduce carbon emissions by an average of 35,180 pounds per year, per sports complex. According to the International

Renewable Energy Agency, by 2050, solar power capacity is expected to increase by six times its current capacity, reaching a staggering 8,519 GW globally.

The North American solar power market showed substantial growth of 12% in 2020, with installations reaching 19.2 GW. From 2010 to 2020, the price of solar photovoltaic modules dropped by approximately 90%, making them more affordable and accessible than ever before. Surprisingly sports venues are pioneers in the promotion of sustainability. Many sports venues have jumped on the sustainability bandwagon to construct or renovate their structure in a race to minimize their carbon footprint, preserve their green legacy, and take the lead in innovation.

Surprisingly sports venues are pioneers in the promotion of sustainability. Many sports venues have jumped on the sustainability bandwagon to construct or renovate their structure in a race to minimize their carbon footprint, preserve their green legacy, and take the lead in innovation. The competition is wild. These are some of the five top stadiums which have incorporated some of the most impressive sustainability elements into their operations, raising the bar in what is expected from sustainability in sport.

Amsterdam ArenaA

The Amsterdam ArenaA, the home of the football club Ajax, is powered by more than 4,200 solar panels and one wind turbine. The main building comprises an impressive energy-generating escalator and the stadium has also installed an energy storage system powered by second-life batteries from used electric vehicles.

The xStorage Buildings system from used Nissan LEAF batteries not only provides backup power for the stadium but also distributes energy to the surrounding neighborhood when needed, to alleviate pressure on the grid.

Rainwater from the stadium roof is collected and re-used to water the grass field, significantly reducing consumption of valuable freshwater. Residual heat is used to keep frost off the playing field, a move that requires no additional energy to be wasted. Fans are encouraged to reduce their travel emissions by using active mobility, electric vehicles or trains. The car

park offers free charging points and every visitor is entitled to discounts on train tickets.

Figure30. Amsterdam ArenaA

Mercedes-Benz Stadium

The Mercedes-Benz is the official home of Atlanta Falcons for the US National Football League (NFL) & United FC and Atlanta United FC of Major League Soccer (MLS). Last November, it became the first professional sports stadium to receive a platinum Leadership in Energy & Environmental Design (LEED) certificate, a global standard for measuring the sustainability of buildings.

Energy consumption is 29 percent less than what the average stadium consumes, due to energy efficiency and renewable energy projects. The stadium is equipped exclusively with LED lighting and LED video boards, and is less reliant on the grid due to 4,000 rooftop solar PV panels.

The stadium has a stormwater management system, with the capacity to store over 2 million gallons onsite, preventing flooding in the surrounding areas. In addition, due to water-efficient fixtures, the stadium uses 47 percent less water than the baseline standard for stadiums.

When the location was decided, the use of active mobility was at the core of the decision making. Fans can easily walk to the event through new pedestrian-friendly walking paths that allow connectivity between communities. A bicycle valet programme operates on event days, and the available electric vehicle charging stations can charge up to 48 cars simultaneously.

Figure31. Mercedes-Benz Stadium

FIFA World Cup 2022 stadiums

Qatar's organizers for the 2022 football World Cup have pledged that all 12 venues (9 new and 3 renovated) will be zero-carbon emitting, as an obligatory requirement from FIFA to deliver a zero-carbon tournament. Special climate controls within the venues will also manage the excess 40C temperatures during the event.

As a showcase in 2010, Arup Associates built the first carbon-neutral stadium, a 500-seat mini stadium, to demonstrate to FIFA that Qatar's bid is achievable. The engineering firm managed to celebrate the potential of solar power to achieve a 100 percent zero emitting stadium despite the difficult and usually carbon intensive cooling challenge.

The technology used is simple: solar power turns the sun into energy and this energy is turned into cool air. The air is then circulated around the stadium to keep the players and the spectators comfortable. When tested, the temperatures outside hit 44°C. But inside the stadium, the temperature was a cooling 23°C even with the roof open. What is left to see is how the new actual venues will manage to scale up the technology, leading the way for the stadiums of the future.

Figure32. FIFA World Cup 2022 stadiums

In such situations, poor water management can result in both water shortages and for allowing the spread of water-borne diseases, making it the primary threat to the sustainability of acceptable levels of public health (Koop and van Leeuwen, 2016). Even when a disease is not water-borne, clean water is an obvious requirement for reducing both its severity and the rate of infection. For example, basic sanitation (regular hand-washing) is the principal measure to be used in the fight against every kind of microbial infection including the recent COVID-19 pandemic and therefore access to an adequate amount of clean water can be considered a basic necessity to deactivate viruses causing microbial infections (Armitage and Nellums, 2020). More directly, a previous water crisis in Flint, Michigan (U.S.) showed that any deterioration in water quality can become the cause of serious public health problems, and the political debates that occurred at the state and federal levels around this event proved that even in developed nations the supply of clean water has significant social aspects that cannot be avoided (Gostin, 2016).

The lengthy relationship between the water and energy sectors has become ever more concrete, largely due to the fact that the water sector has been required to undergo a sharp development process to meet increased environmental legislation (Clos et al., 2020); put simply, more stringent discharge standards lead to higher levels of energy and chemical consumption, and increased greenhouse gas emissions (Wang et al., 2015). In addition, the aforementioned rapid urbanization and the resulting level of complexity in water and wastewater

facilities has dramatically increased the associated energy requirements (Niu et al., 2019), and has resulted in the water sector currently accounting for 4% of global electricity demand (Medeiros et al., 2021). This situation is a clear indication that energy and water management should be considered indivisible, and to meet these new challenges the concept of a “water and energy nexus” has arisen in policy making (Yin et al., 2018).

To date, wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) have generally been operated without specific energy considerations and without significant efforts being made towards material recovery. However, increased global water scarcity, accompanied by the depletion of energy and resources, have forced changes to be made to the current treatment process. The new “nexus” concept allows energy and resource recovery to be maximized, and requires that WWTPs are designed and operated as refineries rather than as installations for treatment and disposal. Several literature reviews have been prepared recently on the importance of energy and resource recovery in WWTPs, as well as innovative treatment technologies that can be used to transform conventional treatment plants into those that meet the circular economy concept. While some of these studies provide a good systematic review, most of such studies focus on specific issues such as the energy balance of WWTPs, recovery of value-added products, or emerging wastewater and sludge treatment configurations. Also, recent work on this topic has often concentrated on technology and energy & resource recovery. It can be suggested that a literature review that provides the milestones of environmental sanitation starting from the first civilizations and the introduction of the first wastewater treatment systems together with new treatment concepts and future needs could provide a better understanding of the biorefinery concept-based treatment. Since the upgrade of conventional WWTPs to high-tech WWTPs includes several aspects in terms of engineering, resource management, economy, policy-making, etc., it would be beneficial to take the subject from a higher perspective.

Fig33. A refinery that works with renewable energy

This review aims to present a concise summary of state-of-art of wastewater management and propose ways forward for wastewater treatment. In the paper, a historical timeline of environmental sanitation and the first attempts at wastewater treatment was provided in order to provide the evolution of sanitation works. Thereafter, the current paradigm in wastewater treatment, which solely considers the treatment objective in general, and problems and limitations encountered in the existing treatment technologies were given. Following the taking picture of the general situation, the paper offers an explanation of the fundamentals that will allow treatment-based wastewater treatment systems to be upgraded to ones that meet the requirements of the biorefinery concept. A detailed descriptive illustration was also presented aiming to highlight distinctions between treatment-based and biorefinery concept-based wastewater treatment systems.

Balancing energy in municipal and industrial wastewater treatment

Since water and wastewater treatment processes account for 4% of global electricity consumption, it's vital that reducing energy consumption is in focus for industrial and domestic wastewater treatment. Not only for sustainability but also for economic reasons. Transformation of municipal wastewater treatment plants from energy consumers into energy generators now couples the water and energy sectors together into a new game-changing industry. Regulation of rotating equipment is a vital element in generating over 100% surplus power in

wastewater treatment, for energy-neutral water cycle management of entire communities.

Fig34. A treatment plant that works with renewable energy

Substantial amounts of fresh water are consumed in modern society and all too often poorly treated wastewater is discharged into the environment. To counter these trends, modern digitalization offers a great degree of controllability in municipal wastewater treatment resulting in higher quality of treated water. And ZLD and MLD processes reduce the volume of industrial wastewater discharge.

To improve the reuse of water and reduce the discharge of industrial wastewater, a zero liquid discharge (ZLD) or a minimal liquid discharge (MLD) treatment system is often used. ZLD and MLD are ambitious wastewater management strategies that enable the plant or facility to recover most of its wastewater for reuse. The standard process is energy intensive, but applying optimized reverse osmosis processes energy consumption can be reduced by up to 75%.

Wastewater treatment plants

Typically, water and wastewater treatment processes account for 25-40% of a municipal electricity budget. Water and wastewater facilities are therefore normally the single-largest electricity consumer for a municipality. Therefore for many years, extensive use of AC drives and real-time online sensors have created the basis for advanced real-time process control to optimize energy efficiency, cutting energy consumption by 20-40%. Now these methods combine with energy production within the wastewater treatment plant, to enable entirely new ambitious levels of energy efficiency. Powered by methane produced in the digester of the

wastewater plant, the 'bio refinery' or 'Water Resource Recovery Facilities' demonstrate that wastewater has now become an energy resource.

Some of the most advanced water management systems achieve complete energy self-sufficiency of the water cycle. The energy recovered from wastewater treatment process not only covers the plant's own needs, but also the energy needs for drinking water production and distribution as well as wastewater pumping. In other words, the whole water cycle can be considered energy neutral.

A precondition for energy neutrality is a control handle in the form of an AC drive available for all rotating equipment, so that the fully computer-controlled facility can adapt to the changing load.

Fig35. A treatment plant that works with renewable energy

The refinery consists of the following processing units: two CDUs, a VDU, a naphtha splitter, a straight run naphtha stripper and utilities, including wastewater treatment, a power plant and a tank farm with an oil heating system. Since it does not have any upgrading units, its configuration is simple and its Nelson complexity index is 1.83. The refinery therefore runs as a bitumen and cut-back production plant. Intermediate products like straight run naphtha, kerosene, gasoil and heavy gasoil are sent to another TüpraÅ refinery, Kirikkale, for further conversion and processing. Kirikkale's final products of gasoil and gasoline are then returned to Batman to meet demand in the city and its surrounding region. Although the refinery was originally situated far from any centres of population, it is now surrounded by urban development. In addition, since the refinery is 60 years old, energy efficiency was not considered an important target in its original design. For both of

these reasons, the refinery needs to be sensitive and ready to take precautions to support the environment, with due regard for emissions and human health. Revamping of old and inefficient equipment and systems is another important issue that requires the refinery's attention with regard to economic performance and reliability. After the handover of Tüpraş Batman refinery from the government to Koç Holding in 2006, several projects to improve energy efficiency and environmental performance, including many refinery revamp projects, were implemented.

Fig36. A refinery that works with renewable energy

Strategic planning and implementation

Since the scale and complexity of the refinery was known, it was not difficult to figure out the gap between actual energy consumption and target consumption based on a benchmark case. Additionally, preliminary calculations were made in order to see the potential for energy savings in the refinery. These calculations covered topics such as energy savings in the heat exchanger network by setting a delta T approach; existing process furnace efficiencies and their potential savings; comparison of steam production costs in different boilers at different grades; and a comparison of cogeneration, back pressure turbine and extractive condensing turbine efficiencies. After identification of areas for improvement (AFI) and their potential savings, a series of actions was taken and project implementations were set in motion.

Fig37. A refinery that works with renewable energy

Increase condensate recovery

Steam leaks were observed everywhere in the plant. Most of the traps were leaking and at many points in the steam network there were no traps. A condensate return system was not operated. Estimations based on some of the leaks gave a loss of >100 kg/h each. In order to enhance the overall efficiency of the refinery and increase steam and condensate recovery, a project team was established with the support of all refinery staff. Within the scope of the project, 300 traps were replaced and many condensate collectors, 2000 meters of carbon steel pipe, 5000 meters of insulation material, a condensate flash drum and a condensate pump were installed. The main condensate collecting lines were divided into two components for clean and oily condensate. Oily condensate was routed to a newly installed condensate recovery and treatment system, including precoat filters and activated carbon filters, in order to remove oil and recover flash steam in the surface condenser. Moreover, instead of raw water, demineralized water was used in the system as a cooling utility. In this way, the temperature was increased from 20°C to 67°C before the existing deaerator in the power plant, and steam consumption in the deaerator decreased by 55% as a consequence. With the increased condensate recovery ratio, the utilization capacity of the demineralization plant was reduced to 50% of its base capacity, resulting in 10 540 Gcal/y of energy saving.

Reduce steam leaks and consumption

As AFI-1 indicates, prevention of steam leaks caused by instrumentation tracing lines vents, direct

open heating vents and steam traps blowing to atmosphere was carried out continuously between the years 2006-2011 across the site. In other words, instrumentation tracing line vents were collected in a separate flash drum and the produced flash steam was used in the dearator. Additionally, new steam tracing lines and steam traps were installed for heating the bitumen production lines. Some of the existing blowing traps were replaced and other leaking traps were repaired.

Fig38. A treatment plant that works with renewable energy

Review power and steam generating strategies

Specifications for the steam boilers and turbogenerators in the power plant are shown in Table 1. Since the boiler tubes underwent widespread retubing and plugging in the past, their efficiencies and reliability were low. Boiler H-504 did not have the capacity for required electricity production, therefore two of boilers H-501, H-502, H-503 were run together with H-504 in order to supply steam demand for the turbogenerator and so sustain operational reliability. The most efficient boiler, H-508, was run for process heating purposes at 13 barg and 250°C. The situation for the turbogenerators was similar: their efficiencies were very low and their electricity unit production costs (depending on the load) were very high, in the region of 4-8 times that of the grid, except for back pressure production. However, the back pressure turbogenerator was designed by taking into consideration a thermo-catalytic cracking unit that was dismantled in 2007, hence its design capacity was too big and this resulted in a case of unbalance in steam-electricity production. Since there were boiler tubes failures every 3-4 months, the first action for improvement made was to improve the

quality of demineralized water in order to reduce failures, and to increase the reliability and efficiencies of the boilers. As a result, the number of online boilers was decreased subsequently from four to one and H-508 began to be employed for both turbo generation and process heating by using the existing let-down station.

Fig39. A factory that works with renewable energy

As a result, between 2006 and 2011, process steam consumption was reduced from 264 000 t/y to 182 000 t/y. This means that over a period of five years there was a 31% reduction in total process steam consumption, or a 45% saving in steam per tonne of crude processed, resulting in 75000 Gcal/y of energy saving based on total annual process steam consumption, and 130000 Gcal/year of energy saving based on tonnes of crude processed. When it came to electricity production, import from the grid was maximised with minimal site production. Later, electricity production was stopped completely for reasons of economy. Additionally, the standby conditions of the existing diesel generator were increased and, by taking the peak electricity demand of the refinery into account, one more diesel generator was installed in case of emergency and to provide redundancy. The inefficient J-503/504 condensing turbogenerators, with just 17% operating efficiency (based on electricity produced per unit of fuel consumed in the boiler), were stood by as redundant items but received weekly maintenance, for instance lubrication of rotors and bearings. As a result, 53 000 Gcal/year of energy saving was accomplished.

Fig40. A factory that works with renewable energy

Sustainability begins in the chilled aisle. But we're not just talking about organic yogurt. The refrigerators themselves make up around 60 percent of a supermarket's total energy requirements, followed by around 20 percent for lighting. And it doesn't stop there. What opportunities should supermarket operators now be using to minimize operating and energy costs and greenhouse gas emissions?

1. Set up an efficient energy supply

The easiest way for supermarket operators to save on energy costs in the long term is through efficient refrigerator technology and lighting. These technologies will improve the energy balance, and help to meet national and international climate targets and the associated reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

The options:

- ❖ Reduce refrigerant quantities
- ❖ Use natural instead of chemical refrigerants
- ❖ Integrate air conditioners in the refrigeration units
- ❖ Switch to energy-efficient LED lighting
- ❖ Optimize and monitor system operation

Detailed energy monitoring will help supermarket operators to record and evaluate their ongoing energy use. Load peaks will be highlighted and weaknesses revealed. Further efficiency-increasing and cost-minimizing measures can be quickly and easily derived from this information.

2. Generate and store solar power

On average, supermarket operators spend 1.6 percent of their annual net sales on energy. With a PV system on the roof and a battery-storage system,

supermarket operators can generate their own electricity. Intelligent energy management will automatically balance generation and requirement to ensure that the largest possible amount of solar power can always be used.

In the modern energy industry, supermarket operators also become prosumers by making their excess energy available to the utility grid and thus contributing to keeping the grid stable. Wind and solar energy are not always available at the same time and grid feed-in fluctuates accordingly. Network services are therefore becoming increasingly important and also mean attractive additional revenue.

The large, unused capacity of refrigeration units can also be used here. Their compressor capacity has to be designed for the warmest and coldest days. Once all food safety requirements have been met, supermarkets can, on average days, make their unused capacity available as thermal storage.

The benefits:

- ✓ Handle load peaks
- ✓ Minimize energy costs
- ✓ Optimize rate of self-consumption
- ✓ Continue to supply cold chains and important consumers during power outages
- ✓ Provide utility grid services
- ✓ Contribute to the energy transition

Fig41. A view of a supermarket that works entirely using renewable energy.

The same model can be used in museums, libraries, schools and hospitals.

3. Generate additional income

Supermarket operators can use direct marketing to sell their solar power to interested buyers. The best prices are achieved when the demand for electricity

and, in turn, the price on the power exchange, is particularly high.

Direct marketing can be an alternative to the feed-in tariff. The PV system operator receives a fixed feed-in tariff from the grid operator to feed their electricity into the grid. The grid operator or the relevant transmission grid operator is reimbursed the difference between the market price and the price paid to the PV system operator. This reimbursement is financed by the consumers, as per the EEG (Renewable Energy Sources Act) apportionment.

The benefits:

- ✚ Generate attractive additional revenue
- ✚ Participate actively on the electricity market
- ✚ Reduce EEG apportionment
- ✚ Use excess heat and cold to power the local area

4. Benefit from a green image

Consumers and employees are becoming more demanding. Consumers are demanding more organically grown, local and fairly traded products. Employees don't want to work for just any company. They want to achieve something meaningful and be rewarded for their efforts at work.

The benefits:

- Provide customers with free charging stations for electric vehicles (and retain them with attractive reward schemes)
- Use your ecological footprint as a selling point
- Make renewable power generation visible in your company's entrance area
- Include more sustainable products in your range

Supermarket operators can score several points at once with a sustainable energy efficiency policy. They can involve customers and employees with green energy. They keep energy costs to a minimum, turn shopping into a positive experience and become more attractive employers. And that's how supermarkets can become one of the main pillars of the energy transition.

Danish industrial machinery manufacturer Danfoss has opened a new energy efficient supermarket in Nordborg, Southern Denmark.

The 1,500 square metre 'Smart Store' showcases a range of innovative refrigeration and heat capture and reuse technology that helps it save on operating costs, limit food waste, and improve food safety.

According to Danfoss, the space is 50% more energy efficient than a standard supermarket with a first-generation CO₂ cooling system and no energy efficiency solutions. The Smart Store's cooling systems are run solely on CO₂, which has a climate impact around 4,000 lower than traditional hydrofluorocarbon refrigerants (HFCs). The supermarket also uses high-end case controllers which can analyse and optimise the performance of refrigerated display cases, helping to save energy while still ensuring food safety.

The space additionally has a heat recovery unit which can capture excess heat from the cooling systems to provide warmth for the entire store and the local community through the district heating network. Reusing excess heating from the cooling systems in this way is predicted to reduce heating costs by up to 90%.

Fig42. A view of a supermarket that works entirely using renewable energy. The same model can be used in museums, libraries, schools and hospitals.

While most retailers operate a heating and hot water system and a separate refrigeration system, Danfoss notes its novel approach integrates supermarket refrigeration, heating, air conditioning, and ventilation, which reduces the store's carbon footprint and brings down installation and operational costs.

Installing doors on fridge and freezer cases allows the Smart Store to cut electricity bills by a third, says Danfoss. It says it also uses up to 85% less electricity by swapping incandescent bulbs for LED lights. Given that they don't emit heat, UVA, or infrared rays, LED are better for preserving fresh foods like fruits, vegetables, and fresh meat and fish. The supermarket is fully powered by solar energy, provided by 100 kW solar panels on the roof of the building.

To tackle food waste, Danfoss has also installed its Alsense Food Retail in the Smart Store, an IoT (Internet of Things) cloud service platform. IoT devices are fitted with different types of software that allow them to communicate with other systems over the internet. With Alsense Food Retail, users can send operational data to the cloud application and receive real-time insights on how the business can throw away less food. The technology also has a 24/7 monitoring and alarm system which prevents large scale waste. For instance, if a supermarket freezer case were to breakdown overnight, the application would alert the store, dispatch the necessary technicians, and even perform remote repairs on site.

Jürgen Fischer, President at Danfoss Climate Solutions commented on the launch of the Smart Store: *"We have developed this new Smart Store supermarket with partners and customers to demonstrate that it is possible to build a climate friendly and super-efficient facility, using world-class heating and cooling technology. Our new 'Smart Store' proves that the future is now. This supermarket is purpose-built for the world ahead of us; a world of more urbanization, larger populations, greater energy demands, a growing need for cooling, and efficient food storage."*

Fischer added that the space will operate as "a 'live' testing site", to trial more innovative and sustainable solutions for supermarkets. He concluded: *"we hope [it] will inspire food retailers around the world to move towards zero emissions supermarkets – while making economic sense."* Sainsbury's has launched a new flagship supermarket in Hook which plans to use only half the energy of a similar-sized store and 25% less electricity than its other most energy-efficient supermarkets. The new 25,000 sq ft supermarket will operate using 100% renewable electricity and will not rely on any fossil fuels.

The store is also part of a new trial that uses doors on chilled cabinets, keeping cold air in and reducing their energy demands by up to 60%.

Further energy savings have been driven by adding lids on frozen food display cabinets, which work in the same way.

Fig43. A view of a supermarket that works entirely using renewable energy. The same model can be used in museums, libraries, schools and hospitals.

It will replicate and build on everything that works well in newly-constructed shops, as well as retrofitting its existing estate with the technology wherever it can. Sainsbury's property director Patrick Dunne said: "I'm immensely proud of everyone at Sainsbury's who has helped to deliver what is a ground-breaking new store for us, the learnings from which will be used in future store investments.

"Sainsbury's Hook is the culmination of many years of innovation, hard work and progress towards a more sustainable future for our business.

"I'd like to take the opportunity to thank the local community for your support and patience whilst we constructed this store. I hope everyone will agree it was worth the wait, not only for the new offer customers can now enjoy but for the progress in store sustainability it represents."

Sainsbury's currently operates with 100% renewable electricity and by the end of 2023 the retailer projects that up to 40% of its electricity will come from new-to-the-planet wind and solar power. The improvements in the store's efficient energy design are part of Sainsbury's wider commitment to becoming Net Zero in its own operations by 2035.

Last week, Sainsbury's revealed it had converted the delivery fleet of its Nine Elms London superstore to

electric vehicles as it looks to reduce its operations emissions.

The new fleet will make on average over 2,000 deliveries each week, saving almost 57 tonnes of carbon annually.

Ever increasing global population, power demands, modern life styles, environmental pollution and at the same time growing awareness; people from all walks of life are pushing towards the utilization of clean and renewable sources of energy (Allouhi et al., 2022). Furthermore, new and innovative ideas and applications like water desalination (Lotfy et al., 2022), combined cooling/heating (Chakravarty et al., 2022), hydrogen production (Arsad et al., 2022) and EV (Costa et al., 2022) are being promoted to be implemented based on renewable energy sources. The EVs are being used in many countries and hence to facilitate the charging of these vehicles peer-to-peer charging stations are required at supermarkets, government official buildings, industrial premises, hospitals, schools, universities, recreational facilities, and so on. This study addresses the possibility of developing renewable energy based EV's charging stations at five supermarkets in Morocco. The forthcoming paragraphs are devoted to discuss the EVs and electric vehicle charging platforms (EVCPs) and utilization of hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES) to supply power to supermarkets and EVCPs.

Sustainable development and net zero energy concept

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) defined by all United Nations Member States seek to promote living conditions of people while protecting the environment, at the present time and in the future. There are 17 SDGs, which needs to be addressed urgently by all member countries (United Nations, 2022). The Division for DSDG in the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) sustains the SDGs and their related thematic problems, such as energy, water, climate, oceans, urbanization, transport, and science and technology. The 17 SDGs identified include among others no poverty, no hunger, healthy conditions and well-being, quality education, clean water and sanitation; affordable and sustainable energy as well as responsible consumption and production (United Nations, 2022). According to

UNDESA, transport is one of the major sectors that need urgent attention to mitigate the atmospheric pollution, which is being addressed in the present work.

The international community has reached to a consensus that to avoid the worst climate damages, the global carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions should reduce to net zero around 2050 and 2070. The Net-Zero Standard proposes a unique, strong, and science-based perception of net-zero concept. Net zero, simply, refers to the balance between the amount of GHG generated and the amount withdrawn from the atmosphere. Net zero scenario can be reached when the amount GHG added in to the atmosphere is almost equal to the amount taken away. Hence, in order to achieve net zero emissions, green and clean sources of energy have to be used in all sectors including transport, utilities, industries, residential, commercial, and public to name some.

Fig44. A view of a supermarket that works entirely using renewable energy. The same model can be used in museums, libraries, schools and hospitals.

Electric vehicle and electric vehicle charging platforms

In UK, almost 8% (2059) of the total electric vehicle (EV) charging units of 26,000 are located at supermarkets. In 2020, there were 1112 EV units located at supermarkets while in 2021 this number increased to 2059, an increase of 85%. The total number of superstores, having EV charging facilities has doubled from 607 in 2020 to 1300 in 2021 (Whitlock, 2021). From 2015 to 2021, the total sales of peer-to-peer electric vehicle charging market exceeded US\$ 800 Mn (FactMR, 2021). Furthermore, rapid adoption of EVs in developing

countries and government incentives, EVs demand is projected to increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 20% and will achieve US\$ 6.7 Bn between 2022 and 2032 (FactMR, 2021). The existing and future EV market is encouraging and hence should be promoted wherever possible. Various government have taken initiatives to promote the implementation of EVs.

EVs have started playing an important role in the public transportation system of many developed and developing countries. They are expected to have a positive impact (Boonraksa et al., 2018) such as reduction of greenhouse gases emissions into the atmosphere (Lata-García et al., 2018), high efficiency (Huang et al., 2014) and simple arrangement (Planas et al., 2015). Mainly, there are 5 types of commonly available EVs: (i) fuel-cell electric vehicles (FCEVs), (ii) extended range electric vehicles (EREVs), (iii) hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), (iv) plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), and (v) battery electric vehicles (BEVs) (CAA, 2022). The methods used to charge the EVs include (i) vehicle-to-vehicle (You and Yang, 2014), (ii) vehicle-to-grid (Contreras-Ocana et al., 2016), and (iii) vehicle-to-building (Contreras-Ocana et al., 2016). Mainly, the EVs are charged using Alternative Current (AC) or direct current (DC) and there are three standards for EVs which include the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE), and CHArge de MOve (CHAdeMO). EVs are driven by electric motors which are 80%–95% efficient (Canals et al., 2016) compared to conventional vehicles (CVs) which are 20% or less efficient (Åhman, 2001). This makes a perfect case of the promotion of EVs beside other many benefits. However, the growth of EVs, on global and regional levels, is still slow due to limited capacity of batteries which can be loaded on vehicle and slow charging process (Hardman et al., 2016, Kempton, 2016).

Some of the issues related to EV charging on the grid include voltage drop and fluctuations, grid overloading, harmonics, and system losses (Anoune et al., 2018, Karmaker, 2019) but its deployment can still bring a new look of power grid and ultimately EVs can be considered as portable energy storage media. Boonraksa et al. (2018) conducted a simulation study of a photovoltaic (PV) and wind

hybrid power system (HPS) for EV charging station by modifying IEEE 33 bus system and concluded that the integration of the HPS with the distribution system proved to be reliable even during peak load times. In Morocco, a renewable energy system (RES) comprising of PV, wind, and grid; was proposed for charging EVs in transportation sector (Anoune et al., 2018).

A study of EVCP, based on PV-Grid HPS with battery storage system (BSS) in conjunction with efficient energy management strategy, was conducted by Eltoumi (2021). The proposed system resulted in improved overall performance, reliability, and the cost. Grid connected wind and solar PV based HPS with or without BSS are being considered to be attractive sources of energy for EVCPs as per the review analysis (Alkawsii et al., 2021). According to this survey, there exist a limited number EVCPs even for domestic EVs and hence new systems should be introduced for charging the heavy-duty vehicles. HOMER Pro software was used to study the techno-economic feasibility of a PV-Wind HPS for EVCPs for five locations in China and found that PV-Wind-Battery was the best option to serve the charging stations (Li et al., 2022). Furthermore, the most economically suitable system was reported for Nanjing and the least suitable for Zhengzhou in China. In Chile, an economic feasibility study of PV-Wind hybrid power systems, with and without battery, for supplying power to the residential buildings and providing electricity for EV charging station was conducted (Salles-mardones et al., 2022). The study found that the proposed HPS without battery backup was more profitable due to lower capital cost and shorter payback time.

To minimize the uncontrolled adverse effects of electric vehicle charging (EVC), a method was proposed for the hybrid EVCP coupled with PV and BSS by utilizing the exact calculation of renewable energy share coming from the battery (Fig. 1) (Petrusic and Janjic, 2020). The system consists of an energy source (PV) and energy storage (battery), and finally to the power grid. The EVs are charged with power available from renewable source and supplemented with battery and the grid if required. The extra power, at any time, is fed to the battery and then to the grid. The multi-criteria optimization methodology of charging/discharging schedule of a

BSS and EVC level was based on the minimization of charging costs and battery degradation and maximization of renewable energy share. A PV powered EVCP, under varying irradiation conditions of Vietnam, was analysed and the authors reported that the economics is greatly dependent on solar irradiation intensity and the feed-in tariff (FIT) (Minh et al., 2021). Authors used HOMER Grid software to model the EVCP in combination with renewable sources of energy.

Renewable energy systems for supermarkets with electric vehicle charging platform

Renewable energy systems have numerous applications and one such application providing power to superstores and at the same time feeding the EVCPs in parking areas to charge the EVs. The supermarkets are considered to be the highest energy consumers in the commercial sector (Franco et al., 2021). In the USA, the total number of Supermarkets and other grocery stores was about 63 thousand with sales value exceeding 765 billion \$ in 2021 (Statista, 2022). The energy intensity of supermarkets is around 537.6 kWh/m² which is more than 2 GWh of electricity annually for a normal supermarket (Sun et al., 2021).

According to Ong et al. (2013), the breakeven process of PV systems installed in supermarket across U.S. vary by a factor of Deshmukh and Pearce (2021) investigated the possibility of developing PV canopies on parking areas of supermarkets and providing EVCPs for charging the EVs to the customers. The study revealed a potential of 3.1 MW for each Walmart Supercentre in the U.S. and this capacity is expected to charge more than 100 EVs. Further analysis showed that Walmart Supercentres in U.S. only could establish 11.1 GW installed capacity of PV canopies over their parking lots sufficient to charge 346,000 EVs.

It was reported that daily mean PV production potential of 4 kWh/kW in Italy suits to achieve a self-sufficiency of 50%–70% and hence the food stores will be the most suitable option for PV utilization either for self-consumption or for EVCPs (Franco et al., 2021). Usually, fast EV chargers are found at workplaces, supermarkets and shopping centres, train and bus stations, and airports (Cheikh-Mohamad et al., 2021). The Evergo Company in Panama, completed the installation of 200 EV

charging stations as of December 2021 and also established such EPCPs at Riba Smith superstores (Fig. 2), Costa del Este, Bella Vista, Transistmica, and Brisas del Golf (Angulo, 2020). PV based EVCPs have been installed at distribution centres in Basson and Centurion, 38 in supermarkets in South Africa and Namibia, and one in home office (Raghubir, 2021).

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